

21NRM03 MEWS

D5 Report on the development of algorithms for new radio signal demodulation to determine the RF power of the resource grid allocation of new radio signals, inclusive of PSS, SSS and DM-RS contributions and the commissioning of a testbed for SI traceable measurements of the power in dBm of each resource element of the new radio resource grid with target uncertainties of 0.05 dB for conducted tests and 0.5 dB for over-the-air tests

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Glossary

BPSK:	Binary Phase Shift Keying
CORESET:	Control Resource Set
CP:	Cyclic Prefix
CRB:	Common Resource Blocks
CRC:	Cyclic Redundancy Check
DCI:	Downlink Control Information
DM-RS:	Demodulation Reference Signal
FDD:	Frequency Division Duplex
FFT:	Fast Fourier Transform
IFFT:	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
OFDM:	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
MIB:	Master Information Block
NR:	New Radio
PBCH:	Physical Broadcast Channel
PDCCH:	Physical Downlink Control Channel
PDSCH:	Physical Data Shared Channel
PSS:	Primary Synchronization Signal
QAM:	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
QPSK:	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
RB:	Resource Blocks
SCS:	Subcarrier Spacing
SDL:	Supplementary Downlink
SIB1:	System Information Block Type 1
SSB:	Synchronization Signal Block
SSS:	Secondary Synchronization Signal
SS/PBCH:	Synchronization Signal and Physical Broadcast Channel
TDL:	Time Division Duplex
UE:	User Equipment

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1 Summary

This document describes the full study on decoding RF downlink synchronization signals, whose measured powers are used for SI traceable measurements of 5G signals. The document first explains an algorithm to demodulate New Radio (NR) 5G Downlink transmission signals, including the Primary Synchronization Signal (PSS), Secondary Synchronization Signal (SSS) and Demodulation Reference Signal (DM-RS) as well as Master Information Block (MIB) and System Information Block Type 1 (SIB1) messages in order to retrieve the required information for obtaining the entire 5G NR resource grid.

Then, the software developed for RF power detection of New Radio (NR) 5G Downlink transmission signals is explained in detail including the coding on Mathematica. This application assumes the usage in laboratory environments where some predefined settings can be applied on the 5G NR signals under consideration.

Moreover, the evaluation of the 5G NR downlink transmission decoding algorithm together with the developed adapted testbed is provided in this document. The verification and the precision of the decoding are studied for different cases of transmission such as different 5G NR frequency range, center frequency, numerology and channel bandwidth using conducted methods. This study is then extended to cover over-the-air measurements.

In the final step, using the whole development mentioned previously, the measurement accuracy of two commercially available 5G measuring receivers are studied.

The main body of this document describes the overview of each step and all technical details are provided in the reports given in the annexes, which are composed progressively within the course of the project.

2 Algorithm Basics of New Radio Signal Demodulation

In order to obtain the entire resource grid of 5G NR downlink signals, a blind approach or an approach with some known configuration information can be employed. Both approaches are evaluated and the differences are studied in the project.

The important information to decode about the full resource grid is as follows:

- 1) Physical Cell ID
- 2) Position of the SSB in resource grid
- 3) Bandwidth of the transmission (i.e. channel bandwidth)
- 4) Subcarrier spacing of the data transmission (i.e. transmission numerology)

The algorithm proposed in this document consists of 8 steps as follows:

1. Detection of the frequency of SSB
2. Search and Detect PSS
3. Search and Detect SSS and Calculate Physical Cell ID
4. Transmission Channel Equalization
5. Search and Detect DM-RS for PBCH
6. Demodulate and Decode PBCH to obtain the MIB message
7. Interpretation of MIB message
8. Demodulating PDCCH and Decode DCI to obtain SIB1 information

It is important to note that this algorithm is applicable to a 5G NR downlink signal recording in baseband for a duration of at least 20 ms (i.e. to cover at least one full radio frame).

Each step of the algorithm enriched with some examples is explained in Annex A in detail.

3 Software Implementation of Demodulation Algorithm

The software implementation of the demodulation algorithm is explained in Annex B in detail. Just as an overview, the flowchart of the implementation can be depicted as follows:

Figure 1. Flowchart of software implementation

3.1 Input

This software can be used for a measurement setup where in-phase and quadrature (I and Q) data can be obtained for an IF band 5G NR downlink transmission recording. The input file having the file format such as ".csv" is to be input in the software. The input file must be a recording of the length of 20 ms so that it can include one full radio frame even in the worst case.

3.2 Function

The function "nrDecode" is implemented on Mathematica and defines the sequence of following procedures for decoding (which is a version of the given sequence in the report A3.1.2 "An Algorithm to Demodulate 5G New Radio Signals" in Section 3).

1. Search and Detect PSS
2. Search and Detect SSS and Calculate Physical Cell ID
3. Transmission Channel Equalization
4. Search and Detect DM-RS for PBCH
5. Calculate the power of all resource elements
6. Save the information in to a file

3.3 Output

The output file has ".csv" file format and lists the measured RF power of all resource elements (REs).

3.4 Information on the Software Implementation

The software implementation given in Annex B has the following structure:

Section 4.1 in Annex B lists the 5G NR configuration for the selected

1. numerology
2. frequency range (FR1 or FR2)
3. carrier frequency
4. channel bandwidth
5. IF Frequency
6. Filter Cut-off Frequency (to limit the noise)

Section 4.2 in Annex B is devoted for the determination of the critical transmission parameters, which are automatically calculated according to the configuration selected in Section 4.1.

Section 4.3 in Annex B lists all sub-functions used in the main function "nrDecode".

Section 4.4 in Annex B shows the implementation of "nrDecode".

Section 4.5 in Annex B is the implementation of the flowchart given in Figure 1.

Section 4.6 in Annex B lists additional functions to retrieve information from MIB and SIB1 messages about the *kSSB* and *offsetToPointA*.

4 Testbed for 5G NR Decoding and RF Power Measurements

The testbed for the demodulation of 5G NR downlink transmission to detect the RF power of signals of interest consists of two modules: Hardware and Software Modules (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the Measurement Setup

In Annex C, each of these modules are explained in detail. Moreover, the verification and the precision of the decoding are studied for 4 different cases of transmission (defined as scenarios) such as different 5G NR frequency range, center frequency, numerology and channel bandwidth. Moreover, the robustness of the RF power detection is also studied by applying 19 different fading scenarios to the 5G NR transmission signals. With the help of these 23 scenarios, all the aspects of the decoding algorithm could be examined.

Additionally, the SI-traceability of the measurements is also established using a calibrated components and the corresponding measurement uncertainty is estimated. The results in Annex C show that the goal uncertainty of 0.05 dB is reached.

5 Testbed for Over-the-air 5G NR Measurements for Decoding and RF Power Detection

In Annex D, the study is extended to traceable, over-the-air measurements of 5G downlink transmission signal. As an overview, the block diagram of the measurement setups for FR1 and FR2 are given in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively.

Figure 3. Final Measurement Setup for FR1

Figure 4. Final Measurement Setup for FR2

The verification and the precision of the decoding are repeated for the over-the-air measurements together with the study on SI-traceability and the estimation of the measurement uncertainty. Together with all the steps for the development, it is shown in Annex D that the goal uncertainty of 0.5 dB is reached.

6 SI-Traceable Calibration of 5G Measuring Receivers

In the study given in Annex E, the SI traceable calibration of two commercially available 5G measuring receivers are presented (See Figure 5).

1) Deviser EM860 (with 5G Option)

2) Narda SRM 3006 (with 5G Option)

Figure 5. Selected 5G Measuring Receiver Products

The methods from Section 4 are used to generate SI traceable 5G downlink synchronization signals and also to determine the precision of the SSS power detection of these devices by means of a calibration. The measurement uncertainties are also obtained with the development in Section 4.

In Annex E, in addition to the methodology and the numerical values, the calibration certificates of these receivers are also presented. With these developments, SI traceable calibration of 5G measuring receivers can be provided for 5G NR SSS power detection precision as a commercial service.

ANNEX A

21NRM03 MEWS - Metrology for emerging wireless standards

An Algorithm to Demodulate 5G New Radio Signals

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1 Introduction

This document describes an algorithm to demodulate New Radio (NR) 5G Downlink transmission signals, including the Primary Synchronization Signal (PSS), Secondary Synchronization Signal (SSS) and Demodulation Reference Signal (DM-RS) as well as Master Information Block (MIB) and System Information Block Type 1 (SIB1) messages in order to retrieve the required information for obtaining the entire 5G NR resource grid.

2 Abbreviations

CORESET: Control Resource Set

CP: Cyclic Prefix

CRB: Common Resource Blocks

CRC: Cyclic Redundancy Check

DCI: Downlink Control Information

DM-RS: Demodulation Reference Signal

FFT: Fast Fourier Transform

IFFT: Inverse Fast Fourier Transform

OFDM: Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing

MIB: Master Information Block

PBCH: Physical Broadcast Channel

PDCCH: Physical Downlink Control Channel

PDSCH: Physical Data Shared Channel

PSS: Primary Synchronization Signal

QAM: Quadrature Amplitude Modulation

QPSK: Quadrature Phase Shift Keying

RB: Resource Blocks

SCS: Subcarrier Spacing

SIB1: System Information Block Type 1

SSB: Synchronization Signal Block

SSS: Secondary Synchronization Signal

SS/PBCH: Synchronization Signal and Physical Broadcast Channel

UE: User Equipment

3 Algorithm Basics

In order to obtain the entire resource grid of 5G NR downlink signals, a blind approach or an approach with some known configuration information can be employed. In this document, both approaches are evaluated and the differences are explained.

The important information to decode about the full resource grid is as follows:

- 1) Physical Cell ID
- 2) Position of the SSB in resource grid
- 3) Bandwidth of the transmission (i.e. channel bandwidth)
- 4) Subcarrier spacing of the data transmission (i.e. transmission numerology)

The algorithm proposed in this document consists of 8 steps as follows:

1. Detection of the frequency of SSB
2. Search and Detect PSS
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4. Transmission Channel Equalization
5. Search and Detect DM-RS for PBCH
6. Demodulate and Decode PBCH to obtain the MIB message
7. Interpretation of MIB message
8. Demodulating PDCCH and Decode DCI to obtain SIB1 information

It is important to note that this algorithm is applicable to a 5G NR downlink signal recording in baseband for a duration of at least 20 ms (i.e. to cover at least one full radio frame).

Each step will be followed in the next sections.

Note: It is advisable to read first [1] before this document as the basics of 5G NR signals and corresponding important parameters are explained there.

4 Detection of the frequency of SSB

Before tuning to the frequency of Synchronization Signal Block (SSB), one critical parameter to obtain is the subcarrier spacing (SCS) of the SSB. During the cell search, SCS of SSB for an operating band is given and must be applied correctly (See Annex B of [1]).

After the SCS of SSB is decided, the possible center frequency of SSB is to be found. As given in Chapter 6.2 in [1], 5G NR employs a grid structure for the center frequency of the SSB. The Global Synchronization Channel Number (GSCN) is defined to describe the exact position of the SSB. Table 5.4.3.3-1 of ETSI TS 138 104 lists all possible SCSs for SSB and Range of GSCNs for all operating bands [2].

When a blind approach (i.e., standalone synchronization) is used, a lookup table of the possible frequency of SSB can be prepared for any given NR operating band [1]. Since the whole SSB should be within the bandwidth of the operating band, the possible center frequencies that cannot satisfy this requirement, are also removed from the list [1]. By searching for PSS (explained in Section 5) on the remaining frequencies and detecting the highest correlation, the frequency of the SSB can be determined.

This step is otherwise omitted if the configuration is known, which is typically the case for the tests in a laboratory environment.

5 Searching and Detecting PSS

The successful detection of PSS can be obtained by applying the following steps to the signal recording:

- 1) Generation of all PSS sequences
- 2) Deciding on the FFT size
- 3) Mapping to the subcarriers
- 4) Obtaining time domain candidate signals
- 5) Applying correlation to the signal record
- 6) Applying the time synchronization

5.1 Generation of all PSS sequences

As mentioned in Chapter 7.2 in [1], the sequence to define PSS can have three possible values. Each of these sequences of length of 127 must be correctly generated.

5.2 Deciding on the FFT Size

Before mapping to the subcarriers, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) size (N_{FFT}) must be defined. As explained in Chapter 3.1 in [1], OFDM time symbols are generated using Inverse FFT (IFFT) and the size of this transform is crucial. For different operating bands and numerologies, the suggested FFT sizes are given in Chapter 5.4 in [1].

5.3 Mapping PSS to the subcarriers

As given in Chapter 6.1 in [1], PSS is located in OFDM symbol number 0 (relative to the start of an SS/PBCH block) on the subcarriers having indexes from 56 to 182. Therefore, the generated sequences in Section 5.1 must be mapped on the corresponding subcarriers in ascending order.

The subcarriers with indexes 0 to 55 and 183 to 239 on this OFDM symbol are set to 0 [1].

These 240 values are assigned to the 240 subcarriers centered around the mid of N_{FFT} , completing the subcarrier mapping. The generated OFDM symbol of length N_{FFT} is depicted in Figure 1. Such generation of OFDM symbols should be repeated for each possible PSS sequence.

Figure 1. OFDM symbol structure of length N_{FFT}

5.4 Obtaining possible PSS signals in time domain

For each OFDM symbol obtained in Section 5.3, IFFT is applied and the time domain signals are obtained.

5.5 Applying correlation to signal record

The signals obtained in Section 5.4 must be correlated with the recorded signal. The index of the possible PSS signal with the highest correlation value gives the information on $N_{ID}^{(2)}$, which is required to calculate Physical Cell ID.

Moreover, the sample with the highest correlation value shows the start of the PSS symbol, which accomplishes the timing synchronization.

An example is shown in Figure 2 for the case of 8 SSBs. $N_{ID}^{(2)} = 0$ yields the highest correlation values with 8 peaks, indicating the start of PSSs in every SSB.

Figure 2. Example output of correlation for different $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ with 8 SSBs

5.6 Applying time synchronization

The first sample with the highest peak in Section 5.5 marks the start of OFDM Symbol 0 relative to the SS/PBCH block under concern. According to Table 15 in [1], this symbol can have either the index 2 or 4 for Case A & Case C and Case B, respectively.

Assuming this symbol has either the index 2 or 4 in the recording, the recorded samples before the symbol having index 0 can therefore be discarded so that only the radio frame with full recoverable information is further processed. In this way, the timing synchronization is achieved.

6 Searching and Detecting SSS and Calculating Physical Cell ID

After successful detecting $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ and achieving timing synchronization, SSS can be detected by applying the following steps to the signal recording, in a similar way to PSS:

- 1) Generation of all SSS sequences based on detected $N_{ID}^{(2)}$
- 2) Mapping to the subcarriers
- 3) Obtaining time domain candidate signals
- 4) Applying correlation to signal record to get $N_{ID}^{(1)}$
- 5) Calculating physical cell ID

6.1 Generation of all SSS sequences based on detected $N_{ID}^{(2)}$

As mentioned in Chapter 7.3 in [1], the sequence to define the PSS can have 1008 (336×3) possible values. Once $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ is detected, the selection narrows down to 336. Each of these 336 sequences having a length of 127 must be correctly generated.

6.2 Mapping to the subcarriers

Mapping to the subcarriers is the same as given for PSS in Section 5.3.

6.3 Obtaining time domain candidate signals

Obtaining the time domain candidate signals is the same as described for PSS in Section 5.4.

6.4 Applying correlation to signal record to get $N_{ID}^{(1)}$

The signals obtained in Section 6.3 must be correlated with the recorded signal. Since SSS is placed two symbols after PSS, the start of its exact location after PSS can be calculated as

$$SSS \text{ Start Sample index} = 2 \times N_{FFT} + 2 \times CP_{short} \quad (1)$$

For $N_{FFT} = 4096$, the cyclic prefix for short symbols (CP_{short}) is equal to 288, which makes $SSS \text{ Start Sample index} = 8768$ samples after PSS. For such a case, a window of 15000 samples shall be taken for correlation calculation.

The index of the candidate signal with the highest correlation value gives the information on $N_{ID}^{(1)}$. An example is shown in Figure 3. $N_{ID}^{(1)}$ value of 83 and the sample at 8768 give the highest correlation.

Figure 3. Example output of correlation for different $N_{ID}^{(1)}$ and the position within the recorded samples

6.5 Calculating physical cell ID

Physical Cell ID is calculated as

$$N_{ID}^{cell} = 3 \times N_{ID}^{(1)} + N_{ID}^{(2)} \quad (2)$$

For the examples given in Figure 2 and Figure 3,

$$N_{ID}^{cell} = 3 \times N_{ID}^{(1)} + N_{ID}^{(2)} = 3 \times 83 + 0 = 249 \quad (3)$$

This procedure can be repeated, when needed, for each SS/PBCH block for beam sweeping.

7 Transmission Channel Equalization

The effect of the transmission channel must be corrected before the next steps. For this purpose, the measured and the ideal values for PSS or SSS can be used. This method here proposes the use of PSS for this purpose. The following steps can be followed to obtain channel equalization:

- 1) Data partitioning to obtain time domain symbols and slots
- 2) Remove cyclic prefix and extract data
- 3) Extract measured PSS
- 4) Channel Estimation using Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE)
- 5) Extrapolation to cover the whole transmission bandwidth
- 6) Additional channel correction if needed
- 7) Obtaining equalized data symbols

7.1 Data partitioning to obtain time domain symbols and slots

The data needs to be partitioned to obtain the slots and the subframes. It is known that each slot has 14 symbols and the number of slots per subframe depends on the numerology (See Chapter 4.4 in [1]).

The length of the symbols in time domain depends on the index of the symbol because the cyclic prefix changes depending on the symbol index. Each symbol has the length of L_{symbol} samples where

$$L_{symbol} = N_{FFT} + CP \quad (4)$$

Cyclic Prefix (CP) is longer for symbols with index 0 or $7 \times 2^{(\mu-1)}$ (μ being the numerology of SSB) (See Chapter 4.5 in [1]).

The partition of the symbols and then to the slots should be performed accordingly.

7.2 Remove cyclic prefix and extract data

From each time domain symbol, CP must be removed from each symbol correctly to obtain the symbol length of N_{FFT} .

7.3 Extract measured PSS

The equalization method proposed here is based on PSS; therefore, the measured PSS must be extracted. For this purpose, the time domain signal corresponding to the PSS (i.e. from the starting sample obtained in Section 5.6 and having a length of N_{FFT}) is isolated from the sequence. Its frequency domain representation is obtained by applying FFT.

7.4 Channel Estimation using MMSE

When the ideal and the measured PSSs under concern are obtained, the effect of the transmission channel can be estimated. This estimation could be done using Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) based equalization. The measured PSS is divided by the ideal PSS in the frequency domain complex plane and MMSE-based data fitting is applied to obtain the equalization parameters. Most mathematical modeling and calculation platforms such as MATLAB, Mathematica or Python have the corresponding functions for this purpose.

An example is given in Figure 4 for the output of the phase correction.

Figure 4. Phase correction based on measurement vs. MMSE-based estimation

A similar application can be performed for frequency correction. The frequency correction procedure is not detailed further here. The application in a laboratory environment would enable a perfect clock synchronization of the measurement equipment, which typically eliminates the need for frequency correction.

7.5 Extrapolation to cover the whole transmission bandwidth

The MMSE-based correction obtained in Section 7.4 is then extrapolated to cover the entire transmission bandwidth. In the case of the blind search, it is extended just to cover the SS/PBCH block. The information on the transmission bandwidth is obtained in the following steps.

7.6 Apply channel estimation on extracted data

The correction parameters obtained in Section 7.5 are applied to the extracted data obtained in Section 7.2.

7.7 Additional channel correction if needed

Additional channel correction may be needed if the perfect equalization is not obtained, for instance, due to imperfections in the instrumentation. Annex A – Possible Equalization

Problems lists some problems which may occur during this procedure and explains their reasons.

7.8 Obtaining equalized data symbols

When the equalization is achieved, the data symbols are successfully obtained. An example is shown in

Figure 5 for 4-QAM.

Figure 5. 4-QAM data symbols obtained after equalization

For some applications, the power of the PSS or SSS can be of interest. In this case, the average absolute value of the complex symbols from a constellation point can be used to measure the power of such signals (See Figure 6).

Figure 6. Average power P of selected symbols

8 Search and Detect DM-RS for PBCH

After obtaining the Cell ID and successfully equalizing the OFDM symbols, PBCH can be investigated and the message symbols can be obtained by applying the following steps to the signal recording:

- 1) Demodulating the received OFDM symbols
- 2) Generation of DM-RS for PBCH sequence based on detected Cell ID and L_{\max}
- 3) Parsing of PBCH signal to get the sequence
- 4) Check if PBCH-DMRS is present and successfully detected
- 5) Obtaining the message symbols on PBCH

Note: This algorithm involves the decoding of a whole radio frame, where the indexes of the detected SS/PBCH block are known. However, a UE may not have such information during blind searching and it should detect the index of the SS/PBCH block by checking the Demodulation Reference Signal (DM-RS) in PBCH.

In this algorithm, it is not obligatory to perform the steps 8.2 to 8.4, but it is a way to check the correctness of the PBCH block and the decoding algorithm.

8.1 Demodulating the received OFDM symbols

The OFDM symbols are complex numbers with equal amplitude and are placed according to their phases in the complex plane (See Figure 5 for 4-QAM). Demodulation for this case and obtaining the bit information is given below and illustrated in Figure 7:

$$Symbol = \begin{cases} 00 & \text{if } 0 < Arg \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \\ 01 & \text{if } \frac{\pi}{2} < Arg \leq \pi \\ 11 & \text{if } \pi < Arg \leq \frac{3\pi}{2} \\ 10 & \text{if } \frac{3\pi}{2} < Arg \leq 2\pi \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 7. 4-QAM Demodulation

8.2 Generation of all DM-RS for PBCH sequence based on detected Cell ID

In order to generate all DM-RS for the PBCH sequence, the Physical Cell ID and the SS/PBCH burst structure must be known. The maximum number of candidate SS/PBCH blocks within the SS Burst Set is denoted as L_{\max} . Chapter 6.1 of [1] explains how L_{\max} is decided based on subcarrier spacing (SCS) and operation frequency. All the candidate DM-RS signals for PBCH are generated accordingly (See Chapter 7.4 of [1] for the generation of DM-RS signals for PBCH).

8.3 Parsing of PBCH signal to get the DM-RS sequence

Chapter 6.1 of [1] explains on which subcarriers and OFDM symbols the PBCH signal is located relative to the start of an SS/PBCH Block. The PBCH sequence must be obtained from these subcarriers, which includes also the DM-RS.

8.4 Check if PBCH-DMRS is present and successfully detected

The corresponding DM-RS signals at the expected locations from the recorded symbols must be checked and verified with the candidates from Section 8.2. The sequence giving the best match denotes SSB index number.

8.5 Obtaining the message symbols on PBCH

After step 8.4, the subcarriers carrying the DMRS symbols are removed from the sequence and the information on the remaining subcarriers of the PBCH having higher-level information can be further decoded. It is a bit sequence of length 864.

9 Demodulate and Decode PBCH to obtain MIB Message

As mentioned in Chapter 9.5 in [1], if the transmission parameters (such as the operating band, transmission bandwidth, etc.) are known, then the steps so far are enough to obtain the entire resource grid.

For the blind approach, additional steps are required to obtain the resource grid. As SSBs are not placed in the middle of the available bandwidth, the bandwidth and its starting frequency must be obtained. For this purpose, two parameters are essential: k_{SSB} and *OffsetToPointA*. The details on these parameters are given in Chapter 6.2 in [1]. The Master Information Block (MIB) must be decoded to obtain the parameter k_{SSB} and the SIB1 (System Information Block 1) must be decoded to obtain the parameter *OffsetToPointA*.

MIB information is stored in the BCH data, which is located in the PBCH and SIB1 is stored in the PDCCH. After obtaining MIB data, the position of PDCCH can be obtained.

The Broadcast Channel Data (BCH) can be obtained from the PBCH data as given in Figure 8.

The output of Section 8.5 corresponds to the input sequence $\tilde{b}(0), \tilde{b}(1), \dots, \tilde{b}(M_{bit} - 1)$ in the flowchart given in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Processing BCH data to obtain PBCH (All the steps are given with the corresponding standard references)

In order to obtain MIB Message, the following steps can be followed:

- 1) Descrambling of PBCH
- 2) Rate matching removal
- 3) Channel Decoding
- 4) Removing checksum
- 5) Descrambling
- 6) Obtaining payload BCH data

9.1 Descrambling of PBCH [3, Chapter 7.3.3.1]

The output sequence of Section 8.5 $\tilde{b}(0), \tilde{b}(1), \dots, \tilde{b}(M_{bit} - 1)$ of length 864 is scrambled according to Chapter 7.3.3.1 in [3]. It must be descrambled accordingly. Please see the details in [3] Chapter 7.3.3.1 for the implementation. The output of this section is denoted as $b(0), b(1), \dots, b(M_{bit} - 1)$. It is denoted as f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{E-1} for $E = 864$.

9.2 Removal of the rate matching [4, Chapter 7.1.5]

Rate matching is applied to increase the series length from 512 to 864. Chapter 7.1.5 in [4] explains the details of the rate-matching implementation. The reversal of this procedure must be accomplished to obtain the sequence d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{N-1} for $N = 512$.

9.3 Channel Decoding [4, Chapter 7.1.4]

Channel coding is based on polar coding. This complex procedure is given in Chapter 7.1.4 in [4]. To obtain the decoded channel information, this procedure must be reversed. The implementation details are not given here. Please refer to the reference mentioned above for details.

The output of this step is denoted as c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{K-1} for $K = 56$.

9.4 Checksum Removal [4, Chapter 7.1.3]

A checksum based on Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) is placed in the sequence c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{K-1} . The calculation principles are given in Chapter 7.1.3 in [4].

The first 32 bits of the sequence c_0, c_1, \dots, c_{K-1} are the payload whereas the last 24 bits belong to CRC. Therefore, this part has to be removed to obtain the sequence $a'_0, a'_1, \dots, a'_{A-1}$ for $A = 32$.

9.5 Descrambling [4, Chapter 7.1.2]

Referring to Chapter 7.1.2 in [4], the sequence $a'_0, a'_1, \dots, a'_{A-1}$ must undergo the corresponding descrambling so that the sequence a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{A-1} can be obtained.

9.6 Obtaining the Payload (i.e. MIB Message) [4, Chapter 7.1.1]

The sequence a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{A-1} is the output of one last interleaving, whose details are given in Chapter 7.1.1 in [4]. The output sequence $\bar{a}_0, \bar{a}_1, \dots, \bar{a}_{A-1}$ for $A = 32$ is the MIB Message. Its interpretation is given in the next chapter.

10 Interpretation of MIB Message

10.1 Structure of MIB Message [5, Chapter 6.2.2]

The bit mapping of the MIB Message is as follows:

Part of the Message	Length (bits)	Type	Explanation
$\bar{a}_0, \bar{a}_1, \dots, \bar{a}_5, \bar{a}_{24}, \bar{a}_{25}, \bar{a}_{26}, \bar{a}_{27}$	10	Integer	System Frame Number
\bar{a}_6	1	Enumerated	Subcarrier spacing common
$\bar{a}_7, \bar{a}_8, \bar{a}_9, \bar{a}_{10}, \bar{a}_{29}, \bar{a}_{30}, \bar{a}_{31}$	7	Integer	SSB subcarrier offset
\bar{a}_{11}	1	Enumerated	DMRS Type A position
$\bar{a}_{12}, \bar{a}_{13}, \dots, \bar{a}_{19}$	8	Integer	PDCCH config SIB1
\bar{a}_{20}	1	Enumerated	Cell Barred
\bar{a}_{21}	1	Enumerated	Intrafreq Reselection
\bar{a}_{22}	1	Bit String	Spare
\bar{a}_{23}	1	Enumerated	BCCH-BCH Message Type Indication
\bar{a}_{28}	1	Enumerated	Half frame bit

Table 1. Components of MIB message and their explanations

The explanations of the relevant components of MIB message are as follows:

- System Frame Number: It provides the current System Frame Number (SFN). 6 Most Significant Bits (MSB) are given for the first 6 bits. It is listed in Table 1 together with the remaining 4 LSB.
- Subcarrier Spacing Common: It defines the subcarrier spacing to be used for the reception of SIB 1. "0" means the subcarrier spacing of SIB1 is either 15 kHz for FR1 and 60 kHz for FR2. "1" means the subcarrier spacing of SIB1 is either 30 kHz for FR1 or 120 kHz for FR2.
- SSB subcarrier Offset: The subcarrier offset k_{SSB} . It is important to note that if k_{SSB} is larger than 23, SIB1 message is not present.
- DMRS Type A position: It specifies the first symbol used by the Demodulation Reference Signal (DMRS) when using 'Mapping Type A'. This information element is applicable to the DMRS for both the PDSCH and PUSCH. "0" means Position 2. "1" means Position 3.
- Cell Barred: A UE is not permitted to complete cell selection nor cell reselection onto a cell which is barred so this column is to indicate the "cellbarred" (Value "0") or "notbarred" (Value "1").
- IntraFreq Reselection: This is applicable when the current cell is to be treated as barred. A value of 'allowed' (i.e. Value "0") indicates that the UE is permitted to reselect another cell on the same frequency.
- PDCCH config SIB1: This field is used to configure Control Resource Set 0 (CORESET#0) and search space#0 (of the initial BWP) which is the most important information the UE

should know in order to monitor for scheduling (PDCCH) of SIB1 (See next section).

10.2 PDCCH config SIB1

It is a message consisting of 8 bits. 4 MSBs are called ControlResourceSetZero and define a CORESET for each of the following cases:

Case	SSB SCS (kHz)	PDCCH SCS (kHz)	Min BW (MHz) [7]	Table [6]
1	15	15	5	38.213 – Table 13-1
2	15	30	5	38.213 – Table 13-2
3	30	15	5 or 10	38.213 – Table 13-3
4	30	30	5 or 10	38.213 – Table 13-4
5	30	15	40	38.213 – Table 13-5
6	30	30	40	38.213 – Table 13-6
7	120	60	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-7
8	120	120	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-8
9	240	60	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-9
10	240	120	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-10

Table 2. Lookup table for different SCS cases (See [6] and [7] for details)

The 4 LSBs are called SearchSpaceZero and determine PDCCH Monitoring Occasion for each of the following cases:

Case	CORESET Multiplexing Pattern	Frequency Range	SSB SCS (kHz)	PDCCH SCS (kHz)	Table [6]
1	Pattern 1	FR1	N/A	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-11
2	Pattern 1	FR2	N/A	N/A	38.213 – Table 13-12
3	Pattern 2	N/A	120	60	38.213 – Table 13-13
4	Pattern 2	N/A	240	120	38.213 – Table 13-14

Table 3. Lookup table for different CORESET Multiplexing Patterns, Frequency Ranges and SCSs for SSB and PDCCH

To illustrate the interpretation, an example is given in the following paragraph.

Ex: Given SSB SCS = 30 kHz, PDCCH SCS = 30 kHz, PDCCH config SIB1 = 0 (i.e. "00000000") and the operation band is n78.

The SCSs of SSB and PDCCH yield cases 4 or 6 in Table 2. From [7] Table 5.3.5-1, the minimum bandwidth for the operation band n78 is 10 MHz. Therefore, the selection would be the Case 4 from Table 2. In this case, Table 13-4 of [6] must be considered (See Table 4).

Index	SS/PBCH block and CORESET Multiplexing Pattern	Number of RBs $N_{RB}^{CORESET}$	Number of Symbols $N_{symb}^{CORESET}$	Offset (RBs)
0	1	24	2	0
1	1	24	2	1
2	1	24	2	2
3	1	24	2	3
4	1	24	2	4
5	1	24	3	0
6	1	24	3	1
7	1	24	3	2
8	1	24	3	3
9	1	24	3	4
10	1	48	1	12
11	1	48	1	14
12	1	48	1	16
13	1	48	2	12
14	1	48	2	14
15	1	48	2	16

Table 4. Table 13-4 of 38.213 [6]

As the PDCCH config SIB1 message is 0, its 4 MSBs (i.e. ControlResourceSetZero) are also "0000", giving the index 0 to be looked up in Table 4. This means, for the given case:

Parameter	Value
SS/PBCH block and CORESET Multiplexing Pattern	1
Number of RBs ($N_{RB}^{CORESET}$)	24
Number of Symbols ($N_{symb}^{CORESET}$)	2
Offset (RBs)	0

Table 5. Detected values for the given example

As the SS/PBCH block and CORESET Multiplexing Pattern are found out to be 1 and the operation band n78 is in FR1, this corresponds to the Case 1 in Table 3. In this case, the table 13-11 of [6] must be considered.

As the PDCCH config SIB1 message is 0, its 4 LSBs (i.e. SearchSpaceZero) are also "0000", giving the index 0 to be looked up in Table 6.

Index	O	Number of search space sets per slot	M	First symbol index
0	0	1	1	0
1	0	2	1/2	{0, if i is even}, { $N_{RB}^{CORESET}$, if i is odd}
2	2	1	1	0
3	2	2	1/2	{0, if i is even}, { $N_{RB}^{CORESET}$, if i is odd}
4	5	1	1	0
5	5	2	1/2	{0, if i is even}, { $N_{RB}^{CORESET}$, if i is odd}
6	7	1	1	0
7	7	2	1/2	{0, if i is even}, { $N_{RB}^{CORESET}$, if i is odd}
8	0	1	2	0
9	5	1	2	0
10	0	1	1	1
11	0	1	1	2
12	2	1	1	1
13	2	1	1	2
14	5	1	1	1
15	5	1	1	2

Table 6. Table 13-11 of 38.213 [6]

In this case, the PDCCH carrying SIB1 has the following relevant parameters:

Parameter	Value
First Symbol Index	0
Number of RBs ($N_{RB}^{CORESET}$)	24
Number of Symbols ($N_{sym}^{CORESET}$)	2
Offset (RBs)	0

Table 7. Parameters for PDCCH in the resource grid for the given example

PDCCH is located on the OFDM symbol index number 0, its length is 24 RBs (i.e. 288 subcarriers) in the frequency domain and 2 symbols in the time domain. It has 0 RBs offset relative to SSB. In such a case, the location of PDCCH in the resource grid is given in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Locations of PDCCH, PSS, SSS and PBCH in the resource grid for given example

The location of PDCCH is found (on symbols 0 and 1, each having 24 RBs and offset being 0 relative to the SSB) and can be processed further to obtain the SIB1 Message.

11 Demodulating PDCCH and Decode DCI to obtain SIB1 Information

The time and frequency domain location of PDCCH is determined in Chapter 10.

PDCCH also includes Demodulation Reference Signals (DM-RS) incorporated into some of its subcarriers. The generation of this DM-RS and mapping to the resources are given in [3] Chapter 7.4.1.3. The DM-RS must be removed to obtain only the information bits.

PDCCH carries CORESET0. See Annex B for a better understanding of the structure of CORESETs in general.

11.1 Obtaining DCI Message

CORESET0 bits denoted as $\tilde{b}(0), \tilde{b}(1), \dots, \tilde{b}(M_{bit} - 1)$ must be processed to obtain the Scheduling data (i.e. DCI Data). The steps are given in the flowchart depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Processing PDCCH to obtain DCI (All the steps are given with the corresponding standard references)

DCI is a very critical message carrying essential messages. It can carry the information to schedule Downlink Data (PDSCH) and Uplink Data (PUSCH) and also to adjust Uplink Power (PUSCH, PUCCH power) for power control.

It has different types which can be used for various purposes (See [4] Table 7.3.1-1 for DCI

Formats). For SIB1, the DCI format "Format 1_0" scrambled with SI_RNTI (given as 65535 in Table 7.1-1 of [8]) is employed.

11.2 Decoding DCI to obtain SIB1 and *OffsetToPointA*

In order to obtain the SIB1 message and therefore *OffsetToPointA*, first, the configuration of the Physical Data Shared Channel (PDSCH) is obtained. After that, the flowchart given in Figure 11 can be followed to obtain the SIB1 message:

Figure 11. Processing of DCI to obtain SIB1 Data

SIB1 message contains large amount of data regarding different parameters. In order to obtain *OffsetToPointA*, the following chart can be followed (see Figure 12):

Figure 12. SIB1 message format and location of *OffsetToPointA* [5, Chapter 6.2.2]

After decoding the SIB1 message, the component corresponding to *OffsetToPointA* can be obtained and the size of the full resource grid can be detected.

12 Discussion on the Implementation of the Algorithm

The steps starting from Section 9 are mostly bit-level complex mathematical calculations for different channels (i.e. different parts of the resource grid) to obtain the channel bandwidth of a given transmission. The physical layer considerations (including PSS, SSS and PBCH) would be more interesting for the metrological applications.

This algorithm can thus be shortened if there is prior information on the channel bandwidth. In a typical laboratory environment, the configuration of the resource grid can be selected freely. So, there would be no need to detect k_{SSB} and *OffsetToPointA*. Moreover, if a normal transmission from a base station is to be measured, channel bandwidth can be agreed on with the operator. In such cases, the algorithm steps up to Section 8 can be used.

A sample usage of this algorithm can be the calibration of 5G NR receivers. There, the calibration method can be based on measuring a specific signal such as PSS or SSS, which is always present in 5G NR transmissions. The power level of such signals and the frequency response can be measured and characterized.

13 References

- [1] Emrah Tas, Frederic Pythoud, *"Review of 5G NR ETSI TS 138 211 for Key Parameters for the Identification of the RF Power of the Resource Grid Allocation"*, 21NRM03 MEWS A3.1.1, May 31, 2023.
- [2] ETSI TS 138 104 5G NR Base Station (BS) radio transmission and reception (3GPP TS 38.104 version 17.9.0 Release 17), 2023-05.
- [3] ETSI TS 138 211 5G NR Physical channels and modulation (3GPP TS 38.211 version 17.4.0 Release 17), 2023-01.
- [4] ETSI TS 138 212 5G NR Multiplexing and channel coding (3GPP TS 38.212 version 17.4.0 Release 17), 2023-01.
- [5] ETSI TS 138 331 5G NR Radio resource control (3GPP TS 38.331 version 17.6.0 Release 17), 2023-10
- [6] ETSI TS 138 213 5G NR Physical layer procedures for control (3GPP TS 38.213 version 17.4.0 Release 17), 2023-01.
- [7] ETSI TS 138 101-1 5G NR User Equipment (UE) radio transmission and reception; Part 1: Range 1 Standalone (3GPP TS 38.101-1 version 17.8.0 Release 17), 2023-01.
- [8] ETSI TS 138 321 5G NR Medium Access Control (MAC) protocol specification (3GPP TS 38.321 version 17.0.0 Release 17), 2022-05.
- [9] <https://5g.smarttelecomedu.com/5g-nr-control-resource-set-coreset/>
- [10] https://www.sharetechnote.com/html/5G/5G_ResourceAllocationUnit.html

Annex A – Possible Equalization Problems

The channel equalization may not be successful due to many factors. The reasons for these problems are worth mentioning here.

If the equalization is not performed, the data symbols are randomly distributed in the constellation diagram and there is no clustering (See Figure 13).

Figure 13. Constellation diagram if the equalization is not performed

If the phase correction is not successful, then even though the symbols are clustered, their positions on the constellation diagram may not be correct (See Figure 14).

Figure 14. Unsuccessful phase correction

If the frequency synchronization is not successful, the symbols rotate in the complex plane with a speed directly proportional to the frequency difference between the source and the measurement chain as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Data symbols in the complex plane if frequency synchronization is not successful

Annex B – CORESET Structure

CORESET is a set of physical resources and parameters to carry DCI. 5G NR PDCCH can transmit configurable CORESET. It creates a flexible transmission possibility including time, frequency, numerologies and operating points. In NR, a parameter is needed to define the frequency domain width for CORESET since the frequency domain width can be set in any value in the multiples of 6 RBs (See Figure 16).

Figure 16. Flexible Frequency Domain Resource Usage by CORESETs [9]

A CORESET is made up of multiple levels of sub-structures. A CORESET can accommodate multiple Aggregation Levels (see Table 8). An Aggregation Level comprises N Control Channel Element (CCE). A CCE is made up of 6 Resource Element Groups (REGs). A REG is made up of 1 RB and 1 OFDM Symbol. See Figure 17 for the visualization of different Aggregation Levels.

Aggregation Level	Number of CCEs
1	1
2	2
4	4
8	8
16	16

Table 8. Supported PDCCH aggregation levels [3, Table 7.3.2.1-1]

Figure 17. Illustration of different aggregation levels [10]

Different possible aggregation levels and their positions in the resource grid are given in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Different possible aggregation levels and their positions in the resource grid [10]

ANNEX B

21NRM03 MEWS - Metrology for emerging wireless standards

Software Implementation of RF Power Detection of 5G NR Downlink Transmission Signals

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1 Introduction

This document describes the software developed for RF power detection of New Radio (NR) 5G Downlink transmission signals and gives the detailed coding on Mathematica.

This software is the implementation of the algorithm defined in the activity A3.1.2, which is explained in detail in the document "An Algorithm to Demodulate 5G New Radio Signals" (available on the project share). Therefore, when needed, the reader is advised to consult that document for detailed explanation.

2 General Structure of the Software Implementation

The flowchart of the software implementation is as follows:

Figure 1. Flowchart of software implementation

2.1 Input

This software can be used for a measurement setup where in-phase and quadrature (I and Q) data can be obtained for an IF band 5G NR downlink transmission recording. The input file having the file format such as ".csv" is to be input in the software. The input file must be a recording of the length of 20 ms so that it can include one full radio frame even in the worst case.

2.2 Function

The function "nrDecode" is implemented on Mathematica and defines the sequence of following procedures for decoding (which is a version of the given sequence in the report A3.1.2 "An Algorithm to Demodulate 5G New Radio Signals" in Section 3).

1. Search and Detect PSS
2. Search and Detect SSS and Calculate Physical Cell ID
3. Transmission Channel Equalization
4. Search and Detect DM-RS for PBCH
5. Calculate the power of all resource elements
6. Save the information in to a file

2.3 Output

The output file has ".csv" file format and lists the measured RF power of all resource elements (REs).

3 Information on the Software Implementation

The software implementation given in Section 4 has the following structure:

Section 4.1 lists the 5G NR configuration for the selected

1. numerology
2. frequency range (FR1 or FR2)
3. carrier frequency
4. channel bandwidth
5. IF Frequency
6. Filter Cut-off Frequency (to limit the noise)

Section 4.2 is devoted for the determination of the critical transmission parameters, which are automatically calculated according to the configuration selected in Section 4.1.

Section 4.3 lists all sub-functions used in the main function "nrDecode".

Section 4.4 shows the implementation of "nrDecode".

Section 4.5 is the implementation of the flowchart given in Figure 1.

Section 4.6 lists additional functions to retrieve information from MIB and SIB1 messages about the *kSSB* and *offsetToPointA*.

Note: Subfunction in 4.3.17.2 in the implementation requires an additional file for the polar decoding. This is also provided in the project share as "PolarSequenceQ.csv".

4 Software

4.1. Configuration

```
(*Numerology*)
numerology = 1; (* For FR1,
numerology 0 and 1 is supported for cell search. For FR2,
only numerology 3 or higher is supported See TS 138.213 Chapter 4.1*)
(*Frequency Range*)
nrFR = 1; (* 1 is FR1,
2 is FR2. Important: FR2 only supports BW 50 MHz or higher*)
(* Operating Band *)
nrOperatingBand = "n78";
(*Carrier Frequency*)
nrFcar = 3500; (*MHz*)
(*Channel Bandwidth*)
nrCHBW = 20 M;
(*IF Frequency*)
nrIntermediateFrequency = 30 * 10^6;
(*Filter Cut-Off Frequency*)
nrFilterCutOffFrequency = nrCHBW;
```

4.2. Parameter Definitions

```
If[numerology == 2, Print["Numerology 2 is not supported for Cell Search"]];
nrSCS = 15 000 * 2^(numerology);
lengthRB = 12; (*Subcarriers*)
guardbandsscs15 =
    {242.5 k, 312.5 k, 382.5 k, 452.5 k, 522.5 k, 592.5 k, 552.5 k, 692.5 k};
guardbandsscs30 = {505 k, 665 k, 645 k, 805 k, 785 k, 945 k, 905 k, 1045 k};
guardbandsscs60 = {0, 1010 k, 990 k, 1330 k, 1310 k, 1290 k, 1610 k, 1570 k};
bandwidththlist = {5 M, 10 M, 15 M, 20 M, 25 M, 30 M, 40 M, 50 M};
indexfound = Position[bandwidththlist, nrCHBW][[1]][[1]];
guardbandfound =
    Which[numerology == 0, guardbandsscs15[[indexfound]], numerology == 1,
    guardbandsscs30[[indexfound]], numerology == 2, guardbandsscs60[[indexfound]];
nrNRBSC = Floor[(bandwidththlist[[indexfound]] - 2 * guardbandfound) / nrSCS / lengthRB];
(*Number of RB available*)
```

```

nrNLGSC = Ceiling[guardbandfound / nrSCS]; (*Left guard band*)
nrFreqHigh = nrFcar;
If[nrFR == 2, (* In FR2,
  our setup supports only 50 MHz Bandwidth with numerology 3*)
  nrNRBSC = 32; (* For CHBW 50 MHz and numerology 3*)
  guardbandfound = 1900;
  nrNLGSC = Ceiling[guardbandfound / nrSCS];
];
nrNRGSC = nrNLGSC - 1; (*Right guard band*)
nrNFFT = If[nrFR == 1 && numerology == 2, 2048, 4096]; (* Selection of FFT number *)
(*SSB Start OFDM Symbols according to numerology and carrier frequency*)
Which[nrFreqHigh ≤ 3000,
  PSSindexes = If[numerology == 0, {2, 8, 16, 22}, {4, 8, 16, 20}],
  nrFreqHigh > 3000,
  PSSindexes = If[numerology == 0,
    PSSindexes = {2, 8, 16, 22, 30, 36, 44, 50}, {4, 8, 16, 20, 32, 36, 44, 48}]
];
If[nrFR == 2, listn = {0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18};
  PSSindexes = Flatten[Map[# * 28 + {4, 8, 16, 20} &, listn]];
Lmax = Length[PSSindexes];

(*Frame Structure*)
nrSamplingTime = 1.0 / (nrSCS * nrNFFT);
nrSamplingRate = nrSCS * nrNFFT;
Ts = 1 / (15 000.0 * 2048);
(* Reference sampling time required for CP calculations*)
nrK = 64;
nrSymbolperSlot = 14;
nrSlotperSubFrame = 2 ^ numerology;
nrSymbolperSubFrame = nrSymbolperSlot * nrSlotperSubFrame;
nrSubFrameperRadioFrame = 10;
nrSymbolperRadioFrame = nrSymbolperSubFrame * nrSubFrameperRadioFrame;
nrSlotperRadioFrame = nrSlotperSubFrame * nrSubFrameperRadioFrame;
nrRadioFrameTime = 10.0 * 10 ^ -3;
nrSubFrameTime = nrRadioFrameTime / 10;
nrSlotTime = nrSubFrameTime / 2 ^ (numerology);
nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame = nrRadioFrameTime / nrSamplingTime;
nrNumSamplesinHalfRadioFrame = nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2;
nrSamplesperSubFrame = nrSubFrameTime / nrSamplingTime;

modOrder = 2;
(*Modulation*)
Which[modOrder == 2,

```

```

nrModulation = "QPSK",
modOrder = 4,
nrModulation = "16QAM",
modOrder = 8,
nrModulation = "64QAM"];

cyclicPrefix = 1;
(*Resource Structure*)
Which[cyclicPrefix == 1,
nrPrefixType = "CP";
nrCPTimeforLongSyms = ((144 * 2^(-numerology)) + 16) * Ts;
nrCPTimeforOtherSyms = (144 * 2^(-numerology)) * Ts,
cyclicPrefix == 2,
nrPrefixType = "ECP";
nrCPTimeforLongSyms = (512 * 2^(-numerology)) * Ts;
nrCPTimeforOtherSyms = (512 * 2^(-numerology)) * Ts;
];
nrSymbolTime = 2048 * Ts * 2^(-numerology);
nrSymbolLen = nrSymbolTime / nrSamplingTime;
nrCPLenforLongSyms = IntegerPart[nrCPTimeforLongSyms / nrSamplingTime];
nrCPLenforOtherSyms = IntegerPart[nrCPTimeforOtherSyms / nrSamplingTime];

lengthpss = 127;
lengthsss = 127;
lengthSSB = 20 * lengthRB;

If[numerology == 0, nrSlotLength = nrNFFT * nrSymbolperSlot +
nrCPLenforLongSyms * 2 + nrCPLenforOtherSyms * (nrSymbolperSlot - 2),
nrSlotLength = nrNFFT * nrSymbolperSlot + nrCPLenforLongSyms +
nrCPLenforOtherSyms * (nrSymbolperSlot - 1)];
samplesBetweenPSS = Map[(# - PSSindexes[[1]]) * nrSymbolLen +
nrCPLenforLongSyms * Floor[# / (7 * 2^numerology)] + nrCPLenforOtherSyms *
(# - PSSindexes[[1]] - Floor[# / (7 * 2^numerology))], PSSindexes[[2 ;; -1]]];
nrAntenna = 0;

nrPhysicalResourceblockBandwidth = nrNRBSC * nrSCS;
nrSSBSC = nrNRBSC * 12; (* Number of usable subcarriers in the band*)

```

4.3. Function Definitions

4.3.1 Gold Sequence Generation

```
Nc = 10;
Mpn = 50; (* Output Sequence Length *)
cinit = 2; (* Initial value for x2*)
x1start = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, 30]]; (*Length-31 Gold sequence*)
x2start = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, 30]]; (*Length-31 Gold sequence*)
x1 = Join[x1start, ConstantArray[0, Nc + Mpn + 31]];
cinitstringform =
  StringReverse[StringSplit[ToString[BaseForm[cinit, 2]], "\n"]][[1]];
For[i = 1, i < StringLength[cinitstringform] + 1, i++,
  x2start[[i]] = ToNumber[StringTake[cinitstringform, {i}]]]
x2 = Join[x2start, ConstantArray[0, Nc + Mpn + 31]];
cn = ConstantArray[0, Mpn]
For[n = 1, n < Mpn + Nc + 1, n++,
  x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];
  x2[[n + 31]] = Mod[x2[[n + 3]] + x2[[n + 2]] + x2[[n + 1]] + x2[[n]], 2];
]
For[n = 1, n < Mpn + 1, n++,
  cn[[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + Nc]] + x2[[n + Nc]], 2]
]
```

4.3.2 Scope Data Read

```
ScopeDataRead[waveformFilename_] :=
  ScopeDataRead[waveformFilename, FileRoot[waveformFilename, 2] <> ".wavedesc.csv"]
```

```

ScopeDataRead[waveformFilename_, wavedescriptionFilename_] := Module[{ok = True,
  binformat, channel, waveform, wavedesc, n, x0, dx, y0, dy, xvalues, yvalues},
  (* ----- Find the binary format and channel ----- *)
  binformat = StringCases[waveformFilename,
    __ ~~ "int" ~~ x : DigitCharacter .. ~~ "." ~~ __ => x];
  If[binformat === {}, ok = False, binformat = First[binformat]];

  channel = StringCases[FileExtensions[waveformFilename, 3],
    __ ~~ "C" ~~ x : DigitCharacter .. ~~ "." ~~ __ => x];
  If[channel === {}, ok = False, channel = First[channel]];

  (* ----- Reads the data and desc ----- *)
  If[ok,
    waveform = IEEEFileRead[waveformFilename, Format -> "Integer" <> binformat];
    wavedesc = FileGet[wavedescriptionFilename];
    If[Or[waveform === $Failed, wavedesc === $Failed], ok = False]];

  (* ----- Performs Scaling ----- *)
  If[ok,
    n = FileSearch[wavedesc, "points*",
      FindRange -> 2, NumberFlag -> True, ViewFlag -> False];
    x0 = FileSearch[wavedesc, "X_origin*", FindRange -> 2,
      NumberFlag -> True, ViewFlag -> False];
    dx = FileSearch[wavedesc, "X_interval*", FindRange -> 2,
      NumberFlag -> True, ViewFlag -> False];
    y0 = FileSearch[wavedesc, "Y_origin*", FindRange -> 2,
      NumberFlag -> True, ViewFlag -> False];
    dy = FileSearch[wavedesc, "Y_interval*", FindRange -> 2,
      NumberFlag -> True, ViewFlag -> False];

    xvalues = ColCreate[
      Range[0, Length[waveform] - 1] * dx + x0, ColName -> "Time", ColUnit -> "s"];
    yvalues = ColCreate[y0 + dy * waveform, ColName -> channel, ColUnit -> "V"];

  If[ok, {xvalues, yvalues}, $Failed]];

```

4.3.3 Plotting

4.3.3.1 Plotting: Time Domain

```
(* ----- Plot Data: Time Domain ----- *)
Options[nrTimePlot] = {N → 10 000.0};
nrTimePlot[time_, signal__List, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {max, min, ShowN},

  ShowN := If[Length[time] < OptionValue[N], Length[time] - 1, OptionValue[N]];

  max = Max[Abs[{signal}]];
  min = -max;

  Manipulate[
    ListPlot[
      Map[Transpose[{Take[time, {i, i + ShowN}] - time[[i]], Take[#, {i, i + ShowN}]}]
        &, {signal}],
      Joined → True, PlotRange → {min, max} * 1.1
    ],
    {i, 1, Length[time] - ShowN, 1}
  ]
];
```

4.3.3.2 Plotting: Frequency Domain

```
(* ----- Plot Scope
Data: Frequency Domain ----- *)
Options[nrFrequencyPlot] = {StartValue → 1.0, StopValue → 100 000.0,
  CenterFrequency → nrIntermediateFrequency, FrequencyRange → 20 M};
nrFrequencyPlot[time_, signal__List, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {startSample, endSample, sampleTime, sampleSignals, freqs, spectrums},

  startSample = OptionValue[StartValue];
  endSample := If[Length[time] < OptionValue[StopValue],
    Length[time] - 1, OptionValue[StopValue]];

  sampleTime = ColCreate[Take[time - time[[startSample]], {startSample, endSample}],
    ColName → "Time", ColUnit → "s"];
  sampleSignals = Map[ColCreate[Take[#, {startSample, endSample}],
    ColName → "Voltage", ColUnit → "V"] &, {signal}];

  {freqs, spectrums} = Transpose[
    Map[FrequencyDomain[{sampleTime, #}, Accuracy → 10^-8] &, sampleSignals]];

  Print[GraphicsGrid[{MapThread[DataPlot[{#1, #2},
    xRange → OptionValue[CenterFrequency] + {-1, 1} OptionValue[FrequencyRange],
    yRange → All, plotLegend → False] &, {freqs, spectrums}]}]];
];
```

4.3.3.3 ScatterPlot

```
ConstellationPlot[signal_,
  plotopts : OptionsPattern[{ListPlot, ConstellationPlot}] :=
  ListPlot[Transpose[{Re[signal], Im[signal]}], AspectRatio → 1,
  Evaluate[FilterRules[{plotopts}, Options[ListPlot]]]];
ConstellationsPlot[signals__List, opts : OptionsPattern[]] :=
  GraphicsGrid[{Map[ConstellationPlot[#, opts] &, signals]}];
```

4.3.4 Digital Mixing

```
(* ----- Digital Down Conversion ----- *)
Options[DigitalMixing] = {amplitude → 1.0, phase → 0.0};
DigitalMixing[time_, signal_, f0_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {A, phi, localOscillatorI, localOscillatorQ, signalI, signalQ},

  A = OptionValue[amplitude];
  phi = OptionValue[phase];

  localOscillatorI = A Sin[time 2 Pi f0 + phi]; (* Implemented in this way
  for practical reasons, normally the I and Q should be opposite*)
  localOscillatorQ = A Cos[time 2 Pi f0 + phi];

  (*localOscillatorI=A Cos[time 2 Pi f0+phi];
  localOscillatorQ=A Sin[time 2 Pi f0+phi];*)

  signalI = signal * localOscillatorI;
  signalQ = signal * localOscillatorQ;

  Return[{time, signalI, signalQ}]
];
```

4.3.5 Filtering

4.3.5.1 RootRaisedCosineFilterFunction

t : time

beta : roll - off factor

ts : symbol interval

```
RootRaisedCosineFilterFunction[t_, beta_, ts_] := Which[
  t == 0, 1 / ts (1 - beta + 4 beta / Pi),
  Or[t == ts / (4 beta), t == -ts / (4 beta)],
  beta / Sqrt[2] / ts ((1 + 2 / Pi) Sin[Pi / (4 beta)] + (1 - 2 / Pi) Cos[Pi / (4 beta)]),
  True, 1 / ts (Sin[Pi t / ts (1 - beta)] + 4 beta t / ts Cos[Pi t / ts (1 + beta)]) /
  (Pi t / ts (1 - (4 beta t / ts)^2));
```

4.3.5.2 RaisedCosineFilterFunction

t : time

beta : roll - off factor

ts : symbol interval

```
RaisedCosineFilterFunction[t_, beta_, ts_] := Which[
  Or[t == ts / (2 beta), t == -ts / (2 beta)], (Pi / 4) Sinc[Pi / (2 beta)] / ts,
  True, Sinc[Pi t / ts] Cos[Pi beta t / ts] / (1 - (2 beta t / ts)^2) / ts];
```

4.3.5.3 RaisedCosineDigitalFilter

```
RaisedCosineDigitalFilter[filterLengthInTsUnits_, beta_, tSymbol_, tSampling_] :=
Module[{n, time, filter},
  n = Ceiling[filterLengthInTsUnits * tSymbol / tSampling];
  time = Range[-n, n] tSampling + 0.0;
  filter = Map[RaisedCosineFilterFunction[#, beta, tSymbol] + 0.0 &, time];
  Return[{time, filter}];
```

4.3.5.4 Root RaisedCosineDigitalFilter

```
RootRaisedCosineDigitalFilter[filterLengthInTsUnits_, beta_, tSymbol_, tSampling_] :=
Module[{n, time, filter},
  n = Ceiling[filterLengthInTsUnits * tSymbol / tSampling];
  time = Range[-n, n] tSampling + 0.0;
  filter = Map[RootRaisedCosineFilterFunction[#, beta, tSymbol] + 0.0 &, time];
  Return[{time, filter}];
```

4.3.5.5 Filtering data

```
FilterData[{time_, data_}, {filtertime_, filter_}] :=
Module[{dt, dtfilter, Nfilter, result},
  dt = time[[2]] - time[[1]];
  dtfilter = filtertime[[2]] - filtertime[[1]];
  Nfilter = filter / Total[filter];
  result = If[Abs[1 - dt / dtfilter] < 10^-7,
    ListConvolve[Nfilter, data, (Length[Nfilter] + 1) / 2],
    Print["No consistent time interval"]; $Failed];
  Return[result];
```

4.3.5.6 Lowpass filter

```
Options[LowPassFilter] = {ViewInfo → False, ViewPlot → False};
LowPassFilter[{time_, signal_}, fcutoff_] :=
  Module[{timefilter, filter, beta, filterlength, tsampling},

    beta = 0.2; (* Makes a smooth filter *)
    filterlength = 20.0;
    (* in Ts units for a frequency resolution of 1MHz *)
    tsampling = (time[[2]] - time[[1]]);

    {timefilter, filter} =
      RaisedCosineDigitalFilter[filterlength, beta, 1/fcutoff, tsampling];

    If[OptionValue[ViewInfo],
      Print["Filter in time domain"]];

    If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
      Print[DataPlot[{timefilter, filter},
        yRange → All, plotColors → {Blue}, plotLegend → False]]];

    Return[FilterData[{time, signal}, {timefilter, filter}]]
  ];
```

4.3.6 Symbol Time Domain to Frequency Domain and vice versa

```
SymbolTDtoFD[TDlist_] := Module[{FDlist, n},
  n = Length[TDlist];
  FDlist = Fourier[TDlist] / Sqrt[n];
  Join[Take[FDlist, -n/2], Take[FDlist, n/2]];
SymbolFDtoTD[FDlist_] := Module[{temp, n},
  n = Length[FDlist];
  temp = Join[Take[FDlist, -n/2], Take[FDlist, n/2]];
  InverseFourier[temp] * Sqrt[n];
];
```

4.3.7 NR Resampling

```
Options[nrResampling] = {ViewPlot → False};
```

```

nrResampling[nrSignalTime_, nrFilteredI_,
nrFilteredQ_, nrSamplingTime_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
{nrResampledTime, nrResampledI, nrResampledQ, max, min, ShowN},

nrResampledTime = Range[nrSignalTime[[1]], nrSignalTime[[-1]], nrSamplingTime];
nrResampledI = Map[Interpolation[Transpose[{nrSignalTime, nrFilteredI}],
InterpolationOrder → 1], nrResampledTime];
nrResampledQ = Map[Interpolation[Transpose[{nrSignalTime, nrFilteredQ}],
InterpolationOrder → 1], nrResampledTime];

If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
max = Max[Max[nrResampledI], Max[nrResampledQ]];
min = Min[Min[nrResampledI], Min[nrResampledQ]];
ShowN = If[Length[nrResampledTime] < 100 000, Length[nrResampledTime], 100 000];
Print[ListPlot[
{Transpose[{Take[nrResampledTime, {1, ShowN}] - nrResampledTime[[1]],
Take[nrResampledI, {1, ShowN}]}
],
Transpose[{Take[nrResampledTime, {1, ShowN}] - nrResampledTime[[1]],
Take[nrResampledQ, {1, ShowN}]}
]
},
Joined → True, PlotRange → {min, max} * 1.1
]
];
Return[{nrResampledTime, nrResampledI, nrResampledQ}]
];

```

4.3.8 File Read - Write

4.3.8.1 File Write

```
Options[nrFileWrite] = {ViewInfo → True};
```

```

nrFileWrite[time_, I_, Q_, name_, ext_, file_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {time1, time2},
  time1 = Date[];
  FileWrite[FileRoot[file, 2] <> "." <> name <> "." <> ext,
  FileCreate[
    {ColCreate[time, ColName → "Time", ColUnit → "s"],
    ColCreate[I, ColName → "I", ColUnit → "V"],
    ColCreate[Q, ColName → "Q", ColUnit → "V"]},
    FileHeader → {"sep=";", {"Author:", "Emrah Tas"}}]];
  time2 = Date[];
  If[OptionValue[ViewInfo], Print["Elapsed Time :",
    (AbsoluteTime[time2] - AbsoluteTime[time1]) / 60.0, " min"]];
];

```

4.3.8.2 Read File

```

Options[nrReadFile] = {nDrop → 3, ViewInfo → True, ViewPlot → True};
nrReadFile[file_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {data, time, signalI, signalQ},
  data = FileGet[file];
  {time, signalI, signalQ} =
    Map[ToNumber[#] &, Transpose[Drop[data, OptionValue[nDrop]]], {2}];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[ListPlot[{time, signalI}, PlotRange → All],
    ListPlot[{time, signalQ}, PlotRange → All]]];
  Return[{time, signalI, signalQ}];
];

```

4.3.9 Correlation

```

xCorr[kernel_, fullsignal_] := Module[
  {output},
  output = ListCorrelate[Conjugate[kernel], fullsignal];
  (*correlation is performed with conjugate
  value to reach a maximum value using complex signals*)
  Return[output];
];

```

4.3.10 Fourier Transformations

4.3.10.1 nrFourier

```
nrFourier[signal_, Nfft_] := Module[
  {tmp, tmp1, tmp2, signalFreqDomain},
  tmp = Fourier[signal];
  tmp1 = Take[tmp, Nfft/2];
  tmp2 = Take[tmp, -Nfft/2];
  signalFreqDomain = Join[Reverse[tmp1], Reverse[tmp2]];
  Return[signalFreqDomain];
];
```

4.3.10.2 nrInverseFourier

```
nrInverseFourier[signal_, Nfft_] := Module[
  {tmp, tmp1, tmp2, signalTimeDomain},
  tmp1 = Take[signal, Nfft/2];
  tmp2 = Take[signal, -Nfft/2];
  tmp = Join[Reverse[tmp1], Reverse[tmp2]];
  signalTimeDomain = InverseFourier[tmp];
  Return[signalTimeDomain];
];
```

4.3.11 PSS Sequence Generation

4.3.11.1 Generate All PSS in Freq Domain

```
GenerateAllPSS[] := Module[{xstart, lengthpss, pss, x, maxNid, psstotal, p, n},
  xstart = {0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1};
  lengthpss = 127;
  maxNid = 2;
  x = Join[xstart, ConstantArray[0, lengthpss - Length[xstart] + 7]];
  pss = ConstantArray[0, lengthpss];
  For[n = 1, n < lengthpss + 1 - Length[xstart], n++,
    x[[n + 7]] = Mod[x[[n + 4]] + x[[n]], 2];
  ];
  psstotal = {};
  For[p = 0, p ≤ maxNid, p++,
    For[n = 0, n < lengthpss, n++,
      pss[[n + 1]] = 1 - (2 * x[[Mod[n + (43 * p), lengthpss] + 1]]);
    ];
    psstotal = Join[psstotal, {pss}];
  ];
  Return[If[psstotal ≠ {}, psstotal, $Failed]];
]
```

4.3.11.2 Generate All PSS in Time Domain

```
PrepareAllTimeDomainPSS[Allpss_] := Module[{psszeropadded,
  psszeropaddedFFT, pssTimeDomain, psszeropaddedFFTCorr, tmp1, tmp2},
  psszeropadded = Map[Join[ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT/2 - lengthSSB/2 + 56],
    #, ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT/2 - lengthSSB/2 + 57]] &,
    Allpss]; (*1928=NFFT/2-SSBlen/2=2048-120*)
  Return[Map[SymbolFDtoTD[#] &, psszeropadded]];
]
```

4.3.11.3 NR PSS Position

```
Options[nrPSSPosition] = {ViewPlot → True};
nrPSSPosition[nrData10ms_, PSSTimeSeq_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {Corr, pssPosition, NID2, pssStartSample, max, min, maxes, lenCW1, lenCW2, lenCW3,
  possibleotherpsspos, absmax, listpssstarts, pssstarts, numberofpssfound,
  flagok, detectedpsspos2, Corrfound, detectedpsspos, temp, meanpos, accumulate},
```

```

Corr = Map[xCorr[#, nrData10ms] &, PSSTimeSeq];
{{NID2, pssPosition}} = Position[Abs[Corr], Max[Abs[Corr]]];
absmax = Max[Abs[Corr]];
flagok = 0;

possibleotherpsspos = Select[Abs[Corr][[NID2]], # > absmax * 0.90 &];
listpssstarts =
  Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[NID2]], #] &, possibleotherpsspos]];
detectedpsspos = Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[NID2]], #] &, Map[Max[#] &,
  Map[Abs[Corr][[NID2]][[#]] &, Split[listpssstarts, Abs[#2 - #1] < 1000 &]]]];
numberofpssfound = Length[detectedpsspos];

Corrfound = Corr[[NID2]];
temp = Table[{i, Abs[Corrfound[[i]]]}, {i, 1, Length[Corrfound]}];
temp = Select[temp, #[[2]] > 0.7 absmax &];
temp = Split[temp, Abs[#1[[1]] - #2[[1]]] ≤ 1 &];
temp = Select[temp, Length[#] ≥ 20 &];
numberofpssfound = Length[temp];
meanpos = Table[temp[[i, All, 1]].temp[[i, All, 2]] /
  Total[temp[[i, All, 2]]], {i, 1, Length[temp]};
detectedpsspos2 = Round[meanpos];

accumulate = Prepend[samplesBetweenPSS, 0];
If[Length[meanpos] == Length[accumulate],
  pssPosition = Round[Mean[meanpos - accumulate]], pssPosition = 0];
pssStartSample = pssPosition;
If[(Last[detectedpsspos] - detectedpsspos[[2]]) >
  (Total[Differences[samplesBetweenPSS]]), (* Not the all SSB is in
  this windows, shift it in the next step to get the full SSB block*)
  pssPosition = 0;
  pssStartSample = 0,
  flagok = 1];
maxes = Map[Max[Abs[#]] &, Corr];
lenCW1 = Length[Select[Abs[Corr[[1]]], # > maxes[[1]] * 0.50 &]];
lenCW2 = Length[Select[Abs[Corr[[2]]], # > maxes[[2]] * 0.50 &]];
lenCW3 = Length[Select[Abs[Corr[[3]]], # > maxes[[3]] * 0.50 &]];
If[lenCW1 > 10 000 && lenCW2 > 10 000 && lenCW3 > 10 000,
  Print["!!! PSS NOT PRESENT IN THIS FRAME !!!"];
  (* plotting *)
max = Max[Abs[Corr]];
min = Min[Abs[Corr]];
If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
  Print[GraphicsGrid[{Map[DataPlot[{Range[1, Length[#]], Abs[#]},

```

```

        yRange → {0, Max[maxes] * 1.1}, plotLegend → False] &, Corr]]];
];
Return[{pssPosition, NID2 - 1, pssStartSample,
        numberofpssfound, detectedpsspos, detectedpsspos2, flagok}];
];

```

4.3.11.4 PSS extraction

```

Options[nrPSSExtraction] = {ViewPlot → True};

nrPSSExtraction[nrData_, pssStartSample_, nrNfft_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {pssDataTimeDomain, pssDataFreqDomain, tmp1, tmp2, tmp,
   tmpWithoutCenterFreq, PSS, plot1, plot2, plot3, plot4, plot5, PSSzeropadded},
  pssDataTimeDomain = Take[nrData, {pssStartSample, pssStartSample + nrNfft - 1}];
  PSSzeropadded =
    SymbolTDtoFD[Take[nrData, {pssStartSample, pssStartSample + nrNfft - 1}]];
  PSS = Take[PSSzeropadded, {nrNfft/2 - (lengthpss - 1)/2,
    nrNfft/2 + (lengthpss - 1)/2}];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    plot1 = ListLinePlot[Abs[pssDataTimeDomain]];
    plot2 = ListPlot[DB[Abs[PSSzeropadded]^2], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    plot3 = ListPlot[Abs[PSS], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    plot4 = ListPlot[Arg[PSS], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{{plot1, plot2}, {plot3, plot4}}]];
  ];
  Return[PSS];
];

```

4.3.12 Channel Correction

4.3.12.1 Phase Correction: Linear Fit & Extrapolation

```

Options[nrPhaseCorrection] = {ViewPlot → True};

```

```

nrPhaseCorrection[PSS_, AllPSS_, NID2_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {tmp, xrange, line, linearFit, linearFitComplex,
   output, plot1, plot2, plot3, plot4, x, a, b, linenew},

  xrange = Range[-((lengthpss - 1)/2), (lengthpss - 1)/2];
  tmp = PSS/AllPSS[[NID2 + 1]];

  linenew = DataFit[{xrange, tmp/Abs[tmp]},
    Exp[I (a + b x)], x, {a, Arg[tmp[[64]]]}, {b, 0}, ViewFlag → False];
  a = (b /. linenew[[2]]);
  b = (a /. linenew[[2]]);
  line = (a /. linenew[[2]]) + x * (b /. linenew[[2]]);
  linearFit = Table[line, {x, -((lengthpss - 1)/2), (lengthpss - 1)/2}];
  linearFitComplex = Exp[I linearFit];
  output = PSS / linearFitComplex;

  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    plot1 = ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Abs[tmp]}]];
    plot2 = ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[tmp]}]];
    plot3 = Show[ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[tmp]}], PlotStyle → Red],
      Plot[{line}, {x, -31, 31}]];
    plot4 = Show[ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[AllPSS[[NID2 + 1]]}],
      PlotStyle → Red],
      ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[PSS]}], PlotStyle → Green],
      ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[output]}], PlotStyle → Blue]];
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{{plot1, plot2}, {plot3, plot4}}]];
  ];
  {a, b}
];

```

4.3.12.2 Phase Extrapolation

```
Options[nrPhaseExtrapolation] = {ViewPlot → True};
```

```

nrPhaseExtrapolation[line_, nrNOccupiedSC_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {numSubCarrier, linearFit, extraploFit},
  numSubCarrier = nrNOccupiedSC - 1;
  extraploFit = Map[Exp[I (line[[1]] # + line[[2]])] &,
    Join[Range[Round[-nrNOccupiedSC/2], -1], Range[1, Round[nrNOccupiedSC/2]]]];
  extraploFit = Map[Exp[I (line[[1]] # + line[[2]])] &,
    Range[-nrNOccupiedSC/2, nrNOccupiedSC/2 - 1]];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[ListLinePlot[{Arg[extraploFit]}]];
  ];
  Return[extraploFit];
];

```

4.3.12.3 Additional Corrections due to Signal Generator Imperfection (All coefficients are empirically determined)

```

RoschiCorrv2[symbolIndex_, fitparamsa_, fitparamsb_] :=
  Exp[I * (fitparamsb * 2 * Pi / 360 + Mod[symbolIndex, 15] * fitparamsa * 2 * Pi / 360 +
    Floor[symbolIndex, 15] * 1 * 2 * Pi / 360 +
    If[Mod[(symbolIndex), (140 + 84)] == 0, -30 * 2 * Pi / 360, 0] +
    If[Floor[(symbolIndex - 140 - 84) / 14] >= Mod[(symbolIndex - 140 - 84), 14] &&
      Mod[symbolIndex, (140 + 84)] != 0 && symbolIndex >= (140 + 84),
      -30 * 2 * Pi / 360, 0] + If[Floor[symbolIndex / 14] > Mod[symbolIndex, 14] &&
      Mod[symbolIndex, 14] != 0, -30 * 2 * Pi / 360, 0]];

```

```

RoschiCorrv3[symbolIndex_, fitparamsa_, fitparamsb_] :=
  Exp[I * (fitparamsb * 2 * Pi / 360 + Mod[symbolIndex, 15] * fitparamsa * 2 * Pi / 360 -
    Floor[symbolIndex, 15] * 3.2 * Pi / 360)];

```

```

PhaseCorrectionExtv2[symbolscorrwithPrev_, fitparamsa_, fitparamsb_, numerology_] :=
  Module[{corrfactor, mm, symbolsflattened,
    symbolscorrRoschiCorrprev, symbolscorrRoschiCorr},
  symbolsflattened = Flatten[symbolscorrwithPrev, 1];
  corrfactor = ConstantArray[0, Length[symbolsflattened]];
  For[mm = 1, mm < Length[corrfactor] + 1, mm++,
    corrfactor[mm] = Which[numerology == 1, RoschiCorrv2[mm, fitparamsa, fitparamsb],
      numerology == 3, RoschiCorrv3[mm, fitparamsa, fitparamsb], numerology == 0, 1]];
  symbolscorrRoschiCorrprev = symbolsflattened / corrfactor;
  symbolscorrRoschiCorr =
    Partition[symbolscorrRoschiCorrprev, 140 * 2^(numerology - 1)];
  Return[symbolscorrRoschiCorr];
];

```

4.3.12.4 Symbol Based Channel Estimation and Correction

```
SymbolChannelEstimCorrect[symbolscorrwithPrev_, PSSindexes_, numerology_] := Module[
  {a, b, args, pos1, listpos1, argsfinal, flag, coeff, linenew, finalcorrected,},
  args = {};
  pos1 = Select[symbolscorrwithPrev[[1]][[PSSindexes[[1]] + 1]],
    Abs[Arg[#]] < (2 * Pi / 360 * 5) &];
  listpos1 = Flatten[Map[Position[symbolscorrwithPrev[[1]][[
    PSSindexes[[1]] + 1]], #] &, pos1]];
  For[i = 1, i < Length[PSSindexes] + 1, i++,
    args = Append[args, 360 / 2 / Pi * Mean[Map[
      Arg[symbolscorrwithPrev[[1]][[PSSindexes[[i]] + 1]][[#]] &, listpos1]]];
  args = Join[{args[[1]]}, Map[If[# < 0, # + 360, #] &, args[[2 ;; -1]]];
  argsfinal = {};
  flag = False;
  coeff = {};
  For[i = 1, i < Length[args] + 1, i++,
    If[(i > 1 && args[[i - 1]] > args[[i]]) || flag,
      argsfinal = Append[argsfinal, args[[i]] + 360]; flag = True,
      argsfinal = Append[argsfinal, args[[i]];];
  linenew =
    DataFit[{PSSindexes + 1, argsfinal}, a + b * x, x, {a, 0}, {b, 0}, ViewFlag -> False];
  a = (b /. linenew[[2]]);
  b = (a /. linenew[[2]]);
  finalcorrected = PhaseCorrectionExtv2[symbolscorrwithPrev,
    a + Which[numerology == 1, 1, numerology == 3, 3, numerology == 0, 0],
    b + Which[numerology == 1 || numerology == 0, 0, numerology == 3, 55], numerology];
  finalcorrected = If[Length[finalcorrected[[-1]]] == 0,
    Drop[finalcorrected, -1], finalcorrected];
  Return[finalcorrected];
];
```

4.3.13 SSS Sequence Generation

4.3.13.1 Generate All SSS in Freq Domain

```
GenerateAllSSS[Nid2_] :=  
  Module[{x0start, x1start, lengthsss, sss, x0, x1, maxNid1, m0, m1, ssstotal, n, p},  
    x0start = {1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0};  
    x1start = {1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0};  
    lengthsss = 127;  
    x0 = Join[x0start, ConstantArray[0, lengthsss - Length[x0start] + 7]];  
    x1 = Join[x1start, ConstantArray[0, lengthsss - Length[x1start] + 7]];  
    sss = ConstantArray[0, lengthsss];  
    For[n = 1, n < lengthsss + 1 - 7, n++,  
      x0[[n + 7]] = Mod[x0[[n + 4]] + x0[[n]], 2];  
    ];  
    For[n = 1, n < lengthsss + 1 - 7, n++,  
      x1[[n + 7]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1]] + x1[[n]], 2];  
    ];  
    maxNid1 = 335;  
    ssstotal = {};  
    For[p = 0, p <= maxNid1, p++,  
      m0 = 15 * Floor[p / 112] + 5 * Nid2;  
      m1 = Mod[p, 112];  
      For[n = 0, n < lengthsss, n++,  
        sss[[n + 1]] =  
          (1 - (2 * x0[[Mod[n + m0, 127] + 1]])) * (1 - (2 * x1[[Mod[n + m1, 127] + 1]]));  
      ];  
      ssstotal = Join[ssstotal, {sss}];  
    ];  
    Return[ssstotal]  
  ];
```

4.3.13.2 Generate All SSS in Time Domain (with possibility of Freq Shift)

```
PrepareAllTimeDomainSSS[Allsss_] := Module[{ssszeropadded,  
  ssszeropaddedFFT, sssTimeDomain, ssszeropaddedFFTcorr, tmp1, tmp2},  
  ssszeropadded = Map[Join[ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 56],  
    #, ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 57]] &, Allsss];  
  (*1928=NFFT/2-lengthSSB/2=2048-120*)  
  Return[Map[SymbolFDtoTD[#] &, ssszeropadded]];
```

4.3.13.3 NR SSS Position

```
Options[nrSSSPosition] = {ViewPlot → False};

nrSSSPosition[nrData10ms_, SSSTimeSeq_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {Corr, sssPosition, maxPosition, NID1, sssStartSample, max,
   min, maxes, lenCW1, lenCW2, lenCW3, possibleotherssspos, absmax,
   listsssstarts, pssstarts, numberofsssfound, flagok, detectedssspos},

  Corr = Map[xCorr[#, nrData10ms] &, SSSTimeSeq];
  {{NID1, maxPosition} = Position[Abs[Corr], Max[Abs[Corr]]];
  absmax = Max[Abs[Corr]];
  flagok = 0;
  possibleotherssspos = Select[Abs[Corr][[NID1]], # > absmax * 0.95 &];
  listsssstarts =
    Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[NID1]], #] &, possibleotherssspos]];
  detectedssspos = Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[NID1]], #] &, Map[Max[#] &,
    Map[Abs[Corr][[NID1]][[#]] &, Split[listsssstarts, Abs[#2 - #1] < 5 &]]]];
  numberofsssfound = Length[detectedssspos];
  sssPosition = Ceiling[Mean[detectedssspos * 1.0]];
  sssStartSample = sssPosition;
  (* plotting *)
  max = Max[Abs[Corr]];
  min = Min[Abs[Corr]];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{{ DataPlot[{Range[1, Length[Corr]],
      Map[Max[Abs[#]] &, Corr]}, yRange → All, plotLegend → False],
      DataPlot[{Range[1, Length[Corr][[NID1]], Abs[Corr][[NID1]]},
        yRange → All, plotLegend → False]
      }]]];
  ];
  Return[{sssPosition, NID1 - 1, sssStartSample, Corr}];
];
```

4.3.13.4 SSS extraction

```
Options[nrSSSExtraction] = {ViewPlot → True};
```

```

nrSSSExtraction[nrData_, sssStartSample_, nrNfft_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {sssDataTimeDomain, sssDataFreqDomain, tmp1, tmp2, tmp,
   tmpWithoutCenterFreq, SSSzeropadded, SSS, plot1, plot2, plot3, plot4, plot5},
  sssDataTimeDomain = Take[nrData, {sssStartSample, sssStartSample + nrNfft - 1}];
  sssDataFreqDomain = Fourier[sssDataTimeDomain] Sqrt[Length[sssDataTimeDomain]];

  tmp1 = Take[sssDataFreqDomain, nrNfft/2];
  tmp2 = Take[sssDataFreqDomain, -nrNfft/2];
  tmp = Join[Reverse[tmp1], Reverse[tmp2]];
  tmpWithoutCenterFreq = Drop[tmp, {nrNfft/2}];
  SSSzeropadded =
    SymbolTDtoFD[Take[nrData, {sssStartSample, sssStartSample + nrNfft - 1}]];
  SSS = Take[SSSzeropadded, {nrNfft/2 - (lengthsss - 1)/2,
    nrNfft/2 + (lengthsss - 1)/2}];

  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    plot1 = ListLinePlot[Abs[sssDataTimeDomain]];
    plot2 = ListPlot[DB[Abs[tmp]^2], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    plot3 =
      ListPlot[DB[Abs[tmpWithoutCenterFreq]^2], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    plot4 = ListPlot[Abs[SSS], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    plot5 = ListPlot[Arg[SSS], Joined → True, PlotRange → All];
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{{plot1}, {plot2, plot3}, {plot4, plot5}}]];
  ];
  Return[SSS];
];

```

4.3.13.5 Phase Correction based on SSS

```
Options[nrPhaseCorrectionSSS] = {ViewPlot → True};
```

```

nrPhaseCorrectionSSS[SSS_, AllSSS_, NID1_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {tmp, xrange, line, linearFit, linearFitComplex,
   output, plot1, plot2, plot3, plot4, x, a, b, linenew},

  xrange = Range[-(lengthsss - 1)/2, (lengthsss - 1)/2];
  tmp = SSS/AllSSS[[NID1 + 1]];

  linenew = DataFit[{xrange, tmp/Abs[tmp]},
    Exp[I (a + b x)], x, {a, Arg[tmp[[64]]]}, {b, 0}, ViewFlag → False];
  a = (b /. linenew[[2]]);
  b = (a /. linenew[[2]]);
  line = (a /. linenew[[2]]) + x * (b /. linenew[[2]]);
  linearFit = Table[line, {x, -(lengthsss - 1)/2, (lengthsss - 1)/2}];
  linearFitComplex = Exp[I linearFit];
  output = SSS / linearFitComplex;

  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    plot1 = ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Abs[tmp]}]];
    plot2 = ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[tmp]}]];
    plot3 = Show[ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[tmp]}], PlotStyle → Red],
      Plot[{line}, {x, -31, 31}]];
    plot4 = Show[ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[AllSSS[[NID1 + 1]]}],
      PlotStyle → Red],
      ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[PSS]}], PlotStyle → Green],
      ListLinePlot[Transpose[{xrange, Arg[output]}], PlotStyle → Blue]];
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{{plot1, plot2}, {plot3, plot4}}]];
  ];
  Return[output];
];

```

4.3.14 DM-RS Sequence Generation

4.3.14.1 Generate All DM-RS in Freq Domain

```
GenerateAllDMRS[CellID_, Lmax_] :=
Module[{cinit, issbbrange, dmrslength = 144, lengthx1 = 31, x2init,
  lengthx2 = 31, issbbar, firsthalfframe = True, nhf = 0, x1, x2, n, g, c, b, rm},
If[Lmax ≠ 4, issbbar = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7},
  If[firsthalfframe, issbbar = {0, 1, 2, 3}, issbbar = {4, 5, 6, 7}
]
];
rm = ConstantArray[ConstantArray[0, dmrslength], Length[issbbar]];
cinit = (2^11) * (issbbar + 1) * (Floor[CellID / 4] + 1.0) +
  (2^6) * (issbbar + 1) + (Mod[CellID, 4]);
c = ConstantArray[ConstantArray[0, dmrslength * 2 + 1], Length[issbbar]];
x1 = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, dmrslength * 2 + 1600]];
x2init = Map[Reverse[IntegerDigits[IntegerPart[#], 2, 31]] &, cinit];
x2 = Map[Join[#, ConstantArray[0, 1600 + 1 + dmrslength * 2 - Length[#]]] &, x2init];
For[n = 1, n < Length[x1] + 1 - 31, n++,
  x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];
];
For[g = 1, g < Length[x2] + 1, g++,
  For[n = 1, n < Length[x2[[g]]] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x2[[g]][[n + 31]] =
      Mod[x2[[g]][[n + 3]] + x2[[g]][[n + 2]] + x2[[g]][[n + 1]] + x2[[g]][[n]], 2];
];
For[b = 1, b < Length[issbbar] + 1, b++,
  For[n = 1, n < (dmrslength * 2) + 1 + 1, n++,
    c[[b]][[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1600]] + x2[[b]][[n + 1600]], 2];
]];
For[d = 1, d < Length[issbbar] + 1, d++,
  For[n = 1, n < dmrslength + 1, n++,
    rm[[d]][[n]] = 1.0 / Sqrt[2] * (1 - 2 * c[[d]][[2 * (n - 1) + 1]]) +
      I * 1.0 / Sqrt[2] * (1 - 2 * c[[d]][[2 * (n - 1) + 2]]);
]];

Return[rm]
];
```

4.3.14.2 Generate All DM-RS in Time Domain (with possibility of Freq Shift)

```
PrepareAllTimeDomainDMRS[AllDMRS_, CellId_] :=
Module[{dmrszeropadded, dmrszeropaddedsymbols, dmrszeropaddedFFT,
  dmrsTimeDomain, dmrszeropaddedFFTcorr, tmp1, tmp2, dmrsfinalTimeDomain},
  dmrszeropaddedsymbols = ConstantArray[ConstantArray[0, 240], 3];
  (* 240*3 resource elements*)
  For[n = 1, n < 61, n++,
    dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[1]] [[(n - 1) * 4 + Mod[CellId, 4] + 1]] = AllDMRS[[n]]
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < 61, n++,
    dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[3]] [[(n - 1) * 4 + Mod[CellId, 4] + 1]] = AllDMRS[[n + 84]]
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < 13, n++,
    dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[2]] [[(n - 1) * 4 + Mod[CellId, 4] + 1]] = AllDMRS[[n + 60]]
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < 13, n++,
    dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[2]] [[(n - 1) * 4 + 192 + Mod[CellId, 4] + 1]] = AllDMRS[[n + 72]]
  ];

  tmp1 = Map[Take[#, (Length[#]) / 2] &, dmrszeropaddedsymbols];
  tmp2 = Map[Take[#, -(Length[#]) / 2] &, dmrszeropaddedsymbols];
  dmrszeropaddedFFT =
  MapThread[Join[{0}, #1, ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT - Length[#2] - Length[#1] - 1], #2] &,
    {tmp2, tmp1}];
  dmrsTimeDomain = Map[InverseFourier[#] &, dmrszeropaddedFFT];
  dmrszeropaddedFFT = Join[ConstantArray[0,
    nrNFFT / 2 - Length[dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[1]]] / 2], dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[1]],
    ConstantArray[0, nrNFFT / 2 - Length[dmrszeropaddedsymbols[[1]]] / 2]];
  dmrsTimeDomain = Map[SymbolFDtoTD[#] &, dmrszeropaddedFFT];
  dmrsfinalTimeDomain = Join[dmrsTimeDomain[[1]],
    Take[dmrsTimeDomain[[2]], -nrCPlenforotherSyms], dmrsTimeDomain[[2]],
    Take[dmrsTimeDomain[[3]], -nrCPlenforotherSyms], dmrsTimeDomain[[3]]];
  Return[dmrsTimeDomain];
]
```

4.3.14.3 NR DM-RS Position

```
Options[nrDMRSPosition] = {ViewPlot -> False};
```

```

nrDMRSPosition[nrData10ms_, DMRSTimeSeq_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {Corr, DMRSPosition, NID1, DMRSStartSample, max, min, maxes,
   lenCW1, lenCW2, lenCW3, possibleotherdmrpos, absmax, listdmrsstarts,
   pssstarts, numberofsssfound, flagok, detecteddmrpos, issbbar},

  Corr = Map[xCorr[#, nrData10ms] &, DMRSTimeSeq];
  {{issbbar, DMRSPosition} = Position[Abs[Corr], Max[Abs[Corr]]];
  DMRSStartSample = DMRSPosition + 1;
  absmax = Max[Abs[Corr]];
  flagok = 0;
  possibleotherdmrpos = Select[Abs[Corr][[issbbar]], # > absmax * 0.90 &];
  listdmrsstarts =
    Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[issbbar]], #] &, possibleotherdmrpos]];
  detecteddmrpos = Flatten[Map[Position[Abs[Corr][[issbbar]], #] &,
    Map[Max[#] &, Map[Abs[Corr][[issbbar]][[#]] &,
      Split[listdmrsstarts, Abs[#2 - #1] < 1000 &]]]];
  numberofsssfound = Length[detecteddmrpos];
  (* plotting *)
  max = Max[Abs[Corr]];
  min = Min[Abs[Corr]];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[GraphicsGrid[{Map[DataPlot[{Range[1, Length[#]], Abs[#]},
      yRange → All, plotLegend → False] &, Corr]}]]; (*yRange→ max*1.1*)
  ];

  Return[{DMRSPosition, issbbar - 1, DMRSStartSample, Corr}]
];

```

4.3.14.4 Check Measured DMRS

```
CheckDMRS[PBCHcorr_, DMRSPBCH_] := Module[
  {diffindexes, detectedDMRSPBCH},
  detectedDMRSPBCH =
    Map[Take[#, {Mod[nrCellID, 4] + 1}] &, Partition[Flatten[PBCHcorr], 4]];
  diffindexes = {};
  For[jj = 1, jj < Length[detectedDMRSPBCH] + 1, jj++,
    If[detectedDMRSPBCH[[jj]] != DMRSPBCH[[jj]],
      diffindexes = Append[diffindexes, jj]];
  ];
  (*The decoded DC resource element carries usually wrong information,
  this can be avoided*)
  If[diffindexes == {} || diffindexes == {31} ||
    diffindexes == {115} || diffindexes == {31, 115},
    Return["DMRS DETECTION SUCCESSFUL!"], Return["DMRS DETECTION FAILED!"]]
  ];
```

4.3.15 QPSK Demodulation

```
QPSKDemod[symbols_] := Module[{PBCHbitmap},
  PBCHbitmap = Map[Which[Arg[#] <= Pi/2 && Arg[#] > 0, {"00"},
    Arg[#] <= Pi && Arg[#] > Pi/2, {"01"},
    Arg[#] <= -Pi/2 && Arg[#] > -Pi, {"11"},
    Arg[#] <= 0 && Arg[#] > -Pi/2, {"10"}
  ] &, symbols];
  Return[PBCHbitmap];
  ];
```

4.3.16 PBCH

4.3.16.1 Demodulate PBCH in Freq Domain

```
(*v is the two LSB of SS/PBCH block index for Lmax=4
      three LSB of SS/PBCH block index for Lmax=8 or 64
  Mbit is the number of bits transmitted on physical broadcast channel =
  Length[receivedbits]*)
```

```

DemodulatePBCH[nrCellID_, SSBindex_, PBCHcorr_] :=
Module[{cinit, Mbit, x2init, issbbar, x1, x2, n, c,
  bi, v, detectedPBCH, detectedPBCHinbits, receivedbits},
  cinit = nrCellID;
  detectedPBCH = Flatten[Transpose[
    Drop[Transpose[Partition[Flatten[PBCHcorr], 4]], {Mod[nrCellID, 4] + 1}]]];
  receivedbits = Flatten[Map[{ToNumber[StringTake[#, {2}]],
    ToNumber[StringTake[#, {1}]]} &, detectedPBCH]];
  v = SSBindex - 1; (*mod(ssbindex,4)*)
  Mbit = Length[receivedbits];
  c = ConstantArray[0, v * Mbit + Mbit];
  x1 = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, (Mbit * (v + 1)) + 1600]];
  x2init = Reverse[IntegerDigits[IntegerPart[cinit], 2, 31]];
  x2 = Join[x2init, ConstantArray[0, 1600 + (Mbit * (v + 1)) - Length[x2init]]];
  bi = ConstantArray[0, Mbit];

  For[n = 1, n < Length[x1] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];
  ];

  For[n = 1, n < Length[x2] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x2[[n + 31]] = Mod[x2[[n + 3]] + x2[[n + 2]] + x2[[n + 1]] + x2[[n]], 2];
  ];

  For[n = 1, n < (Mbit * (v + 1)) + 1, n++,
    c[[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1600]] + x2[[n + 1600]], 2];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < Mbit + 1, n++,
    bi[[n]] = receivedbits[[n]] - c[[n + v * Mbit]];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < Mbit + 1, n++,
    If[bi[[n]] < 0, bi[[n]] = bi[[n]] + 2];
  ];
  Return[bi];
];

```

4.3.16.2 PBCH Channel Correction

```

GetPBCH[nrDatacorr_, nrCellID_,
  Lmax_, PSSindexes_, SSBindex_, numerology_] := Module[
{cinit, allDMRS, PBCHpart1, PBCHpart2, PBCHpart3, PBCHpart1onlyPBCH,
  PBCHpart2onlyPBCH, PBCHpart3onlyPBCH, PBCHreconsphasecorr,
  PBCHbitmap, PBCHtaken1, PBCHtaken2, PBCHtaken3,
  PBCHpart1corr, PBCHpart3corr, PBCHpart2corr, PBCHcorr},

```

```

allDMRS = GenerateAllDMRS [nrCellID, Lmax];
PBCHpart1 = nrDatacorr [[1]] [[PSSindexes [[SSBindex]] + 2]];
PBCHpart2 = nrDatacorr [[1]] [[PSSindexes [[SSBindex]] + 3]];
PBCHpart3 = nrDatacorr [[1]] [[PSSindexes [[SSBindex]] + 4]];
PBCHpart1onlyPBCH =
  Take [PBCHpart1, {nrSSBSC / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 1, nrSSBSC / 2 + lengthSSB / 2}];
PBCHpart2onlyPBCH = Join [Take [PBCHpart2,
  {nrSSBSC / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 1, nrSSBSC / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 1 + 48 - 1}],
  Take [PBCHpart2, {nrSSBSC / 2 + lengthSSB / 2 - 48 + 1, nrSSBSC / 2 + lengthSSB / 2}]];
PBCHpart3onlyPBCH = Take [PBCHpart3, {nrSSBSC / 2 - lengthSSB / 2 + 1,
  nrSSBSC / 2 + lengthSSB / 2}];
PBCHreconphasecorr = Join [PBCHpart1onlyPBCH,
  PBCHpart2onlyPBCH, PBCHpart3onlyPBCH];

PBCHbitmap = QPSKDemod [PBCHreconphasecorr];

PBCHtaken1 = Take [PBCHbitmap, lengthSSB];
PBCHtaken2 = Take [PBCHbitmap, {lengthSSB + 1, lengthSSB + 96}];
PBCHtaken3 = Take [PBCHbitmap, -lengthSSB];
PBCHpart1corr = PBCHtaken1;
PBCHpart2corr = PBCHtaken2;
PBCHpart3corr = PBCHtaken3;
(*For a perfect equalization on PBCH, some additional correction
  is needed. The correction below is determined fully empirically*)
Which [numerology == 1,
  PBCHpart1corr =
    Map [If [# == {"11"}, {"00"}, If [# == {"00"}, {"11"}, #]] &, PBCHtaken1];
  PBCHpart3corr = Map [If [# == {"01"}, {"10"}, If [# == {"10"}, {"01"}, #]] &,
    PBCHtaken3];
  PBCHpart2corr = Map [Which [# == {"01"}, {"00"}, # == {"11"}, {"10"},
    # == {"00"}, {"01"}, # == {"10"}, {"11"}] &, PBCHtaken2],
  numerology == 0,
  PBCHpart1corr =
    Map [If [# == {"01"}, {"10"}, If [# == {"10"}, {"01"}, #]] &, PBCHtaken1];
  PBCHpart3corr = Map [If [# == {"11"}, {"00"}, If [# == {"00"}, {"11"}, #]] &,
    PBCHtaken3];
  PBCHpart2corr = Map [Which [# == {"01"}, {"00"}, # == {"11"}, {"10"},
    # == {"00"}, {"01"}, # == {"10"}, {"11"}] &, PBCHtaken2],
  numerology == 3,
  PBCHpart1corr =
    Map [If [# == {"01"}, {"10"}, If [# == {"10"}, {"01"}, #]] &, PBCHtaken1];
  PBCHpart3corr = Map [If [# == {"11"}, {"00"}, If [# == {"00"}, {"11"}, #]] &,
    PBCHtaken3];

```

```

PBCHpart2corr = Map[Which[# == {"01"}, {"00"}, # == {"11"}, {"10"},
  # == {"00"}, {"01"}, # == {"10"}, {"11"}] &, PBCHtaken2]
];
PBCHcorr = Join[PBCHpart1corr, PBCHpart2corr, PBCHpart3corr];
Return[PBCHcorr];
];

```

4.3.16.3 Check Rate Matching

```

PBCHCheckRateMatching[PBCHdecodedinbits_, Nratematch_] := Module[
  {firsts, repeateds, diffindexes},
  firsts = Take[PBCHdecodedinbits, Nratematch];
  repeateds = Take[PBCHdecodedinbits, -Length[PBCHdecodedinbits] + Nratematch];
  diffindexes = {};
  For[jj = 1, jj < Length[repeateds] + 1, jj++,
    If[firsts[[jj]] != repeateds[[jj]], diffindexes = Append[diffindexes, jj]];
  ];
  (*The DC resource element has the wrong information, it can be avoided*)
  If[diffindexes == {} || diffindexes == {173} || diffindexes == {174} ||
    diffindexes == {181} || diffindexes == {182} || diffindexes == {173, 181} ||
    diffindexes == {174, 182} || diffindexes == {173, 182}, Return[
    "RATE MATCHING START SUCCESSFUL!"], Return["RATE MATCHING START FAILED!"]];
  ];

```

4.3.17 MIB

4.3.17.1 Remove Rate Matching and De-interleave

```

RateandDeinterleave[PBCHdecodedinbits_, Nratematch_] := Module[
  {rateunmatchedbits, J, Pofi, n, i, channelencoded},
  rateunmatchedbits = Take[PBCHdecodedinbits, Nratematch];
  J = ConstantArray[0, Nratematch];
  Pofi = {0, 1, 2, 4, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 16, 9, 17, 10, 18, 11,
    19, 12, 20, 13, 21, 14, 22, 15, 23, 24, 25, 26, 28, 27, 29, 30, 31};
  For[n = 0, n < Nratematch, n++,
    i = Floor[32 * n / Nratematch];
    J[[n + 1]] = Pofi[[i + 1]] * Nratematch / 32 + Mod[n, Nratematch / 32];
  channelencoded = ConstantArray[0, Nratematch];
  For[n = 0, n < Nratematch, n++,
    channelencoded[[J[[n + 1]] + 1]] = rateunmatchedbits[[n + 1]];
  Return[channelencoded];
  ];

```

4.3.17.2 Polar Decoding

```
PolarDecoding[channelencoded_, Nratematch_] := Module[
  {Kpolar, KmaxIL, PolInterPat, interleaved, kk, mm,
   polarseqfile, polarseq, polarseqratematched, polarseqfin, cprime,
   uu, nn, Gof2, bigmat, upolar, upolarcor, cprimerefound, jj, cfound},
  (*Interleaving*)
  Kpolar = 56;
  KmaxIL = 164;
  PolInterPat = {0, 2, 4, 7, 9, 14, 19, 20, 24, 25, 26, 28, 31, 34, 42, 45, 49, 50, 51,
    53, 54, 56, 58, 59, 61, 62, 65, 66, 67, 69, 70, 71, 72, 76, 77, 81, 82, 83, 87,
    88, 89, 91, 93, 95, 98, 101, 104, 106, 108, 110, 111, 113, 115, 118, 119, 120,
    122, 123, 126, 127, 129, 132, 134, 138, 139, 140, 1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 15, 21, 27, 29,
    32, 35, 43, 46, 52, 55, 57, 60, 63, 68, 73, 78, 84, 90, 92, 94, 96, 99, 102, 105,
    107, 109, 112, 114, 116, 121, 124, 128, 130, 133, 135, 141, 6, 11, 16, 22, 30,
    33, 36, 44, 47, 64, 74, 79, 85, 97, 100, 103, 117, 125, 131, 136, 142, 12, 17, 23,
    37, 48, 75, 80, 86, 137, 143, 13, 18, 38, 144, 39, 145, 40, 146, 41, 147, 148,
    149, 150, 151, 152, 153, 154, 155, 156, 157, 158, 159, 160, 161, 162, 163};
  interleaved = Range[0, Kpolar - 1];
  kk = 0;
  For[mm = 0, mm < KmaxIL, mm++,
    If[PolInterPat[[mm + 1]] ≥ KmaxIL - Kpolar,
      interleaved[[kk + 1]] = PolInterPat[[mm + 1]] - (KmaxIL - Kpolar);
      kk++
    ]
  ];

  (*Polar Decoding*)
  polarseqfile = "C:\\\\PolarSequenceQ.csv";
  polarseq = Map[ToNumber[#] &, Flatten[FileGet[polarseqfile, ViewFlag → False]]];
  polarseqratematched = Select[polarseq, # < Nratematch &];
  polarseqfin = Take[polarseqratematched, -Kpolar];
  cprime = Range[1, Kpolar];
  kk = 0;
  uu = ConstantArray[10 000, Nratematch];
  For[nn = 0, nn < Nratematch, nn++,
    If[MemberQ[polarseqfin, nn], uu[[nn + 1]] = cprime[[kk + 1]];
      kk = kk + 1, uu[[nn + 1]] = 0];
  Gof2 = {{1, 0}, {1, 1}};
  bigmat = KroneckerProduct[Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2, Gof2];
  upolar = channelencoded.Inverse[bigmat];
  upolarcor = Map[If[Mod[Abs[#], 2] == 0, 0, 1] &, upolar];
```

```

cprimerefound = ConstantArray[1000, Kpolar];
kk = 1;
For[jj = 1, jj < Nratematch + 1, jj++,
  If[uu[[jj]] ≠ 0, cprimerefound[[kk]] = upolarcor[[jj]]; kk++];
cfound = ConstantArray[1000, Kpolar];
For[jj = 1, jj < Kpolar + 1, jj++,
  cfound[[ (interleaved + 1)[[jj]]]] = cprimerefound[[jj]];
Return[cfound];
];

```

4.3.17.3 Remove CheckSum

```

RemoveCheckSum[cfound_] := Module[
  {polynom, CRCsoll, datawoCRC},
  (*polynom={1,1,0,1,1,0,0,1,0,1,0,1,1,0,0,0,1,0,0,0,1,0,1,1,1};
  (*Reverse[D^0+D^1+D^2+D^4+D^8+D^12+D^13+D^15+D^17+D^20+D^21+D^23+D^24]*
  Take[cfound,32];
  CRCsoll={1,1,0,0,1,0,0,1,1,0,0,1,0,1,1,1,1,1,1,1,0,0,1};
  Take[cfound,-24]==CRCsoll;*)
  datawoCRC = Take[cfound, 32];
  Return[datawoCRC];
];

```

4.3.17.4 Descrambling for Payload and get MIB information

```

GetMIB[datawoCRC_, nrCellID_, Lmax_] := Module[
  {v, CRCsoll, cinit, LenA, Mbit, c, x1, x2init, x2, ai, n, jj, si, result, SFN,
  subcarspaccommon, SSBscffsetdetected, dmrstypeApos, pdcchconfigforSIB1,
  cellbarred, intrafreqresel, sparebits, resultall, coresetzero, searchspacezero},
  v = Which[{datawoCRC[[7]], datawoCRC[[25]]} == {0, 0}, 0,
  {datawoCRC[[7]], datawoCRC[[25]]} == {0, 1}, 1,
  {datawoCRC[[7]], datawoCRC[[25]]} == {1, 0}, 2,
  {datawoCRC[[7]], datawoCRC[[25]]} == {1, 1}, 3];
  cinit = nrCellID;
  LenA = 32;
  If[Lmax == 8 || Lmax == 4, Mbit = LenA - 3, Mbit = LenA - 6];
  c = ConstantArray[0, v * LenA + LenA];
  x1 = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, (LenA * (v + 1)) + 1600]];
  x2init = Reverse[IntegerDigits[IntegerPart[cinit], 2, 31]];
  x2 = Join[x2init, ConstantArray[0, 1600 + (LenA * (v + 1)) - Length[x2init]]];
  ai = ConstantArray[0, LenA];
  For[n = 1, n < Length[x1] + 1 - 31, n++,
  x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];

```

```

];
For[n = 1, n < Length[x2] + 1 - 31, n++,
  x2[[n + 31]] = Mod[x2[[n + 3]] + x2[[n + 2]] + x2[[n + 1]] + x2[[n]], 2]];

For[n = 1, n < (LenA * (v + 1)) + 1, n++,
  c[[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1600]] + x2[[n + 1600]], 2];
];
jj = 0;
si = ConstantArray[100, LenA];
If[Lmax ≠ 64,
  For[n = 1, n < LenA + 1, n++,
    If[n ≠ 1 && n ≠ 7 && n ≠ 25, si[[n]] = c[[jj + v * Mbit + 1]];
    jj++, si[[n]] = 0]],
  For[n = 1, n < LenA + 1, n++,
    If[n ≠ 1 && n ≠ 3 && n ≠ 4 && n ≠ 6 && n ≠ 7 && n ≠ 25, si[[n]] = c[[jj + v * Mbit + 1]];
    jj++, si[[n]] = 0]]
];
ai = datawoCRC - si;
For[n = 1, n < LenA + 1, n++,
  If[ai[[n]] < 0, ai[[n]] = ai[[n]] + 2]];
result = ConstantArray[100, 32];
(*SFN*)
result[[1]] = ai[[17]]; (*jSFN=0, G(0)=16, *)
result[[2]] = ai[[24]]; (*jSFN=1, G(1)=23, *)
result[[3]] = ai[[19]]; (*jSFN=2, G(2)=18, *)
result[[4]] = ai[[18]]; (*jSFN=3, G(3)=17, *)
result[[5]] = ai[[9]]; (*jSFN=4, G(4)=8, *)
result[[6]] = ai[[31]]; (*jSFN=5, G(5)=30, *)
result[[25]] = ai[[11]]; (*jSFN=6, G(6)=10 4th LSB of SFN*)
result[[26]] = ai[[7]]; (*jSFN=7, G(7)=6 3rd LSB of SFN*)
result[[27]] = ai[[25]]; (*jSFN=8, G(8)=24 2nd LSB of SFN*)
result[[28]] = ai[[8]]; (*jSFN=9, G(9)=7 1st LSB of SFN*)

(*SCS common*)
result[[7]] = ai[[2]]; (*jother=14 G(14)=1 jother=15*)

(*SSB subcarrieroffset*)
result[[8]] = ai[[5]]; (*jother=15 G(15)=4 jother=16*)
result[[9]] = ai[[10]]; (*jother=16 G(16)=9 jother=17*)
result[[10]] = ai[[12]]; (*jother=17 G(17)=11 jother=18*)
result[[11]] = ai[[13]]; (*jother=18 G(18)=12 jother=19*)

(*DMRS Type A position*)

```

```

result[[12]] = ai[[14]]; (*jother=19 G(19)=13 jother=20*)

(*PDCCH config SIB1*)
result[[13]] = ai[[15]]; (*jother=20 G(20)=14 jother=21*)
result[[14]] = ai[[16]]; (*jother=21 G(21)=15 jother=22*)
result[[15]] = ai[[20]]; (*jother=22 G(22)=19 jother=23*)
result[[16]] = ai[[21]]; (*jother=23 G(23)=20 jother=24*)
result[[17]] = ai[[22]]; (*jother=24 G(24)=21 jother=25*)
result[[18]] = ai[[23]]; (*jother=25 G(25)=22 jother=26*)
result[[19]] = ai[[26]]; (*jother=26 G(26)=25 jother=27*)
result[[20]] = ai[[27]]; (*jother=27 G(27)=26 jother=28*)

(*Cell barred*)
result[[21]] = ai[[28]]; (*jother=28 G(28)=27 jother=29*)

(*Intra freq selection *)
result[[22]] = ai[[29]]; (*jother=29 G(29)=28 jother=30*)

(*Spare Bit*)
result[[23]] = ai[[30]]; (*jother=30 G(30)=29 jother=31*)

(*BCCH-BCH-Message Type indication*)
result[[24]] = ai[[32]]; (*jother=31 G(31)=31 jother=32*)

(* Half frame bit *)
result[[29]] = ai[[1]]; (*jHRF=10, G(10)=0 *)

(* MSB of kssb and bits of candidate SS/PBCH block index*)
result[[30]] = ai[[6]]; (*jSSB=11, G(11)=5*)
result[[31]] = ai[[4]]; (*jSSB=12, G(12)=3*)
result[[32]] = ai[[3]]; (*jSSB=13, G(13)=2*)
resultall = result;
result = Rest[result];
SFN = Take[resultall, 6];
SFN = Join[Take[resultall, 6], Take[resultall, {-8, -5}]];
subcarspaccommon = Take[result, {7}];
SSBscffsetdetected = Join[Take[result, {-3}], Take[result, {8, 11}]];
dmrstypeApos = Take[result, {12}];
coresetzero = Take[result, {13, 16}];
searchspacezero = Take[result, {17, 20}];
cellbarred = Take[result, {21}];
intrafreqresel = Take[result, {22}];
sparebits = Take[result, {23}];

```

```

Return[{SFN, subcarspaccommon, SSBscffsetdetected, dmrstypeApos,
       coresetzero, searchspacezero, cellbarred, intrafreqresel}
];

```

4.3.18 PDCCH

4.3.18.1 Generate PDCCH DMRS

```

PDCCHDMRS[nrCellID_, nrSymbolperSlot_, coresetslot_, FirstSymbolIndexcoreset_,
          dmrslength_] := Module[{cinit, Mbit, x2init, g, x1, x2, n, c, bi, v, , rm},
  rm = ConstantArray[0, dmrslength];
  cinit =
    Mod[(2^17 * (nrSymbolperSlot * (coresetslot - 1) + (FirstSymbolIndexcoreset - 1) + 1) *
         (2 * nrCellID + 1) + 2 * nrCellID), 2^31];
  c = ConstantArray[0, dmrslength * 2 + 1];
  x1 = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, dmrslength * 2 + 1600]];
  x2init = Reverse[IntegerDigits[IntegerPart[cinit], 2, 31]];
  x2 = Join[x2init, ConstantArray[0, 1600 + 1 + dmrslength * 2 - Length[x2init]]];
  For[n = 1, n < Length[x1] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < Length[x2] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x2[[n + 31]] = Mod[x2[[n + 3]] + x2[[n + 2]] + x2[[n + 1]] + x2[[n]], 2];
  For[n = 1, n < (dmrslength * 2) + 1 + 1, n++,
    c[[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1600]] + x2[[n + 1600]], 2];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < dmrslength + 1, n++,
    rm[[n]] = 1.0 / Sqrt[2] * (1 - 2 * c[[2 * (n - 1) + 1]]) +
      I * 1.0 / Sqrt[2] * (1 - 2 * c[[2 * (n - 1) + 2]]);
  ];
  Return[rm]
];

```

4.3.18.2 Demodulate PDCCH in Freq Domain

```

(*v is the two LSB of SS/PBCH block index for Lmax=4
   three LSB of SS/PBCH block index for Lmax=8 or 64
  Mbit is the number of bits transmitted on physical broadcast channel =
  Length[receivedbits]*)

```

```

DemodulatePDCCH[nrCellID_, PDCCHcorr_, nrNTI_] := Module[
  {cinit, Mbit, x2init, issbbar, x1, x2, n, c, bi, detectedPDCCH, receivedbits, v},
  cinit = Mod[(nrNTI * 2^16 + nrCellID), 2^31];
  detectedPDCCH =
    Flatten[Transpose[Drop[Transpose[Partition[Flatten[PDCCHcorr], 4]], {2}]]];
  receivedbits = Flatten[Map[{ToNumber[StringTake[#, {2}]],
    ToNumber[StringTake[#, {1}]]} &, detectedPDCCH]];
  v = 0; (*mod(ssbindex,4)*)
  Mbit = Length[receivedbits];
  c = ConstantArray[0, v * Mbit + Mbit];
  x1 = Join[{1}, ConstantArray[0, (Mbit * (v + 1)) + 1600]];
  x2init = Reverse[IntegerDigits[IntegerPart[cinit], 2, 31]];
  x2 = Join[x2init, ConstantArray[0, 1600 + (Mbit * (v + 1)) - Length[x2init]]];
  bi = ConstantArray[0, Mbit];

  For[n = 1, n < Length[x1] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x1[[n + 31]] = Mod[x1[[n + 3]] + x1[[n]], 2];
  ];

  For[n = 1, n < Length[x2] + 1 - 31, n++,
    x2[[n + 31]] = Mod[x2[[n + 3]] + x2[[n + 2]] + x2[[n + 1]] + x2[[n]], 2];
  ];

  For[n = 1, n < (Mbit * (v + 1)) + 1, n++,
    c[[n]] = Mod[x1[[n + 1600]] + x2[[n + 1600]], 2];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < Mbit + 1, n++,
    bi[[n]] = receivedbits[[n]] - c[[n + v * Mbit]];
  ];
  For[n = 1, n < Mbit + 1, n++,
    If[bi[[n]] < 0, bi[[n]] = bi[[n]] + 2];
  ];
  Return[bi];
];

```

4.3.19 Data Formatting

4.3.19.1 Data Formatting for numerologies 0 and 1

```
nrDataFormat[nrTimeSyncData_, nrTimeSyncTime_,
  nrSymbolStart_, numSamplesinSubFrame_, nrNfft_] := Module[
  {tmp, ttmp, nrDataBlock, nrTimeBlock},

  tmp = nrTimeSyncData;
  ttmp = nrTimeSyncTime;
  nrDataBlock = {};
  nrTimeBlock = {};

  While[Length[tmp] > numSamplesinSubFrame,
    nrDataBlock = Append[nrDataBlock, Take[tmp, numSamplesinSubFrame]];
    nrTimeBlock = Append[nrTimeBlock, Take[ttmp, numSamplesinSubFrame]];
    tmp = Drop[tmp, numSamplesinSubFrame];
    ttmp = Drop[ttmp, numSamplesinSubFrame];
  ];

  nrDataBlock = Append[nrDataBlock, tmp];
  nrTimeBlock = Append[nrTimeBlock, tmp];

  Return[{nrDataBlock, nrTimeBlock}];
];
```

4.3.19.2 Data Formatting for numerologies 3

```
nrDataFormatNum3[nrDataBlockwithPrev_, nrNfft_] := Module[
  {nrSlotLengthnum3, slotresults, finalslots, kk,
   slot1, tmpDataBlock, slot2to4, slots, finalslotsflattened},
  nrSlotLengthnum3 = nrNfft * nrSymbolperSlot * 4 + nrCPlenforLongSyms +
    nrCPlenforotherSyms * (nrSymbolperSlot * 4 - 1);
  slotresults = Map[Partition[#, {nrSlotLengthnum3}] &, nrDataBlockwithPrev];
  finalslots = {};
  slotresults = Flatten[slotresults, 1];
  For[kk = 1, kk < Length[slotresults] + 1, kk++,
    slot1 = Take[slotresults[[kk]], nrNfft * nrSymbolperSlot +
      nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrCPlenforotherSyms * (nrSymbolperSlot - 1)];
    tmpDataBlock = Drop[slotresults[[kk]], Length[slot1]];
    slot2to4 = Partition[tmpDataBlock,
      {nrNfft * nrSymbolperSlot + nrCPlenforotherSyms * nrSymbolperSlot}];
    slots = Join[{slot1}, slot2to4];
    finalslots = Append[finalslots, slots];
  ];
  finalslotsflattened = Flatten[finalslots, 1];
  Return[finalslotsflattened];
];
```

4.3.20 Data Extraction

4.3.20.1 Remove Cyclic Prefix

```
removenrCPx[SlotData_, nrNfft_, nrCPlenforLongSyms_,
  nrCPlenforotherSyms_, numerology_, slotnr_] := Module[
  {sym1, tmpDataBlock, tmpPartition, tmpSubPartition,
   sym2to13, symbols, sym8, sym2to7, sym9to14, sym2to55},

  Which[numerology == 1,
    sym1 = Take[SlotData, {nrCPlenforLongSyms + 1, nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft}];
    tmpDataBlock = Drop[SlotData, nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft];
    tmpPartition = Partition[tmpDataBlock, {nrCPlenforotherSyms + nrNfft}];
    sym2to13 = Map[Take[#,
      {nrCPlenforotherSyms + 1, nrCPlenforotherSyms + nrNfft}] &, tmpPartition];
    symbols = Join[{sym1}, sym2to13],

  numerology == 0,
    tmpPartition = Partition[SlotData,
```

```

    {nrCPlenforLongSyms + 6 * nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft * 7}];
sym1 = Take[tmpPartition[[1]], {nrCPlenforLongSyms + 1,
    nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft}];
tmpDataBlock = Drop[tmpPartition[[1]], nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft];
tmpSubPartition = Partition[tmpDataBlock, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}];
sym2to7 = Map[Take[#, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + 1, nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}] &,
    tmpSubPartition];
sym8 = Take[tmpPartition[[2]], {nrCPlenforLongSyms + 1,
    nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft}];
tmpDataBlock = Drop[tmpPartition[[2]], nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft];
tmpSubPartition = Partition[tmpDataBlock, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}];
sym9to14 =
    Map[Take[#, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + 1, nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}] &,
        tmpSubPartition];
symbols = Join[{sym1}, sym2to7, {sym8}, sym9to14],

numerology == 3,
If[Mod[slotnr, 4] == 1,
    sym1 = Take[SlotData, {nrCPlenforLongSyms + 1, nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft}];
    tmpDataBlock = Drop[SlotData, nrCPlenforLongSyms + nrNfft];
    tmpPartition = Partition[tmpDataBlock, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}];
    sym2to13 = Map[Take[#, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + 1,
        nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}] &, tmpPartition];
    symbols = Join[{sym1}, sym2to13],
    tmpPartition = Partition[SlotData, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}];
    sym2to13 = Map[Take[#, {nrCPlenforOtherSyms + 1,
        nrCPlenforOtherSyms + nrNfft}] &, tmpPartition];
    symbols = sym2to13;
];
];
Return[symbols];
];

```

4.3.20.2 Remove Guard Band

```
Options[removenrGuardBand] = {ViewPlot -> False};
```

```

removenrGuardBand[signalFreqDomain_,
  nrNLGSC_, nrNRGSC_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {tmp, signal, nSignal},
  tmp = Drop[signalFreqDomain, nrNLGSC];
  signal = Drop[tmp, -nrNRGSC];
  nSignal = Drop[signal, {Round[Length[signal]/2.0]}];

  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[ListLinePlot[Abs[signalFreqDomain], PlotRange → All]];
    Print[ListLinePlot[Abs[tmp], PlotRange → All]];
    Print[ListLinePlot[Abs[signal], PlotRange → All]];
    Print[ListLinePlot[Abs[nSignal], PlotRange → All]];
  ];

  (*Return[nSignal];*)
  Return[signal];
];

```

4.3.20.3 Extract Active Subcarrier

```

Options[nractiveSubCarrier] = {ViewPlot → False};

nractiveSubCarrier[signalWOGuardBand_,
  nrNOccupiedSC_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {signal, numSubCarrier},
  numSubCarrier = nrNOccupiedSC;
  signal =
    Take[signalWOGuardBand, {(Length[signalWOGuardBand])/2 - numSubCarrier/2 + 1,
      (Length[signalWOGuardBand])/2 + numSubCarrier/2}];
  If[OptionValue[ViewPlot],
    Print[ListLinePlot[Abs[signal], PlotRange → All]];
  ];
  Return[signal];
];

```

4.3.20.4 Data Extraction

```
nrDataExtraction[nrSymbol_, nrNfft_, nrNOccupiedSC_] := Module[
  {symbolFreqDomain, symbolWOGuardBand, signalWActiveSubCarrier},
  symbolFreqDomain = SymbolTDtoFD[nrSymbol];
  signalWActiveSubCarrier =
    nractiveSubCarrier[symbolFreqDomain, nrNOccupiedSC, ViewPlot → False];
  Return[signalWActiveSubCarrier];
];
```

4.4. Decode and Save

```
Options[nrDecode] =
  {UncorrectedSymbolViewPlot → False, CorrectedSymbolViewPlot → False,
  ResamplingViewPlot → False, PSSDetectionViewPlot → False,
  SSSDetectionViewPlot → False, PSSExtractionViewPlot → False,
  PhaseCorrectionViewPlot → False, PhaseExtrapolationViewPlot → False};

nrDecode[scopefile_, opts : OptionsPattern[]] := Module[
  {time, timecol, voltage, voltagecol, nrSignalTime, nrSignalI, nrSignalQ,
  nrFilteredI, nrFilteredQ, nrResampledTime, nrResampledI, nrResampledQ,
  zadoffchuSeq, zadTimeSeq, nrData, nrData10ms, zadRoot, pssPosition, nrNID2,
  pssStartSample, detectedpsspos, detectedpsspos2, flag, allpssTD, nrDataBlock,
  nrTimeBlock, nrTimeSyncData, nrTimeSyncTime, nrTimeSyncTimewithPrev,
  nrTimeSyncDatawithPrev, frameStartSample, nrSymbolStart, PSS, xLine,
  phaseCorr, nrSlotData, nrSymbols, pssDataTimeDomain, pssDataFreqDomain,
  signalWOGuardBand, signalWActiveSubCarrier, nrFreqDomain, symbolsuncorr,
  symbolscorr, allSSS, allSSStd, nrDataforSSSdetec, sssPosition, nrNID1,
  nrCellID, sssStartSample, Corr, nrDataBlockwithPrev, nrTimeBlockwithPrev,
  SSSsSubFrame5, SSSsSubFrame0, SSSsmeasured, SSSsmeasuredcor, header,
  FrameNumbers, SymbolNumbers, FrameNumberFinal, xaxis, fullresourcegrid, SSScorr,
  flagSF0, nrNID1s, CellIds, numberofpssfound, flagok, nrSlotDatawithPrev,
  nrSymbolswithPrev, nrFreqDomainwithPrev, symbolsuncorrwithPrev,
  symbolscorrwithPrev, finalcorrected, flagalreadyprinted, symbolscorrnew,
  nrSlotLengthnum3, slotresults, finalslots, slot1, tmpDataBlock, kk,
  slot2to4, slots, finalslotsflattened, nrSymbolswithPrevfinal, ii},
  {timecol, voltagecol} = ScopeDataRead[scopefile];
  time = ColValues[timecol];
  voltage = ColValues[voltagecol];
  {nrSignalTime, nrSignalI, nrSignalQ} =
    DigitalMixing[time, voltage, nrIntermediateFrequency];
  (*Downconversion*) (*0.915322k*)
```

```

nrFilteredI = LowPassFilter[
  {nrSignalTime, nrSignalI}, 2 * nrFilterCutOffFrequency]; (*Filtering*)
nrFilteredQ = LowPassFilter[{nrSignalTime, nrSignalQ},
  2 * nrFilterCutOffFrequency];
{nrResampledTime, nrResampledI, nrResampledQ} =
nrResampling[nrSignalTime, nrFilteredI, nrFilteredQ, nrSamplingTime,
  ViewPlot -> OptionValue[ResamplingViewPlot]]; (* Resampling *)
(*PSS Location*)
nrData = nrResampledI + I nrResampledQ;
nrData10ms = Take[nrData, {1,
  If[numerology == 3, nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame, nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2]}];
allpssTD = PrepareAllTimeDomainPSS[GenerateAllPSS[]];
flagalreadyprinted = False;
Print["FIRST ITERATION OF PSS DETECTION..."];
{pssPosition, nrNID2, pssStartSample, numberofpssfound,
  detectedpsspos, detectedpsspos2, flagok} = nrPSSPosition[nrData10ms,
  allpssTD, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PSSDetectionViewPlot]];
If[flagok == 1 && Length[detectedpsspos] == Length[PSSindexes],
  Print["PSS SUCCESSFULLY DETECTED!"];
  flagalreadyprinted = True,
  Print["PSS DETECTION NOT COMPLETE, SECOND ITERATION OF PSS DETECTION..."];

(*If PSS is too early detected,
then SSS is not present and the Cell ID cannot be detected. For this reason,
the slot must be discarded and the next slot should be considered*)
If[flagok == 0 || Length[detectedpsspos] != Length[PSSindexes],
  flag = False;
  If[Length[detectedpsspos] < Length[PSSindexes], nrData10ms = Take[nrData,
    {1 + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 4, 3 * nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 4}];
    flag = True,
    nrData10ms =
      Take[nrData, {1 + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2, nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame}]];
  {pssPosition, nrNID2, pssStartSample, numberofpssfound, detectedpsspos,
    detectedpsspos2, flagok} = nrPSSPosition[nrData10ms,
    allpssTD, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PSSDetectionViewPlot]];
  pssStartSample = pssStartSample + If[flag, nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 4,
    nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2];
  pssPosition = pssPosition + If[flag, nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 4,
    nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2];
  flag = False;

(*If not enough PSS, one more shift and try*)
If[Length[detectedpsspos] == Length[PSSindexes],

```

```

If[! flagalreadyprinted, Print["PSS SUCCESSFULLY DETECTED!"];
  flagalreadyprinted = True],
Print["PSS DETECTION NOT COMPLETE, THIRD ITERATION OF PSS DETECTION..."];
If[Length[detectedpsspos] < Length[PSSindexes],
  nrData10ms = Take[nrData, {1 + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2,
    nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2 + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame}];
  flag = True;
  {pssPosition, nrNID2, pssStartSample, numberofpssfound,
    detectedpsspos, detectedpsspos2, flagok} = nrPSSPosition[nrData10ms,
    allpssTD, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PSSDetectionViewPlot]];
  pssStartSample = pssStartSample + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2;
  pssPosition = pssPosition + nrNumSamplesinRadioFrame / 2];
flag = False;
If[flagok == 1 && Length[detectedpsspos] == Length[PSSindexes],
  If[! flagalreadyprinted, Print["PSS SUCCESSFULLY DETECTED!"]],
  Print["!!! PSS DETECTION NOT SUCCESSFULL!!! CHECK CONFIGURATION!"]];

nrTimeSyncData = Drop[nrData, pssStartSample - 1];
nrTimeSyncTime = Drop[nrResampledTime, pssStartSample - 1];
nrTimeSyncDatawithPrev =
  Drop[nrData, pssStartSample - 1 - PSSindexes[[1]] * nrCPlenforotherSyms -
    PSSindexes[[1]] * nrNFFT - nrCPlenforLongSyms];
(*PSS is either on 2nd or 5th symbol, extract the previous symbols too*)
nrTimeSyncTimewithPrev = Drop[nrResampledTime,
  pssStartSample - 1 - PSSindexes[[1]] * nrCPlenforotherSyms -
  PSSindexes[[1]] * nrNFFT - nrCPlenforLongSyms];

allSSS = GenerateAllSSS[nrNID2];
allSSStd = PrepareAllTimeDomainSSS[allSSS];
(*nrDataforSSSdetec=nrTimeSyncData[[1;;20000]];*)
nrDataforSSSdetec = nrTimeSyncDatawithPrev[[
  PSSindexes[[1]] * nrCPlenforotherSyms + PSSindexes[[1]] * nrNFFT +
  nrCPlenforLongSyms ;; 20 000 + PSSindexes[[1]] * nrCPlenforotherSyms +
  PSSindexes[[1]] * nrNFFT + nrCPlenforLongSyms]];
{sssPosition, nrNID1, sssStartSample, Corr} = nrSSSPosition[nrDataforSSSdetec,
  allSSStd, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[SSSDetectionViewPlot]];
nrCellID = 3 * nrNID1 + nrNID2;
Print["SSS SUCCESSFULLY DETECTED!"];
Print["Cell ID is " <> ToString[nrCellID]];

(*Data Formatting*)
{nrDataBlock, nrTimeBlock} = nrDataFormat[
  nrTimeSyncData, nrTimeSyncTime, 0, nrSamplesperSubFrame * 5, nrNFFT];

```

```

(*Data Formatting*)
{nrDataBlockwithPrev, nrTimeBlockwithPrev} =
  nrDataFormat[nrTimeSyncDatawithPrev,
    nrTimeSyncTimewithPrev, 0, nrSamplesperSubFrame * 5, nrNFFT];
(* PSS Extraction *)
PSS = nrPSSExtraction[nrData, pssStartSample,
  nrNFFT, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PSSExtractionViewPlot]];
(* nr Phase Correction and Extrapolation *)
xLine = nrPhaseCorrection[PSS, GenerateAllPSS[],
  nrNID2, ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PhaseCorrectionViewPlot]];
phaseCorr = nrPhaseExtrapolation[xLine, nrSSBSC,
  ViewPlot -> OptionValue[PhaseCorrectionViewPlot]];
If[flag, nrDataBlock = Drop[nrDataBlock, -1];
  nrTimeBlock = Drop[nrTimeBlock, -1]];
If[numerology ≠ 3,
  nrSlotDatawithPrev = Map[Partition[#, nrSlotLength] &, nrDataBlockwithPrev];
  nrSymbolswithPrev = Map[MapIndexed[removenrCPx[#1, nrNFFT, nrCPlenforLongSyms,
    nrCPlenforOtherSyms, numerology, #2] &, #] &, nrSlotDatawithPrev];
  nrFreqDomainwithPrev = Map[Map[Map[nrDataExtraction[#, nrNFFT, nrSSBSC] &, #] &,
    #] &, nrSymbolswithPrev];
  symbolsuncorrwithPrev = Map[Apply[Join, #] &, nrFreqDomainwithPrev],
  finalslotsflattened = nrDataFormatNum3[nrDataBlockwithPrev, nrNFFT];
  nrSymbolswithPrevfinal = {};
  For[ii = 1, ii < Length[finalslotsflattened] + 1, ii++,
    nrSymbolswithPrev = removenrCPx[finalslotsflattened[[ii]], nrNFFT,
      nrCPlenforLongSyms, nrCPlenforOtherSyms, numerology, ii];
    nrSymbolswithPrevfinal = Append[nrSymbolswithPrevfinal, nrSymbolswithPrev];
  ];
  nrSymbolswithPrev =
    Partition[Flatten[nrSymbolswithPrevfinal, 1], {140 * 2^(numerology - 1)}];
  nrFreqDomainwithPrev = Map[Map[nrDataExtraction[#, nrNFFT, nrSSBSC] &, #] &,
    nrSymbolswithPrev];
  symbolsuncorrwithPrev = nrFreqDomainwithPrev;
];
symbolscorrwithPrev = Map[Map[# / phaseCorr &, #] &, symbolsuncorrwithPrev];
symbolscorrwithPrev = If[Length[symbolscorrwithPrev[[-1]]] == 0,
  Drop[symbolscorrwithPrev, -1], symbolscorrwithPrev];
If[OptionValue[UncorrectedSymbolViewPlot],
  Print[Map[Manipulate[ConstellationPlot#[[i]],
    PlotRange → Max[Abs[nrFreqDomainwithPrev]] * {{-1, 1}, {-1, 1}},
    {i, 1, 140 * 2^(numerology - 1), 1}] &,
    Map[Map[Drop[#, {Length[#] / 2 + 1}] &, #] &, symbolscorrwithPrev]]];
finalcorrected = If[numerology == 1 || numerology == 3, SymbolChannelEstimCorrect[

```

```

symbolscorrwithPrev, PSSindexes, numerology], symbolscorrwithPrev];
If[OptionValue[CorrectedSymbolViewPlot],
Print[Map[Manipulate[ConstellationPlot#[#[[i]],
PlotRange → Max[Abs[nrFreqDomainwithPrev]] * {{-1, 1}, {-1, 1}}, {i, 1,
140 * 2^(numerology - 1), 1}] &, Map[Map[Drop[#, {Length[#]/2 + 1}] &, #] &,
finalcorrected]]]]; (*Plot without DC carrier*)
(* Get powers of each resource grid and save*)
symbolscorr = finalcorrected;
CellIds = nrCellID;
header = {Join[{"Cell ID"}, {ToString[CellIds]}]};
FrameNumbers = Array[# &, Length[symbolscorr]];
SymbolNumbers = Map[Array[# &, Length[#] &, symbolscorr];
symbolscorrnew = Map[Map[Drop[#, {Length[#]/2 + 1}] &, #] &, symbolscorr];
(*Remove DC Carrier for writing the resource grid*)
FrameNumberFinal =
MapThread[ConstantArray[#1, Length[#2]] &, {FrameNumbers, SymbolNumbers}];
fullresourcegrid = MapThread[MapThread[ColCreate[DB[Abs[#1]], ColName →
"Bin Power", ColUnit → "dB", ColParams → {#2, #3}] &, {#1, #2, #3}] &,
{symbolscorrnew, FrameNumberFinal, SymbolNumbers}];
xaxis = ColCreate[Array[# &, Length[fullresourcegrid[[1]][[1]]]],
ColName → "Subcarrier Number", ColParams → {"Frame Number", "Symbol Number"}];
FileWrite[StringTrim[scopefile, ".bin"] <> ".fullgrid.csv", FileCreate[Join[
{xaxis}, Flatten[fullresourcegrid]], FileHeader → header], FileLegend → 2];
Return[{nrCellID, finalcorrected}];
];

```

4.5. 5G NR Decoding

```

FileSelect[filemeas, "*.bin"] (*Select scope file to decode*)
{nrCellID, finalcorrected} = nrDecode[filemeas];

```

4.6. Additional Functions

4.6.1 DMRS Detection

```
SSBindex = 1;
allDMRS = GenerateAllDMRS[nrCellID, Lmax];
DMRSPBCH = QPSKDemod[allDMRS[[SSBindex]]];
PBCHcorr =
    GetPBCH[finalcorrected, nrCellID, Lmax, PSSindexes, SSBindex, numerology];
CheckDMRS[PBCHcorr, DMRSPBCH]
```

4.6.2 Get MIB Information

4.6.2.1 Check Rate Matching Start

```
PBCHdecodedinbits = DemodulatePBCH[nrCellID, SSBindex, PBCHcorr];
Nratematch = 512;
PBCHCheckRateMatching[PBCHdecodedinbits, Nratematch]
```

4.6.2.2 Rate Matching and Subblock deinterleaving

```
channelencoded = RateandDeinterleave[PBCHdecodedinbits, Nratematch];
```

4.6.2.3 Polar Decoding

```
cfound = PolarDecoding[channelencoded, Nratematch];
```

4.6.2.4 Remove Check Sum

```
datawoCRC = RemoveChecksum[cfound];
```

4.6.2.5 Descrambling for Payload and get MIB information

```
{SFN, subcarpaccommon, SSBscffsetdetected, dmrstypeApos, coresetzero,
    searchspacezero, cellbarred, intrafreqresel} = GetMIB[datawoCRC, nrCellID, Lmax];
```

```

TableForm[{"Subcarrier Spacing Common",
  If[subcarspaccommon == {0}, "15 kHz or 60 kHz", "30 kHz or 120 kHz"]},
{"DMRS Type A Position", If[dmrstypeApos == {0}, 2, 3]},
{"SSB Subcarrier Offset", If[FromDigits[SSBscoffsetdetected, 2] <= 23,
  ToString[FromDigits[SSBscoffsetdetected, 2]],
  "Attention! kSSB = " <> ToString[FromDigits[SSBscoffsetdetected, 2]] <>
  " which is larger than >23. Therefore, SIB1 is not available"}],
{"System Frame Number", FromDigits[SFN, 2]},
{"Coreset Zero", FromDigits[coresetzero, 2]},
{"Search Space Zero", FromDigits[searchspacezero, 2]},
{"Cell Barred", If[cellbarred == {0}, "Barred", "Not Barred"]},
{"Intra Freq Reselection", If[intrafreqresel == {0}, "Allowed", "Not Allowed"]}]}

```

4.6.2.6 Decision on Configuration - Example (i.e. place of CORESET0 in the radio frame)

```

TableCORESET = ConstantArray[ConstantArray[5000, 4], 4];
(*Table 13-1*)
multiplexpattern = Join[ConstantArray[1, 8], ConstantArray[1000, 8]];
ncoresetrbs = Join[ConstantArray[96, 8], ConstantArray[1000, 8]];
ncoresetsymb =
  Join[ConstantArray[1, 4], ConstantArray[2, 4], ConstantArray[1000, 8]];
offsetrbs = {10, 12, 14, 16, 10, 12, 14, 16, 1000,
  1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000};
TableCORESET[[1]] = Transpose[Join[{multiplexpattern},
  {ncoresetrbs}, {ncoresetsymb}, {offsetrbs}]];
(*Table 13-2*)
multiplexpattern = Join[ConstantArray[1, 14], ConstantArray[1000, 2]];
ncoresetrbs =
  Join[ConstantArray[24, 8], ConstantArray[48, 6], ConstantArray[1000, 2]];
ncoresetsymb = Join[ConstantArray[2, 4], ConstantArray[3, 4], ConstantArray[1, 2],
  ConstantArray[2, 2], ConstantArray[3, 2], ConstantArray[1000, 2]];
offsetrbs = {5, 6, 7, 8, 5, 6, 7, 8, 18, 20, 18, 20, 18, 20, 1000, 1000};
TableCORESET[[2]] =
  Transpose[Join[{multiplexpattern}, {ncoresetrbs}, {ncoresetsymb}, {offsetrbs}]];
(*Table 13-3*)
multiplexpattern = Join[ConstantArray[1, 9], ConstantArray[1000, 7]];
ncoresetrbs =
  Join[ConstantArray[48, 6], ConstantArray[96, 3], ConstantArray[1000, 7]];
ncoresetsymb = Join[ConstantArray[1, 2], ConstantArray[2, 2],
  ConstantArray[3, 2], Range[1, 3], ConstantArray[1000, 7]];
offsetrbs = {2, 6, 2, 6, 2, 6, 28, 28, 28, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000, 1000};

```

```

TableCORESET[[3]] =
  Transpose[Join[{multiplexpattern}, {ncoresetrb}, {ncoresetsymb}, {offsetrbs}]];
(*Table 13-4*)
multiplexpattern = ConstantArray[1, 2^Length[searchspacezero]];
ncoresetrb =
  Join[ConstantArray[24, 10], ConstantArray[48, 2^Length[searchspacezero] - 1 - 9]];
ncoresetsymb = Join[ConstantArray[2, 5], ConstantArray[3, 5],
  ConstantArray[1, 3], ConstantArray[2, 2^Length[searchspacezero] - 1 - 12]];
offsetrbs = {0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 12, 14, 16, 12, 14, 16};
TableCORESET[[4]] =
  Transpose[Join[{multiplexpattern}, {ncoresetrb}, {ncoresetsymb}, {offsetrbs}]];
{multip, coresetrb, coresetsymb, coresetoffset} =
  Which[{numerology, subcarspaccommon[[1]]} == {0, 0},
    TableCORESET[[1]], {numerology, subcarspaccommon[[1]]} == {0, 1},
    TableCORESET[[2]], {numerology, subcarspaccommon[[1]]} == {1, 0},
    TableCORESET[[3]], {numerology, subcarspaccommon[[1]]} == {1, 1},
    TableCORESET[[4]][[FromDigits[coresetzero, 2] + 1]];
(*Table 13-11*)
Ocoresets = {0, 0, 2, 2, 5, 5, 7, 7, 0, 5, 0, 0, 2, 2, 5, 5};
numsearchspacesetsperslots = {1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1};
Mcoresets = {1, 0.5, 1, 0.5, 1, 0.5, 1, 0.5, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1};
FirstSymbolIndexcoresets = {0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2};
{Ocoreset, numsearchspacesetsperslot, Mcoreset, FirstSymbolIndexcoreset} =
  Transpose[Join[{Ocoresets}, {numsearchspacesetsperslots}, {Mcoresets},
    {FirstSymbolIndexcoresets}][[FromDigits[searchspacezero, 2] + 1]];
coresetslot = Mod[(Ocoreset * 2^numerology + Floor[(SSBindex - 1) * Mcoreset]),
  nrSlotperRadioFrame] + 1;
radioframecoreset0 =
  If[EvenQ[Floor[(Ocoreset * 2^numerology + Floor[(SSBindex - 1) * Mcoreset]) /
    nrSlotperRadioFrame, 2]], 0, 1] + 1;

```


ANNEX C

21NRM03 MEWS - Metrology for emerging wireless standards

Evaluation of the Reference On-the-Bench Experimental Setup

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1 Introduction

In this document, the evaluation of the 5G NR downlink transmission decoding algorithm together with the testbed developed in A3.1.4 is performed. The verification and the precision of the decoding are studied for different cases of transmission such as different 5G NR frequency range, center frequency, numerology and channel bandwidth. Moreover, the robustness of the RF power detection is also studied by applying different fading scenarios (i.e. multi-path fading propagation) obtained from ETSI TR 138 901 [1] to the 5G NR transmission signals.

Additionally, the SI-traceability of the measurements is also established and the measurement uncertainty is estimated following the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 (GUM) [2].

2 Measurement Setup Description

The measurement system for the demodulation of 5G NR downlink transmission to detect the RF power of signals of interest consists of two modules: Hardware and Software Modules (See Figure 1).

Using the hardware module, the 5G NR downlink transmission signal is passed through an RF down-mixer using a local oscillator to reduce the carrier frequency to IF. Then after applying a low-pass filter, this signal can be measured and recorded using an oscilloscope (IQ signal). Subsequently, the digital signal processing algorithm for the detection of RF powers of the whole resource grid can be applied on this recording to gather the synchronization signals. Last, the power analysis sub-module, which incorporates the compensation of the losses in the measurement chain and obtaining the power of signals of interest, can be applied on this signal to have the required power information of primary synchronization signal (PSS), secondary synchronization signal (SSS) and demodulation reference signal for physical broadcast channel (DMRS-PBCH). In this report, the powers of PSS and SSS resource elements (REs) are investigated for the accuracy of the detection method. Similar approach can be applied for DMRS-PBCH when required.

Figure 1. Block Diagram of the Measurement Setup

The document "Experimental On-The-Bench Setup for 5G NR IQ Waveforms" dated January 31, 2024 describing the works in A3.1.4 explains the hardware module and the measurement principles more in detail. Moreover, the document "Software Implementation of A3.1.2 for RF Power Detection of 5G NR Downlink Transmission Signals" dated December 22, 2023 explains the detection algorithm and the software module. These documents can be consulted when needed.

3 Measurement Scenarios

3.1 Selection of Scenario Parameters

5G NR transmissions can have different numerologies, which changes the subcarrier spacing, and thus affecting the demodulation procedure. Different number of synchronization symbol blocks (SSBs) are defined for different frequency ranges (See the document "Review of 5G NR ETSI TS 138 211 for Key Parameters for the Identification of the RF Power of the Resource Grid Allocation" from A3.1.1 for more details). In order to evaluate the demodulation algorithm together with the testbed, different numerologies, frequency ranges and also channel bandwidths are considered.

For the assessment of the robustness of the detection algorithm, different fading scenarios are also selected and applied depending on the frequency range. Annex explains the details of the fading scenarios from [1].

The parameters selected for the evaluation are given in Table 1.

Carrier Frequencies	Numerologies	Fading Scenarios	Channel Bandwidth
800 MHz, 3500 MHz and 25955 MHz	0, 1 and 3	TDLA30-5 (FR1) TDLA30-10 (FR1) TDLB100-400 (FR1) TDLC300-100 (FR1) TDLA30-75 (FR2) TDLA30-300 (FR2) (See Annex for details)	20 MHz and 50 MHz

Table 1. Selected Parameters for Scenario Definitions

To ensure a good comparison and repeatability, the fading scenarios were generated with the built-in fading generator block in the 5G NR signal generator.

3.2 Definition of Measurement Scenarios

The selected measurements scenarios for the evaluation of the algorithm and the experimental setup are given in Table 2 below.

Scenario Number	Numerology	Frequency Range	Center Frequency (MHz)	Fading Scenario	Channel Bandwidth (MHz)
1	0	FR1	800	None	20
2	0	FR1	3500	None	20
3	1	FR1	800	None	20
4	1	FR1	3500	None	20
5	0	FR1	800	TDLA30-5	20
6	0	FR1	3500	TDLA30-5	20
7	1	FR1	800	TDLA30-5	20
8	1	FR1	3500	TDLA30-5	20
9	0	FR1	800	TDLA30-10	20
10	0	FR1	3500	TDLA30-10	20
11	1	FR1	800	TDLA30-10	20
12	1	FR1	3500	TDLA30-10	20
13	0	FR1	800	TDLB100-400	20
14	0	FR1	3500	TDLB100-400	20
15	1	FR1	800	TDLB100-400	20
16	1	FR1	3500	TDLB100-400	20
17	0	FR1	800	TDLC300-100	20
18	0	FR1	3500	TDLC300-100	20
19	1	FR1	800	TDLC300-100	20
20	1	FR1	3500	TDLC300-100	20
21	3	FR2	25955	None	50
22	3	FR2	25955	TDLA30-75	50
23	3	FR2	25955	TDLA30-300	50

Table 2. Selected Measurement Scenarios

4 Transmission Correction and SI Traceability

As mentioned in the document "Experimental On-The-Bench Setup for 5G NR IQ Waveforms" from A3.1.4 dated January 31, 2024, SI traceability of the measurements are established using a calibrated power meter. A single-tone sine wave is sequentially generated at all selected center frequencies given in Table 2 and measured with a calibrated power meter. Then, the same signal is measured using the hardware module of the measurement chain, and the results are compared and processed to obtain the corresponding correction factor. In this way, the path loss and other imperfections in the transmission can be compensated (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Setup for Establishing SI Traceability

During the calibration, the power levels of the linear operation region of the hardware module are observed. The calibration is performed at -4 dBm input power level for FR1 and 0 dBm input power level for FR2. These selected power levels are applied on the peak envelope power (PEP) level during the measurements in order to ensure the linear operation of components in the measurement setup.

The correction factors resulting from the calibration are applied to the hardware module readings. In this way, the traceability to known power reference is established.

The detailed measurement uncertainty calculations are given in the Section 6.

5 Measurements

5.1 Measurement Setup

In the final measurements, the power delivered to hardware module is constantly monitored using the power meter over a calibrated power splitter to control the stability of 5G signal generation. The block diagram of the setup for FR1 is given in Figure 3 and for FR2 in Figure 4. It is important to note that 5G generator used in the setup cannot deliver signals in FR2, it has an output frequency limited to 6 GHz. Therefore, it requires an additional up-mixing stage to increase the center frequency to FR2 range for the corresponding measurements.

Figure 3. Final Measurement Setup for FR1 (Scenarios 1 to 20)

Figure 4. Final Measurement Setup for FR2 (Scenarios 21 to 23)

Figure 5 depicts the setups for FR1 and FR2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Measurement Setup in (a) FR1 (b) FR2

During the measurements, the 5G generator operated in constant power spectrum density (Constant PSD) mode to keep the RF power of all resource elements constant. The selected number of SSBs were equal to L_{\max} (i.e. maximum number of SSBs for the selected center frequency), which are

- 4 for $f \leq 3$ GHz,
- 8 for $3 \text{ GHz} < f \leq 6$ GHz
- 64 for $6 \text{ GHz} < f$

Full traffic case (100% Traffic) was considered for all scenarios, which helps the illustration of the fading on the power of the whole resource grid.

5.2 Components List

Component	Brand and Model	Function
Vector Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz, SMW200A	5G Signal Generator
Synthesized Sweeper	HP, 83650A	Local Oscillator
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz, NRP-Z91	Power Meter
Power Splitter	Weinschel, PS-018	Power Splitter
Low pass Filter	Mini-Circuits, ZX75LP-83-S+	Low Pass Filter
RF Mixer	Mini-Circuits, ZX05-43LH-S+	Frequency Down-mixer
Oscilloscope	Agilent, Infiniium DSO90254A	Oscilloscope

Table 3. Components List for Measurements in FR1 (Scenarios 1 to 20)

Component	Brand and Model	Function
Vector Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz, SMW200A	5G Signal Generator
Synthesized Sweeper	HP, 83650A	Local Oscillator for Up-mixing
Swept CW Generator	HP, 83650L	Local Oscillator for Down-mixing
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz, NRV-Z52	Power Meter
Power Splitter	HP, 11667B	Power Splitter
Low pass Filter	Mini-Circuits, ZX75LP-83-S+	Low Pass Filter
RF Mixer	Mitec, DB0226HA1	Frequency Up-mixer
RF Mixer	Mitec, DB0226LA1	Frequency Down-mixer
Oscilloscope	Agilent, Infiniium DSO90254A	Oscilloscope

Table 4. Components List for Measurements in FR2 (Scenarios 21 to 23)

5.3 Power Levels

The selected PEP levels, at which the calibration of the setup is performed, and the corresponding RF power level for max. number of SSBs are given in Table 5.

Scenario Number	Selected PEP Level (dBm)	RF Power Level for max. number of SSBs (dBm)
1	-4	-14.69
2	-4	-14.78
3	-4	-14.71
4	-4	-15.04
5	-4	-24.69
6	-4	-24.78
7	-4	-24.71
8	-4	-25.04
9	-4	-24.69
10	-4	-24.78
11	-4	-24.71
12	-4	-25.04
13	-4	-24.69
14	-4	-24.78
15	-4	-24.71
16	-4	-25.04
17	-4	-24.69
18	-4	-24.78
19	-4	-24.71
20	-4	-25.04
21	0	-11.03
22	0	-21.03
23	0	-21.03

Table 5. Selected PEP levels and RF Power Levels for Max. Number of SSBs

5.4 Measurement Results

Each scenario is measured three times with the testbed and the measurements are analysed using the software module. A detailed analysis for PSS and SSS resource element (RE) power detection is made for the scenarios without fading. For the scenarios with fading, the detected PSS and SSS RE powers and the maximum deviation between three measurements are given and the heat map of the resource grid power are depicted for the visualization of the effects of different fading characteristics.

5.4.1 Power Analysis for the scenarios without fading

The power of each RE in either PSS and SSS can be calculated as given in (1):

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} \times \text{Subcarrier Spacing}_{\text{Hz}}) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{\text{Set Power}_{\text{dBm}}}{10}}}{\text{Bandwidth}_{\text{Hz}}} \quad (2)$$

The theoretical RE power calculation for Scenario 1 is performed as follows:

For Set Power = -14.69 dBm, Bandwidth = 20 MHz and SCS = 15 kHz (i.e. numerology 0)

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{-14.69}{10}}}{20 \times 10^6} = 1.6981 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mW/Hz} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(1.6981 \times 10^{-9} \times 15000) = -45.94 \text{ dBm} \quad (4)$$

This calculation is repeated for Scenarios 1 to 4 and also for Scenario 23.

For each scenario without fading, Table 6 and Table 7 present the PSS and SSS RE power analysis, respectively. These tables include the theoretical and the calculated RE powers, the differences of these values and the standard deviations of RE powers in a subframe.

Measured RE power is calculated for both PSS and SSS as follows: For the first measurement, the average value of all detected PSS or SSS RE powers is calculated. This calculation is repeated for all three measurements and the average of three measurements is obtained. The standard deviation is also calculated similarly.

These results show that the theoretical and the measured RE powers for both PSS and SSS match very well with a low standard deviation, proving the stability of the detection algorithm and the testbed.

Scenario Number	Set Power on Generator (dBm)	Theoretical RE Power (dBm)	Measured PSS RE Power (dBm)	Difference of Theoretical Value and Measured Value (dB)	Standard Deviation of PSS RE Powers in a Subframe (dB)
1	-14.69	-45.94	-45.99	0.05	0.011
2	-14.78	-46.03	-46.12	0.09	0.013
3	-14.71	-42.95	-43.03	0.08	0.014
4	-15.04	-43.28	-43.32	0.04	0.043
21	-11.03	-37.23	-37.21	-0.02	0.094

Table 6. PSS RE Power Analysis

Scenario Number	Set Power on Generator (dBm)	Theoretical RE Power (dBm)	Measured SSS RE Power (dBm)	Difference of Theoretical Value and Measured Value (dB)	Standard Deviation of SSS RE Powers in a Subframe (dB)
1	-14.69	-45.94	-46.00	0.06	0.010
2	-14.78	-46.03	-46.10	0.07	0.043
3	-14.71	-42.95	-43.03	0.08	0.010
4	-15.04	-43.28	-43.29	0.01	0.036
21	-11.03	-37.23	-37.27	0.04	0.074

Table 7. SSS RE Power Analysis

5.4.2 Power of PSS and SSS REs for the scenarios with fading

For the scenarios with fading, PSS and SSS RE Powers are also measured for three times and the analysis is performed similar to the scenarios without fading. The deviation between these measurements is analysed for understanding the effect of fading for different cases. Table 8 and Table 9 present these results for PSS and SSS, respectively. It can be observed that fading causes a change in the detected RF power of REs as expected. The deviation in the power reached up to 9.75 dB in the measurements.

In order to visualize the effects of different fading characteristics, the heat maps of the whole resource grid are obtained for each scenario. These heat maps are given from Figure 6 to Figure 15. Please note that these snapshots were taken from the resource grid region around the SSBs. REs of SSBs set to value 0 can be seen with rectangular shapes at the

start of the resource grid, having the colour of dark red (representing very low power). These illustrations have the sole purpose of displaying the fading effects and does not include the detailed quantitative analysis.

Scenario Number	Measured PSS RE Power M1 (dBm)	Measured PSS RE Power M2 (dBm)	Measured PSS RE Power M3 (dBm)	Maximum Deviation between Measurements (dB)
5	-54.94	-54.06	-58.68	4.64
6	-52.12	-54.45	-50.18	4.27
7	-51.39	-50.49	-53.32	2.83
8	-50.46	-50.57	-51.30	0.84
9	-49.41	-52.16	-56.23	6.82
10	-52.55	-53.80	-55.05	2.50
11	-50.48	-52.07	-50.11	1.96
12	-53.42	-50.67	-50.73	2.75
13	-57.04	-63.74	-55.35	8.39
14	-63.94	-60.67	-54.96	8.98
15	-53.19	-57.27	-54.42	4.08
16	-56.23	-53.92	-52.22	4.01
17	-58.83	-53.40	-54.92	5.43
18	-61.27	-61.92	-56.36	5.56
19	-57.61	-55.68	-51.23	6.38
20	-51.58	-59.68	-52.98	8.10
22	-46.04	-44.81	-49.73	4.92
23	-44.24	-42.73	-44.17	1.51

Table 8. PSS REs Power Analysis for Scenarios with Fading

Scenario Number	Measured SSS	Measured SSS	Measured SSS	Maximum Deviation between Measurements (dB)
	RE Power M1 (dBm)	RE Power M2 (dBm)	RE Power M3 (dBm)	
5	-54.95	-53.88	-58.68	4.80
6	-52.08	-54.50	-50.27	4.23
7	-51.40	-50.48	-53.31	2.83
8	-50.47	-50.58	-51.24	0.77
9	-49.36	-52.17	-56.16	6.80
10	-52.55	-53.70	-54.93	2.38
11	-50.50	-52.06	-50.11	1.95
12	-53.43	-50.68	-50.72	2.75
13	-57.43	-63.75	-57.65	6.32
14	-64.22	-56.44	-54.47	9.75
15	-53.49	-57.64	-54.55	4.15
16	-55.01	-53.72	-52.29	2.72
17	-58.93	-53.54	-54.92	5.39
18	-61.18	-60.97	-56.88	4.30
19	-57.22	-55.93	-51.27	5.95
20	-51.29	-60.10	-52.85	8.81
22	-46.01	-44.77	-49.80	5.03
23	-44.15	-42.56	-44.14	1.59

Table 9. SSS REs Power Analysis for Scenarios with Fading

Figure 6. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 5 (Left) and 6 (Right) (TDLA30-5 Fading)

Figure 7. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 7 (Left) and 8 (Right) (TDLA30-5 Fading)

Figure 8. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 9 (Left) and 10 (Right) (TDLA30-10 Fading)

Figure 9. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 11 (Left) and 12 (Right) (TDLA30-10 Fading)

Figure 10. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 13 (Left) and 14 (Right) (TDLB100-400 Fading)

Figure 11. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 15 (Left) and 16 (Right) (TDLB100-400 Fading)

Figure 12. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 17 (Left) and 18 (Right) (TDLC300-100 Fading)

Figure 13. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 19 (Left) and 20 (Right) (TDL300-100 Fading)

Figure 14. Heat Map for Resource Grid Power of Scenario 22 (TDLA30-75 Fading)

Figure 15. Heat Map for Resource Grid Power of Scenario 23 (TDLA30-300 Fading)

6 Measurement Uncertainty

6.1 Sources of Uncertainty

There are 5 influencing factors which contribute to the measurement uncertainty according to the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 [2].

1. Uncertainty of power reference: In the setup, two different calibrated power meters are used for establishing the SI traceability. In the calibration certificates of the power meters, the uncertainties of these power references are given. Depending on the type and the quality of the power meter, this uncertainty changes. It was found out that the power meter used for FR1 has lower standard uncertainty (0.025 dB) than the one used in FR2 (0.060 dB).
2. Resolution of oscilloscope: The oscilloscope used in the measurement chain has 8-bit resolution. The uncertainty in the voltage amplitude measured by the oscilloscope has a rectangular distribution with distribution factor of 1.73. The amount of the uncertainty is calculated as follows:

$$u_{\text{scope}}(\text{dB}) = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2 \times 2^8} \right) = 0.017 \text{ dB} \quad (5)$$

3. Frequency response of the measurement chain: The characterization of the measurement chain using conventional measurement methods such as a VNA or similar would yield the uncertainty contribution from the frequency response of the measurement chain. This effect includes also the broadband characteristics of the chain. In this application, a signal having a bandwidth up to 50 MHz is measured using the chain. The RF mixer and the bandpass filters do not have the same conversion loss throughout the band. This source of uncertainty also considers this factor. The values of 0.03 dB and 0.08 dB for FR1 and FR2 respectively are obtained from the calibration of the chain and the conversion loss characteristics of RF mixer and bandpass filters.
4. Stability of SSS measurements: This factor is obtained by the overestimation of the standard deviation of 100 different SSS measurements.
5. Reproducibility: This source of uncertainty has been investigated and the corresponding contribution of 0.01 dB has been found by repeating measurements for the decoding of the whole resource grid for the exact same configuration.

6.2 Calculation of Measurement Uncertainty Budgets for Different Frequencies

The calculation of the measurement uncertainty budget according to [2] for each center frequency in Table 2 are given in from Table 10 to Table 12.

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty (dB)	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.025	Normal	2	0.013
2	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
3	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.030	Rectangular	1.73	0.017
4	Stability of SSS measurements	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
5	Reproducibility	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
Total (k=1)					0.028
Total (k=2)					0.056

Table 10. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for FR1 800 MHz Measurements

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty (dB)	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.025	Normal	2	0.013
2	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
3	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.030	Rectangular	1.73	0.017
4	Stability of SSS measurements	0.015	Normal	1	0.015
5	Reproducibility	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
Total (k=1)					0.030
Total (k=2)					0.060

Table 11. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for FR1 3500 MHz Measurements

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty (dB)	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.060	Normal	2	0.030
2	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
3	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.080	Rectangular	1.73	0.046
4	Stability of SSS measurements	0.015	Normal	1	0.015
5	Reproducibility	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
Total (k=1)					0.059
Total (k=2)					0.118

Table 12. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for FR2 25955 MHz Measurements

6.3 Discussion on Measurement Uncertainty Budget

The measurement uncertainties reported in this document have been obtained by using the components given in Chapter 5.2. The calculations show that the goal measurement uncertainty of 0.05 dB (k=2) has almost been achieved for the measurements at 800 MHz and 3500 MHz. In FR2 at 25955 MHz, the uncertainty has increased due to the power reference uncertainty and the frequency response uncertainty of the measurement chain.

In order to reduce the overall uncertainty of the measurements, each of these main influencing factors can be examined. The frequency response of the measurement chain can be improved by using adapted and stable components to have lower uncertainty. Moreover, the power meter utilized in the calibration method can also be replaced with a more precise sensor to improve the uncertainty. The measurement uncertainty budget analysis is performed here for SSS. For PSS and DMRS-PBCH, a similar approach can be employed.

7 References

[1] ETSI TR 138 901, "5G; Study on channel model for frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz", v17.0 Release 17, 2022.04.

[2] JCGM 100:2008 (GUM), "*Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement*", First Edition, 2008.

Annex Fading Scenarios

Multi-path fading propagation conditions

The multipath propagation conditions consist of several parts [1]:

- A delay profile in the form of a "tapped delay-line", characterized by a number of taps at fixed positions on a sampling grid. The profile can be further characterized by the RMS delay spread and the maximum delay spanned by the taps [1].
- A combination of channel model parameters that include the Delay profile and the Doppler spectrum that is characterized by a classical spectrum shape and a maximum Doppler frequency [1].
- Different models are used for FR1 and FR2 [1].

Delay Profiles for FR1

The delay profiles for FR1 are selected to be representative of low, medium and high delay spread environment [1]. The resulting model parameters are specified in Table 13 and the tapped delay line models are specified from Table 14 to Table 16.

Model	Number of channel taps	Delay spread (RMS)	Maximum excess tap delay (span)	Delay resolution
TDLA30	12	30 ns	290 ns	5 ns
TDLB100	12	100 ns	480 ns	5 ns
TDLC300	12	300 ns	2595 ns	5 ns

Table 13. Delay profiles for NR channel models for FR1 [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-15.5	Rayleigh
2	10	0	Rayleigh
3	15	-5.1	Rayleigh
4	20	-5.1	Rayleigh
5	25	-9.6	Rayleigh
6	50	-8.2	Rayleigh
7	65	-13.1	Rayleigh
8	75	-11.5	Rayleigh
9	105	-11.0	Rayleigh
10	135	-16.2	Rayleigh
11	150	-16.6	Rayleigh
12	290	-26.2	Rayleigh

Table 14. TDLA30 (DS = 30 ns) [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	0	Rayleigh
2	10	-2.2	Rayleigh
3	20	-0.6	Rayleigh
4	30	-0.6	Rayleigh
5	35	-0.3	Rayleigh
6	45	-1.2	Rayleigh
7	55	-5.9	Rayleigh
8	120	-2.2	Rayleigh
9	170	-0.8	Rayleigh
10	245	-6.3	Rayleigh
11	330	-7.5	Rayleigh
12	480	-7.1	Rayleigh

Table 15. TDLB100 (DS = 100 ns) [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-6.9	Rayleigh
2	65	0	Rayleigh
3	70	-7.7	Rayleigh
4	190	-2.5	Rayleigh
5	195	-2.4	Rayleigh
6	200	-9.9	Rayleigh
7	240	-8.0	Rayleigh
8	325	-6.6	Rayleigh
9	520	-7.1	Rayleigh
10	1045	-13.0	Rayleigh
11	1510	-14.2	Rayleigh
12	2595	-16.0	Rayleigh

Table 16. TDLC300 (DS = 300 ns) [1]

Delay Profiles for FR2

The delay profiles for FR2 are specified in Table 17 and the tapped delay line models are specified from Table 18 to Table 21.

Model	Number of channel taps	Delay spread (RMS)	Maximum excess tap delay (span)	Delay resolution
TDLA30	12	30 ns	290 ns	5 ns
TDLA10	16	10 ns	96 ns	2 ns
TDLD10	10	10 ns	126 ns	2 ns
TDLD30	10	30 ns	375	5 ns

Table 17. Delay profiles for NR channel models for FR2 [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-15.5	Rayleigh
2	10	0	Rayleigh
3	15	-5.1	Rayleigh
4	20	-5.1	Rayleigh
5	25	-9.6	Rayleigh
6	50	-8.2	Rayleigh
7	65	-13.1	Rayleigh
8	75	-11.5	Rayleigh
9	105	-11.0	Rayleigh
10	135	-16.2	Rayleigh
11	150	-16.6	Rayleigh
12	290	-26.2	Rayleigh

Table 18. TDLA30 (DS = 30 ns) [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-16.1	Rayleigh
2	4	0	
3	6	-4	
4	8	-10.2	
5	16	-18.6	
6	18	-9.3	
7	22	-13.7	
8	24	-17.9	
9	26	-13.5	
10	30	-14	
11	40	-15.4	
12	44	-18.9	
13	46	-21.0	
14	48	-21.6	
15	50	-19.3	
16	96	-25.9	

Table 19. TDLA10 (DS = 30 ns) [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-15.5	LOS Rayleigh
	0	0	
2	6	-5.1	
3	14	-5.1	
4	18	-9.6	
5	26	-8.2	
6	40	-13.1	
7	80	-11.5	
8	94	-11.0	
9	98	-16.2	
10	126	-16.6	

Note: Tap #1 follow a Ricean distribution

Table 20. TDLD10 (DS = 10 ns) [1]

Tap #1	Delay (ns)	Power (dB)	Fading Distribution
1	0	-0.2	LOS Rayleigh
	0	-12.4	
2	20	-21	
3	40	-16.7	
4	55	-18.3	
5	80	-21.9	
6	120	-27.8	
7	240	-23.6	
8	285	-24.8	
9	290	-30.0	
10	375	-27.6	

Note: Tap #1 follow a Ricean distribution

Table 21. TDLD30 (DS = 30 ns) [1]

Combinations of channel model parameters

The propagation conditions used for the performance measurements in multi-path fading environment are indicated as a combination of a channel model name and a maximum Doppler frequency, i.e., TDLA<DS>-<Doppler>, TDLB<DS>- <Doppler> or TDLC<DS>-<Doppler> where '<DS>' indicates the desired delay spread and '<Doppler>' indicates the maximum Doppler frequency (Hz) [1].

Table 22 and Table 23 show the propagation conditions that are used for the performance measurements in multipath fading environment for low, medium and high Doppler frequencies for FR1 and FR2, respectively [1].

Combination Name	Tapped Delay Line Model	Maximum Doppler Frequency
TDLA30-5	TDLA30	5 Hz
TDLA30-10	TDLA30	10 Hz
TDLB100-400	TDLB100	400 Hz
TDLC300-100	TDLC300	100 Hz
TDLC300-600	TDLC300	600 Hz
TDLC300-1200	TDLC300	1200 Hz

Table 22. Channel model parameters for FR1 [1]

Combination Name	Tapped Delay Line Model	Maximum Doppler Frequency
TDLA30-75	TDLA30	75 Hz
TDLA30-300	TDLA30	300 Hz
TDLA10-650	TDLA10	650 Hz
TDLA30-650	TDLA30	650 Hz
TDLD10-200	TDLD10	200 Hz
TDLD30-200	TDLD30	200 Hz

Table 23. Channel model parameters for FR2 [1]

ANNEX D

21NRM03 MEWS - Metrology for emerging wireless standards

Evaluation of the 5G Decoding Algorithm with Over-the-Air Experimental Setup

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1 Introduction

In this document, the evaluation of the 5G NR downlink transmission decoding algorithm defined in MEWS activity A3.1.2 and developed in A3.1.3 with an over-the-air testbed is explained in detail. The over-the-air setup is a modified version of the setup defined in A3.2.1. The verification and the precision of the decoding are studied for the scenarios created for MEWS activity A3.2.1 [1] with the over-the-air measurements. Moreover, the robustness of the RF power detection is here also studied for different fading scenarios.

Additionally, the SI-traceability of the measurements is also established for the over-the-air measurements and the measurement uncertainty is estimated following the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 (GUM) [2].

2 Measurement System Description

The measurement system for the demodulation of 5G NR downlink transmission to detect the RF power of signals of interest consists of two modules: Hardware and Software Modules (See Figure 1). Please refer [1] for more details on the operation principles.

Figure 1. Block Diagram of the Measurement Setup

Additionally, [3] and [4] can be consulted for the details on the hardware module and software modules, respectively.

3 Measurement Scenarios

3.1 Definition of Measurement Scenarios

The selected measurements scenarios for the evaluation of the algorithm and the experimental setup are already defined in A3.2.1 and given again in Table 1 below.

Scenario Number	Numerology	Frequency Range	Center Frequency (MHz)	Fading Scenario	Channel Bandwidth (MHz)
1	0	FR1	800	None	20
2	0	FR1	3500	None	20
3	1	FR1	800	None	20
4	1	FR1	3500	None	20
5	0	FR1	800	TDLA30-5	20
6	0	FR1	3500	TDLA30-5	20
7	1	FR1	800	TDLA30-5	20
8	1	FR1	3500	TDLA30-5	20
9	0	FR1	800	TDLA30-10	20
10	0	FR1	3500	TDLA30-10	20
11	1	FR1	800	TDLA30-10	20
12	1	FR1	3500	TDLA30-10	20
13	0	FR1	800	TDLB100-400	20
14	0	FR1	3500	TDLB100-400	20
15	1	FR1	800	TDLB100-400	20
16	1	FR1	3500	TDLB100-400	20
17	0	FR1	800	TDLC300-100	20
18	0	FR1	3500	TDLC300-100	20
19	1	FR1	800	TDLC300-100	20
20	1	FR1	3500	TDLC300-100	20
21	3	FR2	25955	None	50
22	3	FR2	25955	TDLA30-75	50
23	3	FR2	25955	TDLA30-300	50

Table 1. Selected Measurement Scenarios

4 Transmission Correction and SI Traceability

Similar to the study in [1], SI traceability of the measurements are established using a calibrated power meter. A single-tone sine wave is sequentially generated at all selected center frequencies given in Table 1 and transmitted over the transmitting antenna towards the measuring setup. The signal received over the receiving antenna is measured with a calibrated power meter. Then, the same received signal is measured using the hardware module of the measurement chain, and the results are compared and processed to obtain the corresponding correction factor. In this way, the path loss and other imperfections in the transmission can be compensated (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Setup for Establishing SI Traceability

During the calibration, the power levels of the linear operation region of the hardware module are observed. The calibration is performed at 3 dBm input power level for 800 MHz and 6 dBm input power level for 3500 MHz and 25955 MHz. These selected power levels are applied on the peak envelope power (PEP) level during the measurements in order to ensure the linear operation of components in the measurement setup.

The correction factors resulting from the calibration are applied to the hardware module readings. In this way, the traceability to known power reference is established.

The detailed measurement uncertainty calculations are given in the Section 6.

5 Measurements

5.1 Overview

The block diagram of the setup for FR1 (800 MHz and 3500 MHz) is given in Figure 3 and for FR2 (25955 MHz) in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Final Measurement Setup for FR1 (Scenarios 1 to 20)

Figure 4. Final Measurement Setup for FR2 (Scenarios 21 to 23)

The measurements in FR1 were performed in the FAR of METAS, whereas the measurements in FR2 were performed in laboratory environment inside a faraday room. The details of each setup are given in the following subsections.

5.2 Measurement Setup for 800 MHz

Figure 5 depicts the setup for the scenarios with center frequency of 800 MHz (i.e., scenarios with odd-numbered index up to 19).

Figure 5. Measurement Setup for 800 MHz (a) Transmitting Side (b) Receiving Side

The components list for the measurements at 800 MHz is given in Table 2.

Component	Brand and Model	Function
Vector Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz, SMW200A	5G Signal Generator
Synthesized Sweeper	HP, 83650A	Local Oscillator
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz, NRP-Z91	Power Meter
Power Splitter	Weinschel, PS-018	Power Splitter
Low pass Filter	Mini-Circuits, ZX75LP-83-S+	Low Pass Filter
RF Mixer	Mini-Circuits, ZX05-43LH-S+	Frequency Down-mixer
Oscilloscope	Agilent, Infiniium DSO90254A	Oscilloscope
Antenna	Schwarzbeck, VUSLP 9111, SN 193	Transmitting Antenna
Antenna	Schwarzbeck, VUSLP 9111, SN 195	Receiving Antenna

Table 2. Components List for Measurements at 800 MHz

The tip-to-tip distance of the antennas was 1.4 m and the antennas were placed at a height of 1.6 m. The selections of the distance and the measurement height were arbitrary.

5.3 Measurement Setup for 3500 MHz

Figure 6 depicts the setup for the scenarios with center frequency of 3500 MHz (i.e., scenarios with even-numbered index up to 20).

Figure 6. Measurement Setup for 3500 MHz (a) Transmitting Side (b) Receiving Side

The components list for the measurements at 3500 MHz is given in Table 3.

Component	Brand and Model	Function
Vector Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz, SMW200A	5G Signal Generator
Synthesized Sweeper	HP, 83650A	Local Oscillator
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz, NRP-Z91	Power Meter
Power Splitter	Weinschel, PS-018	Power Splitter
Low pass Filter	Mini-Circuits, ZX75LP-83-S+	Low Pass Filter
RF Mixer	Mini-Circuits, ZX05-43LH-S+	Frequency Down-mixer
Oscilloscope	Agilent, Infiniium DSO90254A	Oscilloscope
Antenna	Schwarzbeck, BBHA 9120 D, SN 470	Transmitting Antenna
Antenna	Schwarzbeck, BBHA 9120 D, SN 516	Receiving Antenna

Table 3. Components List for Measurements at 3500 MHz

The tip-to-tip distance of the antennas was 1.7 m and the antennas were placed at a height of 1.6 m. The selections of the distance and the measurement height were arbitrary.

5.4 Measurement Setup for 25955 MHz

Figure 7 depicts the setup for the scenarios with center frequency of 25955 MHz (i.e., scenarios 21, 22 and 23).

Figure 7. Measurement Setup for 25955 MHz

The tip-to-tip distance of the antennas were 0.3 m. Thanks to the directive radiation pattern characteristics of the horn antennas and very high center frequency, the measurements could be performed out of FAR. The selection of the distance was arbitrary.

Component	Brand and Model	Function
Vector Signal Generator	Rohde & Schwarz, SMW200A	5G Signal Generator
Synthesized Sweeper	HP, 83650A	Local Oscillator for Up-mixing
Swept CW Generator	HP, 83650L	Local Oscillator for Down-mixing
Power Meter	Rohde & Schwarz, NRV-Z52	Power Meter
Power Splitter	HP, 11667B	Power Splitter
Low pass Filter	Mini-Circuits, ZX75LP-83-S+	Low Pass Filter
RF Mixer	Mitec, DB0226HA1	Frequency Up-mixer
RF Mixer	Mitec, DB0226LA1	Frequency Down-mixer
Oscilloscope	Agilent, Infiniium DSO90254A	Oscilloscope
Antenna	Flann, 20240-20, SN 134850	Transmitting Antenna
Antenna	Flann, 20240-20, SN 134849	Receiving Antenna

Table 4. Components List for Measurements at 25955 MHz

5.5 5G Signal Generation Settings

Similar to the measurements performed in A3.2.1, the 5G generator operated in constant power spectrum density (Constant PSD) mode to keep the RF power of all resource elements constant. The selected number of SSBs were equal to L_{\max} (i.e. maximum number of SSBs for the selected center frequency), which are

- 4 for $f \leq 3$ GHz,
- 8 for $3 \text{ GHz} < f \leq 6$ GHz
- 64 for $6 \text{ GHz} < f$

Full traffic case (100% Traffic) was considered for all scenarios, which helps the illustration of the fading on the power of the whole resource grid.

5.6 Power Levels

The selected peak envelope power (PEP) levels, at which the calibration of the setup is performed, and the corresponding RF power level for max. number of SSBs are given in Table 5.

Scenario Number	Selected PEP Level (dBm)	RF Power Level for max. number of SSBs (dBm)
1	3	-7.69
2	6	-4.78
3	3	-7.71
4	6	-5.04
5	3	-17.69
6	6	-14.78
7	3	-17.71
8	6	-15.04
9	3	-17.69
10	6	-14.78
11	3	-17.71
12	6	-15.04
13	3	-17.69
14	6	-14.78
15	3	-17.71
16	6	-15.04
17	3	-17.69
18	6	-14.78
19	3	-17.71
20	6	-15.04
21	6	-5.03
22	6	-15.03
23	6	-15.03

Table 5. Selected PEP levels and RF Power Levels for Max. Number of SSBs

The PEP levels were selected in order to have high SNR at the receiving side of the setup. As different antenna types have different gains, this adjustment was required.

5.7 Measurement Results

Each scenario was measured three times with the testbed and the measurements were analysed using the software module. A detailed analysis for PSS and SSS resource element (RE) power detection was made for the scenarios without fading. For the scenarios with fading, the detected PSS and SSS RE powers and the maximum deviation between three measurements are given and the heat map of the resource grid power are depicted for the visualization of the effects of different fading characteristics.

5.7.1 Power Analysis for the scenarios without fading

The power of each RE in either PSS and SSS can be calculated as given in (1):

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} \times \text{Subcarrier Spacing}_{\text{Hz}}) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{\text{Set Power}_{\text{dBm}}}{10}}}{\text{Bandwidth}_{\text{Hz}}} \quad (2)$$

The theoretical RE power calculation for Scenario 1 is performed as follows:

For Set Power = -7.69 dBm, Bandwidth = 20 MHz and SCS = 15 kHz (i.e. numerology 0)

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{-7.69}{10}}}{20 \times 10^6} = 8.511 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mW/Hz} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(8.511 \times 10^{-9} \times 15000) = -38.94 \text{ dBm} \quad (4)$$

This calculation is repeated for Scenarios 1 to 4 and also for Scenario 21.

For each scenario without fading, Table 6 and Table 7 present the PSS and SSS RE power analysis, respectively. These tables include the theoretical and the calculated RE powers, the differences of these values and the standard deviations of RE powers in a subframe.

Measured RE power is calculated for both PSS and SSS as follows: For the first measurement, the average value of all detected PSS or SSS RE powers is calculated. This calculation is repeated for all three measurements and the average of three measurements is

obtained. The standard deviation is also calculated similarly.

These results show that the theoretical and the measured RE powers for both PSS and SSS match very well with a low standard deviation, proving the stability of the detection algorithm and the testbed.

Scenario Number	Set Power on Generator (dBm)	Theoretical SSS RE Power (dBm)	Measured SSS RE Power (dBm)	Difference of Theoretical Value and Measured Value (dB)	Standard Deviation of SSS RE Powers in a Subframe (dB)
1	-7.69	-38.94	-38.79	-0.15	0.022
2	-4.78	-36.03	-36.32	0.29	0.109
3	-7.71	-35.95	-35.81	-0.14	0.022
4	-5.04	-33.28	-33.56	0.28	0.121
21	-5.03	-31.23	-31.07	-0.16	0.108

Table 6. PSS RE Power Analysis

Scenario Number	Set Power on Generator (dBm)	Theoretical SSS RE Power (dBm)	Measured SSS RE Power (dBm)	Difference of Theoretical Value and Measured Value (dB)	Standard Deviation of SSS RE Powers in a Subframe (dB)
1	-7.69	-38.94	-38.79	-0.15	0.014
2	-4.78	-36.03	-36.27	0.24	0.175
3	-7.71	-35.95	-35.82	-0.13	0.018
4	-5.04	-33.28	-33.45	0.17	0.160
21	-5.03	-31.23	-31.13	-0.10	0.105

Table 7. SSS RE Power Analysis

5.7.2 Power of PSS and SSS REs for the scenarios with fading

For the scenarios with fading, PSS and SSS RE Powers are also measured for three times and the analysis is performed similar to the scenarios without fading. The deviation between these measurements is analyzed for understanding the effect of fading for different cases. Table 8 and Table 9 present these results for PSS and SSS, respectively. It can be observed that fading causes a change in the detected RF power of REs as expected. The deviation in the power reached up to 10.68 dB in the measurements.

In order to visualize the effects of different fading characteristics, the heat maps of the whole resource grid are obtained for each scenario. These heat maps are given from Figure 8 to

Figure 17. Please note that these snapshots were taken from the resource grid region around the SSBs. REs of SSBs set to value 0 can be seen with rectangular shapes at the start of the resource grid, having the colour of dark red (representing very low power). These illustrations have the sole purpose of displaying the fading effects and does not include the detailed quantitative analysis.

Scenario Number	Measured PSS RE Power M1 (dBm)	Measured PSS RE Power M2 (dBm)	Measured PSS RE Power M3 (dBm)	Maximum Deviation between Measurements (dB)
5	-53.10	-46.64	-43.65	9.45
6	-40.58	-47.02	-46.20	6.44
7	-49.03	-49.66	-44.23	5.43
8	-41.43	-48.02	-39.28	8.74
9	-57.16	-51.87	-52.17	5.29
10	-51.70	-44.76	-45.19	6.94
11	-44.84	-48.20	-41.90	6.30
12	-39.76	-42.87	-43.02	3.26
13	-46.74	-51.86	-48.45	5.12
14	-53.74	-44.54	-43.06	10.68
15	-41.31	-46.07	-45.81	4.76
16	-48.23	-45.38	-47.34	2.85
17	-56.44	-48.59	-50.88	6.85
18	-42.82	-47.17	-44.68	4.35
19	-44.63	-48.47	-41.66	6.81
20	-41.62	-44.18	-43.68	2.56
22	-36.16	-34.68	-36.20	1.52
23	-43.03	-36.66	-38.56	6.37

Table 8. PSS REs Power Analysis for Scenarios with Fading

Scenario Number	Measured SSS RE Power M1 (dBm)	Measured SSS RE Power M2 (dBm)	Measured SSS RE Power M3 (dBm)	Maximum Deviation between Measurements (dB)
5	-53.10	-46.66	-43.62	9.48
6	-40.53	-47.12	-46.18	6.59
7	-48.94	-49.76	-44.21	5.55
8	-41.38	-47.89	-39.25	8.64
9	-57.05	-51.95	-52.07	5.10
10	-51.67	-44.67	-45.11	7.00
11	-44.91	-48.16	-41.94	6.22
12	-39.74	-42.94	-43.03	3.29
13	-47.02	-55.94	-49.06	8.92
14	-51.16	-44.91	-44.76	6.40
15	-41.68	-45.66	-45.68	4.00
16	-48.61	-45.11	-47.20	3.50
17	-56.58	-48.64	-50.85	7.94
18	-42.87	-47.09	-46.08	4.22
19	-44.73	-48.61	-41.74	6.87
20	-41.65	-43.76	-43.79	2.14
22	-36.18	-34.63	--36.25	1.62
23	-43.02	-36.72	-38.52	6.30

Table 9. SSS REs Power Analysis for Scenarios with Fading

Figure 8. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 5 (Left) and 6 (Right) (TDLA30-5 Fading)

Figure 9. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 7 (Left) and 8 (Right) (TDLA30-5 Fading)

Figure 10. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 9 (Left) and 10 (Right) (TDLA30-10 Fading)

Figure 11. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 11 (Left) and 12 (Right) (TDLA30-10 Fading)

Figure 12. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 13 (Left) and 14 (Right) (TDLB100-400 Fading)

Figure 13. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 15 (Left) and 16 (Right) (TDLB100-400 Fading)

Figure 14. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 17 (Left) and 18 (Right) (TDLB300-100 Fading)

Figure 15. Heat Maps for Resource Grid Power of Scenarios 19 (Left) and 20 (Right) (TDL300-100 Fading)

Figure 16. Heat Map for Resource Grid Power of Scenario 22 (TDLA30-75 Fading)

Figure 17. Heat Map for Resource Grid Power of Scenario 23 (TDLA30-300 Fading)

6 Measurement Uncertainty

6.1 Sources of Uncertainty

There are 6 influencing factors which contribute to the measurement uncertainty according to the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 [2].

1. Uncertainty of power reference: In the setup, two different calibrated power meters are used for establishing the SI traceability. In the calibration certificates of the power meters, the uncertainties of these power references are given. Depending on the type and the quality of the power meter, this uncertainty changes. It was found out that the power meter used for FR1 has lower standard uncertainty (0.025 dB) than the one used in FR2 (0.060 dB).
2. Uncertainty of antenna factor: 3 different antenna types were used in the measurements. The calibration certificates of these antennas showed that for the antenna factor (and therefore, antenna gain), the respective uncertainties are 0.85 dB and 0.50 dB for FR1 and FR2, respectively.
3. Resolution of oscilloscope: The oscilloscope used in the measurement chain has 8-bit resolution. The uncertainty in the voltage amplitude measured by the oscilloscope has a rectangular distribution with distribution factor of 1.73. The amount of the uncertainty is calculated as follows:

$$u_{\text{scope}}(\text{dB}) = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2 \times 2^8} \right) = 0.017 \text{ dB} \quad (5)$$

4. Frequency response of the measurement chain: The characterization of the measurement chain using conventional measurement methods such as a VNA or similar would yield the uncertainty contribution from the frequency response of the measurement chain. This effect includes also the broadband characteristics of the chain. In this application, a signal having a bandwidth up to 50 MHz is measured using the chain. The RF mixer and the bandpass filters do not have the same conversion loss throughout the band. This source of uncertainty also considers this factor. The values of 0.03 dB and 0.08 dB for FR1 and FR2 respectively are obtained from the calibration of the chain and the conversion loss characteristics of RF mixer and bandpass filters.
5. Stability of PSS/SSS measurements: This factor is obtained by the overestimation of the standard deviation of 100 different PSS/SSS measurements.

6. Reproducibility: This source of uncertainty has been investigated and the corresponding contribution of 0.01 dB has been found by repeating measurements for the decoding of the whole resource grid for the exact same configuration.

6.2 Calculation of Measurement Uncertainty Budgets for Different Frequencies

The calculation of the measurement uncertainty budget according to [2] for FR 1 and FR2 are given in Table 10 and Table 11, respectively.

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty (dB)	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.025	Normal	2	0.013
2	Uncertainty of antenna factor	0.850	Normal	2	0.425
3	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
4	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.030	Rectangular	1.73	0.017
5	Stability of PSS/SSS measurements	0.015	Normal	1	0.015
6	Reproducibility	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
Total (k=1)					0.426
Total (k=2)					0.852

Table 10. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for FR1 Measurements

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty (dB)	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty (dB)
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.060	Normal	2	0.030
2	Uncertainty of antenna factor	0.500	Normal	2	0.250
3	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
4	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.080	Rectangular	1.73	0.046
5	Stability of PSS/SSS measurements	0.015	Normal	1	0.015
6	Reproducibility	0.010	Normal	1	0.010
Total (k=1)					0.257
Total (k=2)					0.514

Table 11. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for FR2 MHz Measurements

6.3 Discussion on Measurement Uncertainty Budget

The measurement uncertainties reported in this document have been obtained by using the components given in Chapter 5. The calculations show that the goal measurement uncertainty of 0.5 dB (k=2) has been achieved for the measurements in FR2. For FR1, the uncertainty has increased due to the higher antenna factor uncertainty, which is the dominating component of the uncertainty budget.

In order to reduce the overall uncertainty of the measurements, this main influencing factor must be improved. The calibrations of log-per and rigged horn antennas have intrinsically higher uncertainties. Another type of antenna (such as a horn antenna) can be used in order to reduce the associated uncertainty.

7 References

- [1] Emrah Tas, "*Evaluation of the Reference On-the-Bench Experimental Setup*", 21NRM03 MEWS Activity number: A3.2.1, Version 2.0, May 16, 2024
- [2] JCGM 100:2008 (GUM), "*Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement*", First Edition, 2008.
- [3] Emrah Tas, "*Experimental On-The-Bench Setup for 5G NR IQ Waveforms*", 21NRM03 MEWS Activity number: A3.1.4, Version 1.0, January 31, 2024
- [4] Emrah Tas, "*Software Implementation of A3.1.2 for RF Power Detection of 5G NR Downlink Transmission Signals*", 21NRM03 MEWS Activity number: A3.1.3, Version 1.1, December 22, 2023

ANNEX E

21NRM03 MEWS - Metrology for emerging wireless standards

SI-Traceable Calibration of 5G Measuring Receivers

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21NRM03 MEWS Activity number: A3.2.3

Version: 1.0

Date: September 24, 2024

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1 Introduction

In this document, the measurement accuracy of two commercially available 5G measuring receivers are studied. The study is based on the metrological calibration of two different modes of the receivers, namely Level Recorder and 5G EMF.

For Level Recorder mode, the frequency and linearity accuracy are investigated similar to a measuring receiver without any decoding capabilities.

For 5G EMF mode, 4 selected scenarios, which are derived from 21NRM03 Activity 3.2.1, are applied and the accuracy of the measured power level of the resource elements (REs) associated with Secondary Synchronization Symbol (SSS) is examined using the measurement setup obtained in Activity 3.1.4. SI-Traceability of all the measurements is provided using a calibrated power meter.

2 Calibration Principles

2.1 Selected 5G Measuring Receiver Products

Two commercially available 5G measuring receivers are calibrated in this activity:

- 1) Deviser EM860 (with 5G Option)
- 2) Narda SRM 3006 (with 5G Option)

Figure 1. Selected 5G Measuring Receiver Products

2.2 Level Recorder Mode

The calibration of the receivers in level recorder mode is based on the well-established metrological calibration method which is based on continuous waves without any modulation and using the following components:

1. Two calibrated power meters
2. A calibrated programmable step attenuator
3. Signal Generator
4. Power Splitter
5. Cables

In the first step, the output power of the signal generator is measured with the setup shown in Figure 2 with a frequency sweep. The step attenuator is kept at 0 dB attenuation level. In the second step, the second power meter is replaced with the 5G measurement receiver and measured similarly for different attenuation values.

Figure 2. Calibration Setup for Level Recorder Mode

The corresponding corrections are performed for different attenuation values and the calibration of the 5G receiver in Level Recorder Mode is obtained for frequency spectrum and linearity.

2.3 5G NR EMF Mode

2.3.1 Measurement Setup

In order to assess the precision of the SSS power measurement capabilities of the 5G receiver under test, the method proposed in MEWS activity A3.1.4 is used (See Figure 3 and Figure 4) [1].

Figure 3. Calibration Setup for 5G EMF Mode

Figure 4. Hardware Module for 5G PSS and SSS Power Detection (LO: Local Oscillator)

In the first step, the output power of the 5G Generator is calibrated without modulation for the selected carrier frequencies. The generated power is measured both by the calibrated power meter and the hardware module. The correction due to the path loss between the power meter and the hardware module is also obtained. Then, in the second step, 5G signals of the selected scenarios are measured with the same setup. By this way, 5G signal power measurements of SSS symbols are obtained using the hardware module. The SI-traceability of these measurements is provided by using the correction factors obtained in step 1. In the third step, the measurements are repeated using 5G receiver under test and the corresponding difference is obtained as correction factor of the receiver reading.

2.3.2 Measurement Settings

The selected measurements settings are derived from MEWS Activity 3.2.1 where no fading was applied. The definitions of the settings are given in Table 1 below [2].

Settings Number	Numerology	Center Frequency (MHz)	Number of SSB	Channel Bandwidth (MHz)
1	0	800	4	20
2	0	3500	8	20
3	1	800	4	20
4	1	3500	8	20

Table 1. Selected Measurement Scenarios (SSB: Synchronization Symbol Block)

For the measurements, two selected measurands are

- 1) The average of the measured maximum SSS power (i.e., "Avg (SSS Max)")
- 2) The average of the measured summation of all SSS powers (i.e., "Avg (SSS Sum)")

For the selected settings, the difference between these measurands is expected to be

- 1) $10 \times \log_{10}4 = 6.02$ dB for Settings 1 and 3
- 2) $10 \times \log_{10}8 = 9.03$ dB for Settings 2 and 4

3 Calibration Results

The calibration results are provided in the form a calibration certificate attached to this report.

4 References

[1] Emrah Tas, "*Experimental On-The-Bench Setup for 5G NR IQ Waveforms*", 21NRM03
MEWS Activity number: A3.1.4, Version 1.0, January 31, 2024

[2] Emrah Tas, "*Evaluation of the Reference On-the-Bench Experimental Setup*", 21NRM03
MEWS Activity number: A3.2.1, Version 2.0, May 16, 2024

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

<i>Object</i>	Receiver for ONIR measurement Deviser EM860N S/N 3001231090, ID No. MM10199
<i>Order</i>	Calibration of the receiver for measurements related to protection against non-ionizing radiation
<i>Applicant</i>	Eidg. Institut für Metrologie METAS Lindenweg 50 3003 Bern-Wabern
<i>Traceability</i>	The reported measurement values are traceable to national standards and thus to internationally supported realisations of the SI units.
<i>Date of calibration</i>	02.08.2024 to 07.08.2024
<i>Marking</i>	-

3003 Bern-Wabern, 14 February 2025

For the Measurements Emrah Tas

Approved by Dr Frédéric Pythoud, Head of Laboratory
Laboratory EMC

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Extent of the calibration

Calibration of the measuring receiver:

1. Frequency sweep and linearity
 - from 30 MHz to 6 GHz
 - over 40 dB dynamic
 - in 4 measurements ranges: -25 dBm, -10 dBm, 5 dBm, 20 dBm
2. Reflection parameter
 - from 30 MHz to 6 GHz
 - receiver center frequency at the measurement frequency
 - in 4 measurements ranges: -25 dBm, -10 dBm, 5 dBm, 20 dBm
3. 5G NR code selective receiver at frequencies of 800 MHz and 3.5 GHz with 4 selected signals

Measurement procedure

The calibration has been performed against a calibrated signal generator.

Measurement conditions

Environmental conditions

Temperature: (23.0 ± 2.0) °C
Relative humidity: (45 ± 10) %

Measurement apparatus

Device	Manufacturer	Type	Inventory
Signal generator	Rohde&Schwarz	SMW 200A	7737
Signal generator	HP	80653A	372
Step attenuator	Agilent	8496H	9363
Power splitter	Weinschel Corporation	1870A	6765
Powermeter	Rohde&Schwarz	NRP-Z51	5874
Powermeter	Rohde&Schwarz	NRP-Z91	7135
Vector Network Analyzer	Rohde&Schwarz	ENA E5080A	8160
TOSM Calibration Kit N 50 Ω	Rohde&Schwarz	ZV-Z21	4112
Type-N Calibration Kit, Option 500	Agilent	85032F	5344

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Device	Manufacturer	Type	Inventory
Oscilloscope	Agilent	Infiniium DSO90254A	6587
Frequency Mixer	Mini-Circuits	ZX05-43LH-S+	8124
Bandpass Filter	Mini-Circuits	ZX75LP-83-S+	8120

Measurement results

For the frequency sweep measurements, the DUT was calibrated with a CW signal.

The DUT setup:

Measuring mode	Level recorder
Measuring range	See table header
Resolution bandwidth	100 kHz

The following tables report the correction (value to be added) that has to be applied to the reading in order to get the correct signal power.

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range -25 dBm

Input Signal Frequency ()	Correction in the range -25dBm					Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
	-30dBm	-40dBm	-50dBm	-60dBm	-70dBm	
	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	
30 MHz	0.00	-0.07	-0.09	-0.07	-0.20	0.2 dB from -30 dBm to -70 dBm
50 MHz	-0.04	-0.10	-0.12	-0.11	-0.23	
70 MHz	-0.12	-0.17	-0.19	-0.17	-0.30	
100 MHz	-0.11	-0.15	-0.18	-0.17	-0.31	
200 MHz	-0.13	-0.18	-0.15	-0.19	-0.35	
400 MHz	-0.12	-0.17	-0.18	-0.17	-0.33	
600 MHz	-0.21	-0.22	-0.24	-0.24	-0.42	
800 MHz	-0.06	-0.08	-0.11	-0.11	-0.32	
1.0 GHz	-0.13	-0.08	-0.10	-0.10	-0.33	
1.2 GHz	0.03	0.02	-0.01	0.01	-0.26	
1.4 GHz	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.03	-0.29	
1.6 GHz	-0.11	-0.07	-0.08	-0.08	-0.45	
1.8 GHz	-0.14	-0.09	-0.12	-0.14	-0.50	
2.0 GHz	-0.25	-0.20	-0.23	-0.24	-0.59	
2.2 GHz	-0.32	-0.34	-0.35	-0.36	-0.80	
2.4 GHz	-0.36	-0.32	-0.32	-0.37	-0.97	
2.6 GHz	-0.37	-0.31	-0.35	-0.38	-1.06	
2.8 GHz	-0.16	-0.08	-0.12	-0.16	-0.91	
3.0 GHz	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.06	-0.37	
3.2 GHz	-0.18	-0.17	-0.17	-0.20	-0.60	
3.4 GHz	-0.29	-0.24	-0.26	-0.26	-0.66	
3.6 GHz	-0.32	-0.27	-0.29	-0.29	-0.72	
3.8 GHz	-0.08	-0.01	-0.04	-0.03	-0.53	
4.0 GHz	-0.23	-0.18	-0.20	-0.22	-0.83	
4.2 GHz	-0.30	-0.26	-0.25	-0.31	-0.94	
4.4 GHz	-0.35	-0.31	-0.32	-0.37	-1.05	
4.6 GHz	-0.38	-0.38	-0.34	-0.36	-1.10	
4.8 GHz	-0.28	-0.22	-0.25	-0.29	-1.14	
5.0 GHz	-0.54	-0.53	-0.49	-0.57	-1.44	
5.2 GHz	-0.48	-0.43	-0.45	-0.52	-1.39	
5.4 GHz	-0.46	-0.48	-0.42	-0.50	-1.43	
5.6 GHz	-0.15	-0.11	-0.10	-0.23	-1.44	
5.8 GHz	-0.72	-0.69	-0.67	-0.76	-2.16	
6.0 GHz	-0.60	-0.55	-0.57	-0.69	-2.51	

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range -10 dBm

Input Signal Frequency ()	Correction in the range -10dBm					Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	-40dBm	-50dBm	
	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	
30 MHz	-0.11	-0.20	-0.17	-0.22	-0.29	0.2 dB from -10 dBm to -50 dBm
50 MHz	-0.13	-0.20	-0.19	-0.22	-0.29	
70 MHz	-0.18	-0.25	-0.22	-0.24	-0.32	
100 MHz	-0.17	-0.24	-0.27	-0.23	-0.30	
200 MHz	-0.20	-0.25	-0.28	-0.26	-0.33	
400 MHz	-0.21	-0.27	-0.22	-0.25	-0.32	
600 MHz	-0.29	-0.33	-0.36	-0.31	-0.42	
800 MHz	-0.28	-0.32	-0.34	-0.30	-0.40	
1.0 GHz	-0.21	-0.26	-0.26	-0.28	-0.31	
1.2 GHz	-0.15	-0.19	-0.19	-0.22	-0.26	
1.4 GHz	-0.10	-0.15	-0.14	-0.11	-0.23	
1.6 GHz	-0.25	-0.28	-0.29	-0.31	-0.41	
1.8 GHz	-0.21	-0.25	-0.25	-0.20	-0.36	
2.0 GHz	-0.32	-0.35	-0.36	-0.39	-0.46	
2.2 GHz	-0.50	-0.53	-0.52	-0.56	-0.65	
2.4 GHz	-0.48	-0.49	-0.49	-0.48	-0.71	
2.6 GHz	-0.49	-0.51	-0.51	-0.53	-0.72	
2.8 GHz	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.32	-0.55	
3.0 GHz	-0.20	-0.20	-0.22	-0.20	-0.29	
3.2 GHz	-0.30	-0.35	-0.33	-0.40	-0.40	
3.4 GHz	-0.38	-0.43	-0.41	-0.44	-0.45	
3.6 GHz	-0.46	-0.48	-0.48	-0.50	-0.52	
3.8 GHz	-0.25	-0.27	-0.29	-0.29	-0.34	
4.0 GHz	-0.33	-0.31	-0.35	-0.37	-0.45	
4.2 GHz	-0.46	-0.55	-0.48	-0.55	-0.60	
4.4 GHz	-0.44	-0.47	-0.45	-0.50	-0.56	
4.6 GHz	-0.44	-0.43	-0.44	-0.46	-0.54	
4.8 GHz	-0.38	-0.37	-0.38	-0.41	-0.52	
5.0 GHz	-0.51	-0.50	-0.51	-0.54	-0.71	
5.2 GHz	-0.62	-0.60	-0.61	-0.64	-0.75	
5.4 GHz	-0.53	-0.52	-0.51	-0.55	-0.66	
5.6 GHz	-0.22	-0.24	-0.22	-0.28	-0.41	
5.8 GHz	-0.74	-0.69	-0.71	-0.74	-0.96	
6.0 GHz	-0.76	-0.66	-0.71	-0.73	-1.05	

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range 5 dBm

Input Signal	0dBm	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	-40dBm	Uncertainty
Frequency	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	(k=2)
()	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)
30 MHz	-0.08	-0.08	-0.07	-0.11	-0.26	0.2 dB from 0 dBm to -40 dBm
50 MHz	-0.02	-0.08	-0.07	-0.11	-0.27	
70 MHz	-0.15	-0.18	-0.17	-0.21	-0.36	
100 MHz	-0.10	-0.14	-0.13	-0.16	-0.34	
200 MHz	-0.03	-0.09	-0.08	-0.12	-0.29	
400 MHz	-0.11	-0.14	-0.12	-0.16	-0.34	
600 MHz	-0.19	-0.23	-0.19	-0.23	-0.45	
800 MHz	-0.12	-0.17	-0.20	-0.18	-0.38	
1.0 GHz	-0.11	-0.13	-0.17	-0.15	-0.37	
1.2 GHz	0.02	-0.01	0.03	-0.04	-0.29	
1.4 GHz	0.11	0.07	0.04	0.05	-0.28	
1.6 GHz	-0.07	-0.09	-0.13	-0.13	-0.52	
1.8 GHz	-0.10	-0.13	-0.17	-0.17	-0.51	
2.0 GHz	-0.22	-0.25	-0.21	-0.27	-0.60	
2.2 GHz	-0.36	-0.39	-0.42	-0.48	-0.81	
2.4 GHz	-0.37	-0.38	-0.40	-0.43	-1.07	
2.6 GHz	-0.40	-0.43	-0.45	-0.48	-1.10	
2.8 GHz	-0.17	-0.21	-0.23	-0.32	-0.92	
3.0 GHz	-0.06	-0.10	-0.09	-0.08	-0.38	
3.2 GHz	-0.19	-0.25	-0.29	-0.25	-0.48	
3.4 GHz	-0.35	-0.37	-0.39	-0.41	-0.54	
3.6 GHz	-0.36	-0.38	-0.38	-0.43	-0.57	
3.8 GHz	-0.05	-0.17	-0.14	-0.23	-0.39	
4.0 GHz	-0.28	-0.26	-0.27	-0.33	-0.61	
4.2 GHz	-0.43	-0.41	-0.49	-0.50	-0.85	
4.4 GHz	-0.43	-0.44	-0.48	-0.52	-0.85	
4.6 GHz	-0.44	-0.44	-0.43	-0.52	-0.83	
4.8 GHz	-0.34	-0.38	-0.38	-0.47	-0.89	
5.0 GHz	-0.56	-0.56	-0.60	-0.67	-1.18	
5.2 GHz	-0.61	-0.62	-0.65	-0.72	-1.15	
5.4 GHz	-0.61	-0.57	-0.59	-0.66	-1.12	
5.6 GHz	-0.36	-0.34	-0.40	-0.47	-1.17	
5.8 GHz	-0.79	-0.81	-0.81	-0.92	-1.62	
6.0 GHz	-0.75	-0.75	-0.71	-0.90	-1.77	

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Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

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Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range 20 dBm

Input Signal	Correction in the range 20dBm				Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
	0dBm	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	
Frequency ()	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	
30 MHz	-0.05	-0.06	-0.06	-0.43	0.2 dB from 0 dBm to -30 dBm
50 MHz	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.40	
70 MHz	-0.10	-0.09	-0.10	-0.47	
100 MHz	-0.09	-0.09	-0.11	-0.49	
200 MHz	-0.15	-0.14	-0.15	-0.55	
400 MHz	-0.04	-0.02	-0.04	-0.45	
600 MHz	-0.15	-0.13	-0.17	-0.63	
800 MHz	-0.15	-0.13	-0.16	-0.65	
1.0 GHz	-0.07	-0.05	-0.11	-0.63	
1.2 GHz	0.07	0.07	0.03	-0.62	
1.4 GHz	0.13	0.14	0.07	-0.73	
1.6 GHz	-0.04	-0.04	-0.12	-1.04	
1.8 GHz	-0.02	-0.02	-0.09	-0.95	
2.0 GHz	-0.15	-0.14	-0.20	-1.00	
2.2 GHz	-0.31	-0.29	-0.39	-1.32	
2.4 GHz	-0.22	-0.21	-0.40	-1.94	
2.6 GHz	-0.24	-0.27	-0.45	-2.02	
2.8 GHz	-0.07	-0.09	-0.28	-2.01	
3.0 GHz	0.08	0.06	0.04	-0.68	
3.2 GHz	-0.10	-0.11	-0.18	-0.74	
3.4 GHz	-0.25	-0.15	-0.25	-0.69	
3.6 GHz	-0.27	-0.25	-0.31	-0.84	
3.8 GHz	0.11	0.09	0.00	-0.73	
4.0 GHz	-0.10	-0.06	-0.20	-1.17	
4.2 GHz	-0.30	-0.20	-0.42	-1.46	
4.4 GHz	-0.24	-0.25	-0.44	-1.51	
4.6 GHz	-0.21	-0.21	-0.36	-1.66	
4.8 GHz	-0.16	-0.20	-0.43	-1.90	
5.0 GHz	-0.31	-0.33	-0.60	-2.37	
5.2 GHz	-0.38	-0.40	-0.62	-2.14	
5.4 GHz	-0.36	-0.31	-0.57	-2.17	
5.6 GHz	-0.05	-0.08	-0.47	-2.74	
5.8 GHz	-0.53	-0.60	-0.95	-3.27	
6.0 GHz	-0.55	-0.61	-0.99	-3.81	

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03577

Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

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5G code selective receiver

The 5G code selective receiver is calibrated with 4 different signals. These are 5G test signals whose components are listed in the following table (SSB: Synchronization Symbol Block).

Signal Number	Numerology	Center Frequency (MHz)	Number of SSB	Channel Bandwidth (MHz)
1	0	800	4	20
2	0	3500	8	20
3	1	800	4	20
4	1	3500	8	20

The DUT setup:

Measuring mode	5G NR EMF
Measuring range	Auto
Unit	dBm
Automatic Gain Control (AGC)	On
SSS Block Pattern	Case A for Signal Number 1 and 3 Case B for Signal Number 2 and 4
Subcarrier Spacing (SCS)	15 kHz for Signal Number 1 and 3 30 kHz for Signal Number 2 and 4
Channel Bandwidth	20 MHz

For each of these signals, the following values are reported:

1. the set signal power on the 5G NR signal generator
2. the "SSS power" value measured with the calibrated METAS setup
3. the "Avg (SSS Max)" value measured by the DUT
4. and "Avg (SSS Sum)" value measured by the DUT
5. the difference between the measured value "Avg (SSS Max)" and the expected value "SSS power", and its uncertainty.

Signal Number	Signal power (dBm)	SSS power (dBm)	Measured Avg (SSS Max) (dBm)	Measured Avg (SSS Sum) (dBm)	Difference (dB)	Expanded uncertainty (dB)
1	-14.69	-53.51	-53.83	-47.81	0.32	0.05
2	-14.78	-54.42	-54.63	-45.61	0.21	
3	-14.71	-50.74	-50.76	-44.74	0.02	
4	-15.04	-51.76	-51.82	-42.80	0.06	

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Signal Number	Expected Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum (dB)	Measured Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum (dB)	Difference	Expanded uncertainty (dB)
1	6.02	6.02	0.00	0.05 dB
2	9.03	9.02	0.01	
3	6.02	6.02	0.00	
4	9.03	9.02	0.01	

Uncertainty of measurement

The reported uncertainty of measurement is stated as the combined standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$. The measured value (y) and the associated expanded uncertainty (U) represent the interval ($y \pm U$) which contains the value of the measured quantity with a probability of approximately 95%. The uncertainty was estimated following the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 (GUM).

The measurement uncertainty contains contributions originating from the measurement standard, from the calibration method, from the environmental conditions and from the object being calibrated. The long-term characteristic of the object being calibrated is not included.

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<i>Object</i>	Receiver for ONIR measurement Narda SRM-3006 S/N UNDISCLOSED
<i>Order</i>	Calibration of the receiver for measurements related to protection against non-ionizing radiation
<i>Applicant</i>	UNDISCLOSED
<i>Traceability</i>	The reported measurement values are traceable to national standards and thus to internationally supported realisations of the SI units.
<i>Date of calibration</i>	13.08.2024 to 15.08.2024
<i>Marking</i>	Calibration label METAS 08.2024

3003 Bern-Wabern, 14 February 2025

For the Measurements Emrah Tas

Approved by Dr Frédéric Pythoud, Head of Laboratory
Laboratory EMC

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03622

Extent of the calibration

Calibration of the measuring receiver:

1. Frequency sweep and linearity
 - from 30 MHz to 6 GHz
 - over 50 dB dynamic
 - in 4 measurements ranges: -25 dBm, -10 dBm, 5 dBm, 20 dBm
2. Reflection parameter
 - from 30 MHz to 6 GHz
 - receiver center frequency at the measurement frequency
 - in 4 measurements ranges: -25 dBm, -10 dBm, 5 dBm, 20 dBm
3. 5G NR code selective receiver at frequencies of 800 MHz and 3.5 GHz with 4 selected signals

Measurement procedure

The calibration has been performed against a calibrated signal generator.

Measurement conditions

Environmental conditions

Temperature: (23.0 ± 2.0) °C
Relative humidity: (45 ± 10) %

Measurement apparatus

Device	Manufacturer	Type	Inventory
Signal generator	Rohde&Schwarz	SMW 200A	7737
Signal generator	HP	80653A	372
Step attenuator	Agilent	8496H	9363
Power splitter	Weinschel Corporation	1870A	6765
Powermeter	Rohde&Schwarz	NRP-Z51	5874
Powermeter	Rohde&Schwarz	NRP-Z91	7135
Vector Network Analyzer	Rohde&Schwarz	ENA E5080A	8160
TOSM Calibration Kit N 50 Ω	Rohde&Schwarz	ZV-Z21	4112
Type-N Calibration Kit, Option 500	Agilent	85032F	5344

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Device	Manufacturer	Type	Inventory
Oscilloscope	Agilent	Infiniium DSO90254A	6587
Frequency Mixer	Mini-Circuits	ZX05-43LH-S+	8124
Bandpass Filter	Mini-Circuits	ZX75LP-83-S+	8120

Measurement results

For the frequency sweep measurements, the DUT was calibrated with a CW signal.

The DUT setup:

Measuring mode	Level recorder
Measuring range	See table header
Resolution bandwidth	100 kHz

The following tables report the correction (value to be added) that has to be applied to the reading in order to get the correct signal power.

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03622

Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range -25 dBm

Input Signal	Correction in the range -25dBm						Uncertainty (k=2) (dB)
	-30dBm	-40dBm	-50dBm	-60dBm	-70dBm	-80dBm	
Frequency ()	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	
30 MHz	-0.35	-0.37	-0.34	-0.31	-0.27	-0.26	0.2 dB from -30dBm to -70dBm 0.5 dB for -80dBm
50 MHz	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.14	0.18	0.18	
70 MHz	0.00	-0.01	0.02	-0.04	-0.06	-0.22	
100 MHz	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	-0.05	-0.07	-0.26	
200 MHz	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.03	0.00	-0.02	
400 MHz	0.10	0.08	0.10	0.03	-0.01	-0.14	
600 MHz	0.02	0.02	0.05	-0.01	-0.06	-0.16	
800 MHz	0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.03	-0.07	-0.26	
1.0 GHz	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.02	-0.03	-0.20	
1.2 GHz	0.15	0.14	0.15	0.08	0.02	-0.27	
1.4 GHz	-0.06	-0.08	-0.04	-0.10	-0.13	-0.26	
1.6 GHz	-0.04	-0.05	-0.02	-0.08	-0.15	-0.58	
1.8 GHz	0.04	0.04	0.05	-0.01	-0.08	-0.46	
2.0 GHz	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	-0.06	-0.09	-0.24	
2.2 GHz	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01	-0.06	-0.11	-0.33	
2.4 GHz	-0.05	-0.05	-0.05	-0.09	-0.12	-0.32	
2.6 GHz	-0.05	-0.07	-0.04	-0.10	-0.12	-0.29	
2.8 GHz	-0.08	-0.08	-0.07	-0.10	-0.15	-0.35	
3.0 GHz	0.11	0.11	0.10	0.05	0.00	-0.13	
3.2 GHz	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.04	-0.09	-0.18	
3.4 GHz	0.05	0.03	0.04	-0.03	-0.07	-0.23	
3.6 GHz	-0.02	-0.03	-0.04	-0.09	-0.14	-0.38	
3.8 GHz	0.06	0.05	0.03	-0.02	-0.07	-0.34	
4.0 GHz	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.02	-0.05	-0.33	
4.2 GHz	-0.11	-0.11	-0.11	-0.16	-0.19	-0.44	
4.4 GHz	-0.10	-0.10	-0.12	-0.16	-0.22	-0.65	
4.6 GHz	-0.06	-0.06	-0.09	-0.13	-0.21	-0.71	
4.8 GHz	-0.07	-0.08	-0.10	-0.15	-0.23	-1.03	
5.0 GHz	0.12	0.11	0.05	0.01	-0.12	-1.05	
5.2 GHz	-0.08	-0.08	-0.12	-0.15	-0.24	-0.73	
5.4 GHz	-0.22	-0.20	-0.22	-0.24	-0.32	-0.81	
5.6 GHz	-0.23	-0.24	-0.24	-0.30	-0.34	-0.79	
5.8 GHz	-0.22	-0.21	-0.22	-0.27	-0.33	-0.85	
6.0 GHz	-0.32	-0.32	-0.32	-0.34	-0.36	-0.52	

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Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

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Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range -10 dBm

Input Signal	Correction in the range -10dBm						Uncertainty (k=2)
	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	-40dBm	-50dBm	-60dBm	
Frequency ()	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	(dB)
30 MHz	-0.23	-0.22	-0.22	-0.21	-0.20	-0.16	0.2 dB from -10dBm to -50dBm 0.5 dB for -60dBm
50 MHz	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.34	0.39	0.41	
70 MHz	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.00	-0.06	
100 MHz	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.01	-0.03	-0.11	
200 MHz	0.11	0.10	0.10	0.07	0.04	0.01	
400 MHz	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.05	-0.01	
600 MHz	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.02	-0.04	
800 MHz	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.01	-0.04	
1.0 GHz	0.12	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.03	-0.06	
1.2 GHz	0.16	0.15	0.13	0.10	0.06	-0.07	
1.4 GHz	0.02	0.01	0.02	-0.01	-0.04	-0.11	
1.6 GHz	0.03	0.02	0.03	-0.01	-0.04	-0.19	
1.8 GHz	0.08	0.09	0.07	0.04	-0.01	-0.21	
2.0 GHz	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.02	-0.02	-0.08	
2.2 GHz	0.02	0.01	0.02	-0.02	-0.05	-0.14	
2.4 GHz	0.02	0.00	0.01	-0.03	-0.05	-0.15	
2.6 GHz	0.01	0.01	0.01	-0.03	-0.05	-0.12	
2.8 GHz	-0.02	0.00	-0.01	-0.04	-0.07	-0.15	
3.0 GHz	0.03	0.01	0.01	-0.03	-0.06	-0.12	
3.2 GHz	0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.03	-0.06	-0.11	
3.4 GHz	0.02	0.02	0.01	-0.03	-0.05	-0.12	
3.6 GHz	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03	-0.08	-0.11	-0.18	
3.8 GHz	0.05	0.05	0.04	-0.01	-0.04	-0.13	
4.0 GHz	0.03	0.01	0.01	-0.04	-0.08	-0.17	
4.2 GHz	-0.09	-0.09	-0.09	-0.12	-0.15	-0.23	
4.4 GHz	-0.08	-0.09	-0.09	-0.13	-0.16	-0.30	
4.6 GHz	-0.08	-0.10	-0.10	-0.14	-0.18	-0.33	
4.8 GHz	-0.08	-0.10	-0.09	-0.13	-0.17	-0.43	
5.0 GHz	0.05	0.05	0.01	-0.02	-0.08	-0.39	
5.2 GHz	-0.11	-0.09	-0.13	-0.15	-0.20	-0.34	
5.4 GHz	-0.18	-0.17	-0.18	-0.19	-0.24	-0.37	
5.6 GHz	-0.17	-0.18	-0.17	-0.20	-0.23	-0.39	
5.8 GHz	-0.14	-0.17	-0.16	-0.20	-0.22	-0.41	
6.0 GHz	-0.24	-0.23	-0.23	-0.25	-0.28	-0.34	

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Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

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Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range 5 dBm

Input Signal	Correction in the range 5dBm						Uncertainty
	0dBm	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	-40dBm	-50dBm	
Frequency	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	Corr.	(k=2)
()	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)	(dB)
30 MHz	-0.40	-0.40	-0.38	-0.38	-0.39	-0.38	0.2 dB from 0dBm to -40dBm 0.5 dB for -50dBm
50 MHz	-0.12	-0.13	-0.10	-0.06	-0.04	-0.04	
70 MHz	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.07	-0.06	
100 MHz	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.09	0.05	-0.06	
200 MHz	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.10	0.06	
400 MHz	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.15	0.11	-0.05	
600 MHz	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.08	-0.04	
800 MHz	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.07	-0.02	
1.0 GHz	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.08	-0.13	
1.2 GHz	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.06	-0.24	
1.4 GHz	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.02	-0.10	
1.6 GHz	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.01	-0.25	
1.8 GHz	0.14	0.12	0.13	0.10	0.02	-0.57	
2.0 GHz	0.11	0.10	0.12	0.09	0.06	-0.14	
2.2 GHz	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.00	-0.24	
2.4 GHz	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.04	-0.01	-0.22	
2.6 GHz	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.04	-0.01	-0.20	
2.8 GHz	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.01	-0.23	
3.0 GHz	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.01	-0.10	
3.2 GHz	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	-0.05	-0.14	
3.4 GHz	0.00	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	-0.07	-0.19	
3.6 GHz	-0.02	-0.03	-0.02	-0.04	-0.10	-0.27	
3.8 GHz	0.01	0.01	0.01	-0.02	-0.08	-0.26	
4.0 GHz	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.04	-0.09	-0.33	
4.2 GHz	-0.06	-0.04	-0.05	-0.06	-0.10	-0.27	
4.4 GHz	-0.08	-0.07	-0.07	-0.09	-0.14	-0.47	
4.6 GHz	-0.05	-0.06	-0.09	-0.10	-0.16	-0.54	
4.8 GHz	-0.06	-0.03	-0.06	-0.07	-0.14	-0.70	
5.0 GHz	0.01	0.04	0.03	-0.02	-0.10	-0.73	
5.2 GHz	-0.03	-0.08	-0.07	-0.12	-0.16	-0.54	
5.4 GHz	-0.05	-0.08	-0.09	-0.11	-0.13	-0.49	
5.6 GHz	-0.15	-0.07	-0.10	-0.09	-0.14	-0.45	
5.8 GHz	-0.04	-0.04	-0.08	-0.08	-0.15	-0.53	
6.0 GHz	-0.14	-0.13	-0.14	-0.14	-0.18	-0.29	

Certificate of calibration No. 218-03622

Note: The complete dataset is available in electronic format

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Frequency sweep, linearity and reflection in the range 20 dBm

Input Signal	Correction in the range 20dBm					Uncertainty (k=2)
	-0dBm	-10dBm	-20dBm	-30dBm	-40dBm	
Frequency ()	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	Corr. (dB)	(dB)
30 MHz	-0.41	-0.41	-0.43	-0.40	-0.43	0.2 dB from 0dBm to -40dBm
50 MHz	-0.11	-0.08	-0.07	-0.06	-0.09	
70 MHz	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.02	-0.08	
100 MHz	0.09	0.09	0.10	0.00	-0.29	
200 MHz	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.08	-0.05	
400 MHz	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.06	-0.31	
600 MHz	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.05	-0.25	
800 MHz	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.05	-0.30	
1.0 GHz	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.03	-0.46	
1.2 GHz	0.10	0.10	0.09	-0.03	-0.86	
1.4 GHz	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.02	-0.38	
1.6 GHz	0.08	0.08	0.07	-0.01	-0.76	
1.8 GHz	0.11	0.10	0.07	-0.16	-1.73	
2.0 GHz	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.00	-0.51	
2.2 GHz	0.07	0.06	0.02	-0.06	-0.73	
2.4 GHz	0.02	0.05	0.02	-0.05	-0.74	
2.6 GHz	0.05	0.03	0.03	-0.06	-0.62	
2.8 GHz	0.07	0.06	0.04	-0.06	-0.76	
3.0 GHz	0.05	0.04	0.02	-0.02	-0.32	
3.2 GHz	-0.02	-0.02	-0.04	-0.08	-0.31	
3.4 GHz	-0.03	-0.03	-0.05	-0.10	-0.44	
3.6 GHz	-0.06	-0.07	-0.09	-0.15	-0.61	
3.8 GHz	-0.04	-0.05	-0.06	-0.14	-0.63	
4.0 GHz	-0.06	-0.07	-0.10	-0.17	-0.73	
4.2 GHz	-0.07	-0.06	-0.09	-0.13	-0.59	
4.4 GHz	-0.08	-0.08	-0.11	-0.21	-1.10	
4.6 GHz	-0.07	-0.08	-0.14	-0.24	-1.15	
4.8 GHz	-0.07	-0.05	-0.11	-0.28	-1.71	
5.0 GHz	-0.04	-0.02	-0.05	-0.25	-1.63	
5.2 GHz	-0.06	-0.11	-0.12	-0.27	-1.11	
5.4 GHz	-0.04	-0.08	-0.12	-0.23	-1.14	
5.6 GHz	-0.14	-0.06	-0.12	-0.22	-0.97	
5.8 GHz	-0.03	-0.04	-0.10	-0.22	-1.40	
6.0 GHz	-0.11	-0.09	-0.13	-0.18	-0.51	

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5G code selective receiver

The 5G code selective receiver is calibrated with 4 different signals. These are 5G test signals whose components are listed in the following table (SSB: Synchronization Symbol Block).

Signal Number	Numerology	Center Frequency (MHz)	Number of SSB	Channel Bandwidth (MHz)
1	0	800	4	20
2	0	3500	8	20
3	1	800	4	20
4	1	3500	8	20

The DUT setup:

Measuring mode	5G NR EMF
Measuring range	Auto
Unit	dBm
Automatic Gain Control (AGC)	On
SSS Block Pattern	Case A for Signal Number 1 and 3 Case B for Signal Number 2 and 4
Subcarrier Spacing (SCS)	15 kHz for Signal Number 1 and 3 30 kHz for Signal Number 2 and 4
Channel Bandwidth	20 MHz

For each of these signals, the following values are reported:

1. the set signal power on the 5G NR signal generator
2. the "SSS power" value measured with the calibrated METAS setup
3. the "Avg (SSS Max)" value measured by the DUT
4. and "Avg (SSS Sum)" value measured by the DUT
5. the difference between the measured value "Avg (SSS Max)" and the expected value "SSS power", and its uncertainty.

Signal Number	Signal power (dBm)	SSS power (dBm)	Measured Avg (SSS Max) (dBm)	Measured Avg (SSS Sum) (dBm)	Difference (dB)	Expanded uncertainty (dB)
1	-14.69	-52.45	-52.93	-47.11	0.48	0.05
2	-14.78	-53.42	-53.21	-44.50	-0.21	
3	-14.71	-49.46	-49.80	-43.88	0.34	
4	-15.04	-50.73	-50.43	-41.59	-0.30	

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Signal Number	Expected Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum (dB)	Measured Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum (dB)	Difference	Expanded uncertainty (dB)
1	6.02	5.82	0.20	0.05 dB
2	9.03	8.71	0.32	
3	6.02	5.92	0.10	
4	9.03	8.84	0.19	

Uncertainty of measurement

The reported uncertainty of measurement is stated as the combined standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$. The measured value (y) and the associated expanded uncertainty (U) represent the interval ($y \pm U$) which contains the value of the measured quantity with a probability of approximately 95%. The uncertainty was estimated following the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 (GUM).

The measurement uncertainty contains contributions originating from the measurement standard, from the calibration method, from the environmental conditions and from the object being calibrated. The long-term characteristic of the object being calibrated is not included.